

WHO Guidelines for malaria

Systematic reviews, background papers and other unpublished evidence considered in the development of recommendations

Prevention/Vector control

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Title

Effectiveness of dual active ingredient insecticide-treated nets in preventing malaria: a systematic review and meta-analysis

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This systematic review was reviewed by the Guideline Development Group on Malaria Vector Control, convened by the World Health Organization Global Malaria Programme to support the development of recommendations included in the *WHO Guidelines for malaria*. It is being made publicly available for transparency purposes and information, in accordance with the *WHO handbook for guideline development, 2nd edition (2014)*.

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Effectiveness of dual active ingredient insecticide-treated nets in preventing malaria: a systematic review and meta-analysis

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Summary

Background

Malaria vectors have demonstrated resistance to pyrethroid-based insecticides used in insecticide-treated nets, diminishing their effectiveness. This systematic review and meta-analysis investigated two forms of dual active-ingredient (DAI) insecticide-treated nets (ITN(s)) for malaria prevention.

Methods

A comprehensive search was conducted on July 6th 2022. The databases searched included PubMed, Embase, CINAHL, amongst others. Trials were eligible if they were conducted in a region with ongoing malaria transmission. The first DAI ITN investigated were those that combined a pyrethroid with a non-pyrethroid insecticides. The second DAI ITN investigated were that combined a pyrethroid with an insect growth regulator. These interventions were compared against either a pyrethroid-only ITN, or ITNs treated with pyrethroid and piperonyl-butoxide.

Assessment of risk of bias was conducted in duplicate using the Cochrane risk of bias 2 tool for cluster-randomised trials. Summary data was extracted using a custom data-extraction instrument. This was conducted by authors THB, JCS and SH. Malaria case incidence was the primary outcome and has been meta-analysed, adverse events were narratively synthesised. The review protocol is registered on PROSPERO (CRD42022333044).

Findings

From 9494 records, 48 reports were screened and 13 reports for three studies were included. These studies contained data from 186 clusters and all reported a low risk of bias. Compared to pyrethroid-only ITNs, clusters that received pyrethroid-non-pyrethroid DAI ITNs were associated with 190 fewer cases per 1000-person years (224 fewer to 149 fewer). Clusters that received pyrethroid-insect growth regulator ITNs were associated with 145 fewer cases per 1000-person years (197 fewer to 83 fewer). Similar findings were observed for clusters that received intervention nets compared to those that received pyrethroid-piperonyl-butoxide nets.

Interpretation

DAI ITNs demonstrated consistent reductions in malaria case incidence and other outcomes across multiple comparisons. DAI ITNs present a novel intervention for the control of malaria.

Funding

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Panel: Research in context

Evidence before this study

This review conducted a comprehensive search for controlled clinical trials across PubMed (NCBI), Embase (Ovid), CINAHL with Full Text (EBSCO), Cochrane Library (Wiley), clinicaltrials.gov, WHO ICTRP (International Clinical Trials Registry Platform), and the ISRCTN (International Standard Randomised Controlled Trial Number) Trial Registry. Studies were included where they had been conducted in residents of an area with ongoing malaria transmission with the intervention of interest being dual active-ingredient (DAI) insecticide-treated nets (ITNs). DAI ITNs were eligible where they had been treated with either, a pyrethroid and non-pyrethroid insecticide or a pyrethroid insecticide and an insect growth regulator. These interventions were compared against either pyrethroid-only ITNs or ITNs that combined a pyrethroid insecticide with piperonyl-butoxide. The only exclusion criteria were studies that contained no epidemiological outcome data (e.g. entomological studies, modelling studies). Three studies were included in this review, all of which were judged to be a low risk of bias.

Added value of this study

This is the first systematic review to investigate the effectiveness of dual active-ingredient insecticide-treated nets compared to pyrethroid-only insecticide-treated nets or pyrethroid and piperonyl-butoxide insecticide-treated nets. This review contains multiple synthesised effect estimates combining data from three individual studies as to the effectiveness of dual active-ingredient nets to prevent and control malaria in the context of increasing insecticide resistance. Certainty in the evidence was assessed following the GRADE approach, and these findings were associated with mainly high or moderate certainty.

Implications of all the available evidence

The results of this review have been used to inform the first recommendations for dual active-ingredient insecticide-treated nets made by the WHO Global Malaria Programme. This review has also identified that future primary research can be conducted in settings with varying transmission intensity and for greater than 2-years to investigate the robustness of the findings.

Summary of Findings

Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to pyrethroid-only ITNs for prevention of malaria

Certainty assessment							Summary of findings				
Participants (studies) Follow-up	Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Publication bias	Overall certainty of evidence	Study event rates (%)		Relative effect (95% CI)	Anticipated absolute effects	
							With Pyrethroid-only nets	With Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid nets		Risk with Pyrethroid-only nets	Risk difference with Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid nets

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

2000-person years (2 RCTs) Length of time observed: <1 month to 24 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (1 study)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High ^{a,b}	677.58 cases over 1000-person years (67.8%)	355.44 cases over 1000-person years (35.5%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.52 (0.48 to 0.57)	678 cases per 1,000-person years	190 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 224 fewer cases to 149 fewer cases) ^c
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Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post-intervention)

2000-person years (2 RCTs) Length of time observed: <1 month to 12 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (1 study)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High ^{d,e}	485.52 cases over 1000-person years (48.5%)	213.01 cases over 1000-person years (21.3%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.44 (0.37 to 0.52)	486 cases per 1,000-person years	272 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 307 fewer cases to 234 fewer cases) ^c
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Malaria Case Incidence (2-years post-intervention)

2000 (2 RCTs) Length of time observed: 12 months to 24 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (1 study)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High ^{f,g}	815.38 cases over 1000-person years (81.5%)	465.12 cases over 1000-person years (46.5%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.57 (0.51 to 0.63)	815 cases per 1,000-person years	351 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 400 fewer cases to 302 fewer cases) ^c
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Parasite Prevalence (6-months follow-up)

2249 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	412/1471 (31.2%)	231/1475 (15.6%)	RR 0.56 (0.48 to 0.65)	312 per 1,000	156 fewer per 1,000 (from 178 fewer to 128 fewer)
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Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)

2473 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	642/1227 (52.3%)	509/1246 (40.9%)	RR 0.78 (0.72 to 0.85)	523 per 1,000	115 fewer per 1,000 (from 147 fewer to 78 fewer)
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Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)

5445 (2 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High ^{h,i}	1218/2716 (44.8%)	923/2729 (33.8%)	RR 0.75 (0.70 to 0.80)	448 per 1,000	112 fewer per 1,000 (from 135 fewer to 90 fewer)
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Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)

2471 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	549/1199 (45.8%)	326/1272 (25.6%)	RR 0.56 (0.50 to 0.63)	458 per 1,000	201 fewer per 1,000 (from 229 fewer to 169 fewer)
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CI: confidence interval; **RR:** risk ratio

Table 1 - Summary of findings: Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus Pyrethroid-only ITNs

Explanations

a. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). For each subgroup the IRR was: *An. funestus* = 0.49 (0.43, 0.57); *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii* = 0.87 (0.67, 0.78). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p < 0.0001$ (chance an unlikely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined low credibility, likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

b. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). For each subgroup the IRR was: Rural = 0.87 (0.79, 0.96); Mixed = 0.49 (0.43, 0.57). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p < 0.0001$ (chance an unlikely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined low credibility, likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

b. Absolute calculation performed manually as GRADEPro cannot calculate using IRR

d. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). For each subgroup the IRR was: *An. funestus* = 0.41 (0.31, 0.54); *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii* = 0.46 (0.37, 0.57). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.53$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

e. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). For each subgroup the IRR was: Rural = 0.46 (0.37, 0.57); Mixed = 0.41 (0.31, 0.54). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.53$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

f. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). For each subgroup the IRR was: *An. funestus* = 0.55 (0.47, 0.65); *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii* = 0.58 (0.51, 0.66). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.69$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

g. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). For each subgroup the IRR was: Rural = 0.58 (0.51, 0.66); Mixed = 0.55 (0.47, 0.65). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.69$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

h. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). For each subgroup the RR was: *An. funestus* = 0.78 (0.72, 0.85); *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii* = 0.72 (0.65, 0.80). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p < 0.25$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

i. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). For each subgroup the RR was: Rural = 0.72 (0.65, 0.80); Mixed = 0.78 (0.72, 0.85). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.25$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid nets compared to pyrethroid-PBO nets for prevention of malaria

Certainty assessment							Summary of findings				
Participants (studies) Follow-up	Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Publication bias	Overall certainty of evidence	Study event rates (%)		Relative effect (95% CI)	Anticipated absolute effects	
							With Pyrethroid-PBO nets	With Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid nets		Risk with Pyrethroid-PBO nets	Risk difference with Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid nets

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

2000-person years (1 RCT) Length of time observed: <1 month to 24 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (1 study)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	333.16 cases over 1000-person years (33.3%)	227.34 cases over 1000-person years (22.7%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.68 (0.59 to 0.79)	333 cases per 1,000-person years	107 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 137 fewer cases to 70 fewer cases) ^a
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Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post-intervention)

2000-person years (1 RCT) Length of time observed: <1 month to 12 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (1 study)	not serious	not serious	not serious	very serious ^b	none	⊕⊕○○ Low	133.49 cases over 1000-person years (13.3%)	130.84 cases over 1000-person years (13.1%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.98 (0.71 to 1.36)	133 cases per 1,000-person years	3 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 39 fewer cases to 48 more cases) ^a
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Malaria Case Incidence (2-years post-intervention)

2000-person years (1 RCT) Length of time observed: 12 months to 24 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (1 study)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	482.95 cases over 1000-person years (48.3%)	314.95 cases over 1000-person years (31.5%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.65 (0.55 to 0.77)	483 cases per 1,000-person years	155 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 198 fewer cases to 101 fewer cases) ^a
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Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)

2197 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	serious ^c	none	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate	206/1071 (19.2%)	176/1126 (15.6%)	RR 0.81 (0.68 to 0.98)	192 per 1,000	37 fewer per 1,000 (from 62 fewer to 4 fewer)
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Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow up)

2406 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	serious ^d	none	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate	502/1160 (43.3%)	509/1246 (40.9%)	RR 0.94 (0.86 to 1.04)	433 per 1,000	26 fewer per 1,000 (from 61 fewer to 17 more)
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Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)

2531 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	512/1259 (40.7%)	326/1272 (25.6%)	RR 0.63 (0.56 to 0.71)	407 per 1,000	150 fewer per 1,000 (from 179 fewer to 118 fewer)
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CI: confidence interval; **RR:** risk ratio

Table 2 - Summary of findings: Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus Pyrethroid-PBO ITNs

Explanations

- Absolute calculation performed manually as GRADEPro cannot calculate using IRR
- Confidence intervals are very wide (39 fewer to 48 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making threshold (including line of no effect).
- Confidence intervals are wide (62 fewer to 4 fewer) and may have crossed many important decision-making threshold.
- Confidence intervals are wide (from 61 fewer to 17 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making threshold (including line of no effect).

Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid nets compared to pyrethroid-only nets for prevention of malaria

Certainty assessment							Summary of findings				
Participants (studies) Follow-up	Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Publication bias	Overall certainty of evidence	Study event rates (%)		Relative effect (95% CI)	Anticipated absolute effects	
							With Pyrethroid-only nets	With Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid nets		Risk with Pyrethroid-only nets	Risk difference with Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid nets

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

2000-person years (3 RCTs) Length of time observed: 5 months to 24 months Based on data from at least 63,163 participants (2 studies)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High ^{a,b,c}	1036.93 cases over 1000-person years (103.7%)	929.22 cases over 1000-person years (92.9%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.86 (0.81 to 0.92)	1,037 cases per 1,000-person years	145 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 197 fewer cases to 83 fewer cases) ^d
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Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post-intervention)

2000-person years (2 RCTs) Length of time observed: <1 month to 12 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (1 study)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High ^{e,f}	485.52 cases over 1000-person years (48.6%)	392.74 cases over 1000-person years (39.3%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.81 (0.70 to 0.93)	487 cases per 1,000-person years	92 fewer cases per 1,000-person years (from 146 fewer cases to 34 fewer cases) ^d
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Malaria Case Incidence (2-year post-intervention)

2000 (2 RCTs) Length of time observed: 12 months to 24 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (1 study)	not serious	not serious ^g	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High ^{h,i}	815.39 cases over 1000-person years (81.5%)	715.84 cases over 1000-person years (71.6%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 0.91 (0.81 to 1.02)	815 cases per 1,000-person years	106 fewer per 1,000 (from 163 fewer to 41 fewer) ^d
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Parasite Prevalence (6-months follow-up)

2934 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	serious ^j	none	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate	412/1471 (28.0%)	394/1463 (26.9%)	RR 0.96 (0.85 to 1.08)	280 per 1,000	11 fewer per 1,000 (from 42 fewer to 22 more)
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Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)

2192 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	350/1123 (31.2%)	232/1069 (21.7%)	RR 0.7 (0.6 to 0.8)	312 per 1,000	93 fewer per 1,000 (from 125 fewer to 62 fewer)
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Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)

5337 (2 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	serious ^k	none	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate ^{l,m}	1218/2716 (44.8%)	1147/2631 (43.8%)	RR 0.98 (0.92 to 1.04)	448 per 1,000	9 fewer per 1,000 (from 36 fewer to 18 more)
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Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)

2457 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	549/1199 (45.8%)	472/1258 (37.5%)	RR 0.82 (0.75 to 0.90)	458 per 1,000	82 fewer per 1,000 (from 114 fewer to 46 fewer)
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CI: confidence interval; **RR:** risk ratio

Table 3 - Summary of findings: Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus Pyrethroid-only ITNs

Explanations

- a. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for net type (Royal Guard versus Sumitomo Chemical). For each subgroup the IRR was: Royal Guard = 0.85 (0.79, 0.92); Sumitomo Chemical = 0.76 (0.71, 0.81). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.02$ (chance may not explain). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- b. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). For each subgroup the IRR was: *An. funestus* = 0.9 (0.81, 1.01); *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii* = 0.77 (0.73, 0.82). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.02$ (chance may not explain). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- c. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). For each subgroup the IRR was: Rural = 0.82 (0.74, 0.9); Mixed = 0.79 (0.75, 0.84). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.37$ (chance a likely explanation or unclear). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- d. Absolute calculation performed manually as GRADEPro cannot calculate using IRR
- e. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). For each subgroup the IRR was: *An. funestus* = 0.83 (0.67, 1.03); *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii* = 0.79 (0.66, 0.95). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.74$ (chance may not explain). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined low credibility, likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- f. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). For each subgroup the IRR was: Rural = 0.79 (0.66, 0.95); Mixed = 0.83 (0.67, 1.03). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.74$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- g. Borderline inconsistency, point estimate vary to some extent and I2 48%. However, not deemed serious enough to rate down.
- h. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). For each subgroup the IRR was: *An. funestus* = 0.94 (0.82, 1.07); *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii* = 0.83 (0.74, 0.93). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.17$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- i. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). For each subgroup the IRR was: Rural = 0.83 (0.74, 0.93); Mixed = 0.94 (0.82, 1.07). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.17$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.
- j. Confidence intervals are wide (from 42 fewer to 22 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making thresholds (including line of no effect).
- k. Confidence intervals are wide (from 36 fewer to 18 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making thresholds (including line of no effect).

l. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for vector (*An. funestus* versus *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii*). For each subgroup the OR was: *An. funestus* = 0.97 (0.89, 1.04); *An. gambiae sensu stricto* and *An. coluzzii* = 0.99 (0.91, 1.09). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.66$ (chance a very likely explanation). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined very low credibility, very likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

m. ICEMAN effect modifier credibility assessments were conducted on this analysis for setting (Rural versus Mixed). For each subgroup the IRR was: Rural = 0.99 (0.91, 1.09); Mixed = 1.17 (1.07, 1.27). Test for subgroup differences between subgroups was $p = 0.01$ (chance may not explain). ICEMAN credibility assessment determined low credibility, likely no effect modification. Of note the ICEMAN tool is not intended to rule out a true difference. As such, only the overall effect is presented however uncertainty remains. Forest plot and ICEMAN assessment presented in supplementary files.

Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid nets compared to pyrethroid-PBO nets for prevention of malaria

Certainty assessment							Summary of findings				
Participants (studies) Follow-up	Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Publication bias	Overall certainty of evidence	Study event rates (%)		Relative effect (95% CI)	Anticipated absolute effects	
							With Pyrethroid-PBO nets	With Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid nets		Risk with Pyrethroid-PBO nets	Risk difference with Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid nets

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

2000-person years (1 RCT) Length of time observed: <1 month to 24 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (1 study)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	333.16 cases over 1000-person years (33.3%)	415.98 cases over 1000-person years (41.6%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 1.25 (1.10 to 1.41)	333 cases per 1,000-person years	83 more cases per 1,000-person years (from 33 more cases to 137 more cases) ^a
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Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post-intervention)

2000-person years (1 RCT) Length of time observed: <1 month to 12 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (1 study)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	130.84 cases over 1000-person years (13.1%)	266.33 cases over 1000-person years (26.6%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 2.04 (1.55 to 2.68)	131 cases per 1,000-person years	136 more cases per 1,000-person years (from 72 more cases to 220 more cases) ^a
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Malaria Case Incidence (2-years post-intervention)

2000-person years (1 RCT) Length of time observed: 12 months to 24 months Based on data from at least 61,183 participants (1 study)	not serious	not serious	not serious	serious ^b	none	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate	482.95 cases over 1000-person years (48.3%)	530.86 cases over 1000-person years (53.1%)	Incidence Rate Ratio 1.10 (0.95 to 1.27)	483 cases per 1,000-person years	48 more cases per 1,000-person years (from 24 fewer cases to 130 more cases) ^a
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Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)

2140 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	serious ^c	none	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate	206/1071 (19.2%)	232/1,069 (21.7%)	RR 1.13 (0.95 to 1.33)	192 per 1,000	25 more per 1,000 (from 10 fewer to 63 more)
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Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up))

2313 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	502/1160 (43.3%)	583/1,153 (50.6%)	RR 1.17 (1.07 to 1.27)	433 per 1,000	74 more per 1,000 (from 30 more to 117 more)
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Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)

2517 (1 RCT)	not serious	not serious	not serious	serious ^d	none	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate	512/1259 (40.7%)	472/1,258 (37.5%)	OR 0.88 (0.75 to 1.03)	407 per 1,000	30 fewer per 1,000 (from 67 fewer to 7 more)
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CI: confidence interval; **OR:** odds ratio; **RR:** risk ratio

Table 4 - Summary of findings: Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus Pyrethroid-PBO ITNs

Explanations

- Absolute calculation performed manually as GRADEPro cannot calculate using IRR
- Confidence intervals are very wide (from 24 fewer 130 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making thresholds (including line of no effect).
- Confidence intervals are wide (from 10 fewer to 63 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making thresholds (including line of no effect).
- Confidence intervals are wide (from 67 fewer to 7 more) and may have crossed many important decision-making thresholds (including line of no effect).

Introduction

Malaria is an infectious, parasitic disease transmitted through the bite of infected female *Anopheles* mosquitoes.¹ Malaria is caused by the *Plasmodium* parasite, with *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* species being the most virulent and widespread for human hosts.¹ Malaria presents a significant burden to global public health, with an estimated 627,000 deaths in 2020 due to the disease.²

The sub-Saharan region of Africa bears the heaviest morbidity and mortality burden, accounting for 95% and 96% of global malaria cases and deaths, respectively.² Those at greater risk of severe disease include children under the age of five, pregnant women, and travellers from non-endemic countries.² In 2020, it was estimated the global cases of malaria totalled 241 million, which increased from the estimate of 227 million in 2019.² The WHO has estimated that almost half the world's population is at risk of contracting malaria.^{1,2}

Substantial progress has been made since 2000 in reducing global malaria cases from 80 cases per 1000 to 57 per 1000 in 2019.¹ The most successful malaria treatment strategies have often included the distribution of insecticide-treated nets (ITN) and indoor residual spraying (IRS) of insecticides. These particular strategies target the mosquito vector itself and have demonstrated considerable effectiveness. This reduction in malaria cases is primarily attributed to the distribution of ITNs, which contributed an estimated 68% to the reduction of the malaria burden, whilst IRS contributed 11% to this reduction.²

WHO recognises three major classes of ITNs. The first of these classes includes pyrethroid-only nets prequalified by WHO that are treated with pyrethroid at the time of manufacture and conventionally treated nets. These nets require treatment using a WHO prequalified self-treatment kit containing pyrethroid and are periodically re-treated. The ITN products that belong to this category have demonstrated public health value and meet safety standards. Therefore the WHO recommends that pyrethroid-only nets be used for large-scale deployment.³ However, recent findings demonstrating resistance to pyrethroid insecticides in mosquito vectors may compromise the long-term effectiveness of these ITNs.¹ In response to the spread of pyrethroid resistance, the WHO has stated that new types of ITNs should be developed to combat insecticide-resistant vectors.³ WHO has identified two other classes of ITNs, those designed to kill host-seeking insecticide-resistant mosquitoes and those designed to sterilize and/or reduce their fecundity.

The second class of ITNs, designed to kill resistant mosquitoes, consists of combinations of pyrethroid insecticides and other compounds. Belonging to this class includes an ITN that is treated with both a pyrethroid and piperonyl butoxide (PBO).¹ PBO is a synergist that acts to inhibit the metabolic enzymes of the mosquito that work to detoxify (and therefore reduce effectiveness of) insecticides. The benefits to public health of these pyrethroid-PBO ITNs have been demonstrated, resulting in the WHO conditionally recommending that these nets be used, particularly in areas where pyrethroid-resistant mosquitoes are present.¹ This class also provisionally includes nets that combine pyrethroids with other active ingredients (henceforth referred to as dual active ingredient nets, DAI). However, public health value has yet to be determined for a DAI ITN treated with pyrethroid and non-pyrethroid insecticide formulations. Studies on one sub-type of DAI ITN, that combines alpha-cypermethrin (pyrethroid) and the pyrrole chlorfenapyr have recently demonstrated both entomological and epidemiological benefit.^{4,5}

Finally, the third class of ITNs include those that have been designed to sterilize and/or reduce the fecundity of host-seeking insecticide-resistant mosquitoes. This class provisionally includes DAI ITNs treated with a pyrethroid insecticide and an insect growth regulator such as pyriproxyfen. Pyriproxyfen is an insecticide that interferes with the reproduction and development of female mosquitoes, effectively sterilising them.⁵ The value to public health of DAI ITNs treated with both pyrethroids and insect growth regulators has not yet been determined.

This systematic review is specifically interested in two interventions. These interventions will be considered as separate review questions in the one review. The first intervention includes DAI ITNs treated with a pyrethroid and non-pyrethroid insecticide. The second intervention includes DAI ITNs treated with a pyrethroid and an insect growth regulator.

Both *Anopheles gambiae* (s.s.) and *An. funestus* (s.s.), the most prevalent malaria vectors, have demonstrated widespread resistance to pyrethroid insecticides.^{6,7} This has presented a significant concern for the long-term efficacy of these insecticides for use in vector control programmes including insecticide residual spraying and in the treatment of mosquito nets. DAI ITNs may provide a solution to address vector pyrethroid resistance and may prove to have utility in future malaria control programmes. There is an urgent need to systematically review the evidence on the effectiveness of DAI ITNs as tools for the control and prevention of malaria. There have been no previous systematic reviews on this topic.

The main objective of this review is to assess the benefits (on malaria transmission or burden) and harms (adverse effects and unintended consequences) of insecticidal nets treated with a pyrethroid and a second active ingredient (either non-pyrethroid insecticide or insect growth regulator). Two review questions were formulated for this review, these questions are as follows:

1. In areas with ongoing malaria transmission, should nets treated with a pyrethroid and non-pyrethroid insecticide versus either nets treated with pyrethroid insecticide alone or with pyrethroid insecticide in combination with Piperonyl butoxide (PBO) be used to prevent malaria in adults and children?
2. In areas with ongoing malaria transmission, should long lasting insecticidal nets treated with a pyrethroid and an insect growth regulator versus either nets treated with pyrethroid insecticide alone or with pyrethroid insecticide in combination with PBO be used to prevent malaria in adults and children?

Methods

The methodology of this systematic review and meta-analyses is based on methods guidance from the Cochrane Handbook,⁸ JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis,⁹ and the GRADE Working Group.¹⁰ It has been reported in line with PRISMA 2020. The protocol was registered a priori on PROSPERO (registration number CRD42022333044) and has been published in F1000Research.¹¹

Eligibility Criteria

Participants

Studies conducted in adults and children who are residents of a region with ongoing malaria transmission and have been provided with an insecticide-treated net were eligible for this review.

Interventions

The interventions of interest are dual active ingredient (DAI) insecticide-treated nets (ITNs). DAI ITNs are eligible where they have been treated with a pyrethroid and non-pyrethroid insecticide (review question 1) or with a pyrethroid and an insect growth regulator (review question 2). The level of ITN distribution (per household or per individual) did not impact the eligibility of studies for inclusion in the review.

Background interventions

Studies conducted where background interventions were present were included if these background interventions were balanced between intervention and control arms.

Comparators

This systematic review considered studies that have compared the interventions of interest against nets treated with pyrethroid insecticide alone or with pyrethroid insecticide in combination with PBO. The same comparator(s) was used for both review questions specified above.

Outcomes

The following outcomes were considered for inclusion and are grouped into epidemiological outcomes, entomological outcomes, unintended benefits, and harms/ unintended consequences.

Epidemiological

- Malaria case incidence rate – Defined as [malaria] symptoms plus [malaria] parasitaemia, over a population at risk or person-time. Detected either through passive or active surveillance.
- Malaria infection incidence – Defined as parasitaemia with or without symptoms, over a population at risk or person-time. Detected through passive or active surveillance.
- Incidence of severe disease – Defined as hospitalisation with parasitaemia, over a population at risk or person-time.
- Parasite prevalence – Parasitaemia with or without symptoms, over the population sampled. Detected through cross-sectional surveys.
- All-cause mortality – Number of deaths over the population at risk or person-time.
- Malaria mortality – Number of deaths attributed to malaria over the population at risk or person-time.
- Prevalence of anaemia – Defined by study thresholds of anaemia.

Entomological

Studies containing data on entomological outcomes were only included in this review where data for epidemiological outcomes were also reported. These outcomes were only listed during data extraction and have not formed the basis of any outcome reporting.

- Entomological inoculation rate (EIR) – Defined as the number of infective bites received per person per unit of time.
- Sporozoite rate – Percentage of female *Anopheles* mosquitoes with sporozoites in the salivary glands.
- Anopheline density – Number of female anopheline mosquitoes in relation to the number of specified shelters or hosts or to a given period sampled, specifying the methods of collection.
- Biting rate – Average number of mosquito bites received by a host in a unit of time, specified according to the host and mosquito species.
- Mortality of adult female *Anopheles* – Defined as the mosquito being knocked down, immobile or unable to stand or take off for 24 hours after exposure to a discriminating concentration of an insecticide (or as reported in the primary evidence).

Contextual factors

Studies containing data on contextual factors were only included in this review where epidemiological outcomes were also considered by the primary study.

- Values and preferences – The values and preferences of the individuals and populations receiving the intervention.
- Acceptability – Extent to which those receiving the intervention consider the intervention to be appropriate, based on anticipated or experienced cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention. Includes willingness to participate in the intervention.
- Health equity – Extent to which the intervention benefits all populations and the potential to discriminate based on sex, age, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation or gender identity, disability status, education, socioeconomic status, residence or any other characteristic.

- Financial and economic considerations – Costs, resource use, overall economic impact, cost-benefit, cost effectiveness.
- Feasibility considerations – legal barriers to implementation, programmatic considerations, timeliness (the ability to reach all targeted households/household members in a timely manner) etc.

Unintended benefits

- Epidemiological impact on other vector-borne diseases

Harms and/or unintended consequences of interventions

- Adverse effects known to be associated with insecticides, including skin irritation, irritation of upper airways, nausea, and headache.
- Human behaviour changes e.g., change in sleeping location
- Any influence on neighbouring houses e.g., increased vector abundance/biting in houses without nets
- Environmental impacts such as biodiversity and ecosystem changes.
- Entomological impacts e.g., mosquito behaviour changes such as changes in outdoor biting rate, biting times, feeding preference, development of insecticide resistance, change in vector composition.

Setting

Studies conducted in countries with ongoing malaria transmission were considered for this review. The presence of other background interventions did not impact on study eligibility if they were present in both arms equally. Studies where additional malaria interventions are considered standard of care were included if interventions (both malaria and non-malaria) were balanced between intervention and control arms.

Study design

Only cluster randomised and non-randomised cluster-controlled studies that included more than one cluster per arm were considered for this review. Non-randomised controlled study designs were only considered for inclusion when there was a comparison/control group present. This could include historical controls. There were no exclusion rules based on any buffer period (i.e., when participants act as their own controls) or length of intervention or timing of measurement of outcomes. All observational studies and modelling studies were excluded.

Studies were not excluded based on language or publication status (i.e., published, unpublished, in press, in progress, pre-print). There were no date limitations. For studies published in languages other than English, Google Translate was to be used to determine whether the study meets inclusion criteria based on its title and abstract. Where studies were published in a language other than English and met the inclusion criteria, Google Translate translations were to be reviewed by a person fluent in that language.

Search strategy

The literature search methods have been conducted in line with guidance from JBI⁹ and Cochrane.⁸ The search strategy aimed to locate both published and unpublished studies and was developed with the input of a medical librarian.

An initial limited search of PubMed via NCBI was undertaken to identify relevant articles on this topic. The terminology contained in the titles and abstracts of relevant articles, including related subject headings, were used to develop a full search strategy for malaria and insecticidal nets. The search strategy, including all identified keywords and subject headings, was adapted for each included database and/or information source, by using Polyglot¹² and with the aid of a medical librarian. No limits or filters were applied to the searches. The search strategies for each database were then peer-reviewed using the Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies Guideline Statement.¹³ The full search strategy for major databases is available in Appendix 1.

The databases searched included Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), published in The Cochrane Library (Wiley) and including the Cochrane Infectious Diseases Group Specialized Register; PubMed (NCBI); Embase (Ovid); CINAHL with Full Text (EBSCO), US National Institutes of Health Ongoing Trials Register (www.ClinicalTrials.gov/); ISRCTN registry (www.isrctn.com/); The WHO's International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO ICTRP ([www.who.int.ictip](http://www.who.int/ictip))). Additionally, experts in the field and relevant organisations were asked whether they know of any studies (completed or ongoing) that are relevant to this review topic. The searches were run on June 7, 2022.

Study selection and screening

Following the search, all identified citations were collated and uploaded into EndNote (Clarivate, Philadelphia, United States). Duplicates were removed using the Deduplicator.¹⁴ The studies were then imported into Covidence (Veritas Health Innovation, Melbourne, Australia) where additional duplicates were identified and removed. Within Covidence, the studies were screened on their titles and abstracts by two independent reviewers (THB and SH) for assessment against the eligibility criteria for the review. Potentially relevant studies were retrieved in full. The full text of selected citations was then assessed in detail against the eligibility criteria by the same two independent reviewers. Studies that were excluded at full text screening as they did not meet the eligibility criteria have been recorded and the reasons for their exclusion reported (Appendix 2). Any disagreements between the two reviewers at each stage of the selection process were resolved through discussion.

Data extraction

Data was extracted from papers included in the review by three independent reviewers (THB, SH, JCS*) using a tailored data extraction tool developed by the reviewers (Appendix 3). Any disagreements between the reviewers were resolved through discussion. The authors of one study protocol¹⁵ were contacted directly for their data as the results of their work had not yet been published (discussed in detail in the results).

Assessment of risk of bias

Three review authors (THB, SH, JCS*) assessed the risk of bias for each study using the Cochrane Risk of Bias 2 tool for cluster-randomised trials.¹⁶ The domains of bias considered in this tool include bias arising from the randomisation process, bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants, bias due to deviations from the intended interventions, bias due to missing outcome data, bias in measurement of the outcome and bias in selection of the reported result. All risk of bias assessment was undertaken at the result level. Any disagreements between the reviewers in assessing the risk of bias were resolved through discussion.

Data synthesis and meta-analysis

Where possible, epidemiological outcomes were pooled using pair-wise meta-analysis in Review Manager 5 (RevMan5). Results have been pooled when data for the same outcome has been reported between studies and according to the active-ingredient composition of the DAI ITN intervention and of the pyrethroid-only ITN or pyrethroid-PBO ITN comparators. Data were also pooled at time-points measured in the contributing studies (6-months, 12-months, 18-months, 24-months post intervention). As some studies provided data for up to 18-months post-intervention and some provided data for up to 24-months post-intervention, these outcome results have been combined under the classification of 'furthest possible follow-up'. Also included in this classification is data derived from stepped-wedge trials. Where only one study had contributed data to a particular outcome, a forest plot was presented for illustrative purposes. A narrative description of the results has been presented alongside the meta-analysis. Where outcome data between studies cannot be pooled together in a meta-analysis, a narrative synthesis has been presented.

For dichotomous data, effect sizes have been presented as relative risks. These results have been presented with their 95% confidence intervals (CIs). Where incidence rates were reported, incidence rate ratios have been reported with their 95% CIs in the meta-analysis. When three or more studies contribute to a meta-analysis, a random effects model has been used. A fixed effect model was used when there are only two studies contributing to a meta-analysis. Cost data and data related to contextual factors have been narratively synthesised. Entomological outcomes listed in the included studies have been reported in Appendix 3.

Assessment of heterogeneity and publication bias

Heterogeneity (both clinical and methodological) was first assessed by comparing the included studies against each other in terms of the eligibility criteria specified above. Statistical heterogeneity was assessed through visual inspection of the forest plot and by the Cochran's Q (P value 0.05), and I² statistic. Interpretation of the I² statistic was according to the guidance in the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions⁸ and occurred as follows:

- 0% to 40%: heterogeneity might not be important;
- 30% to 60%: may represent moderate heterogeneity;
- 50% to 90%: may represent substantial heterogeneity; or
- 75% to 100%: considerable heterogeneity.

The typical statistical tests of publication bias were not appropriate^{17,18} as fewer than 10 studies were included in all meta-analyses. Efforts were made to reduce the impact of publication bias in this review by seeking both published and unpublished literature using the comprehensive search strategy discussed above and provided in Appendix 1.

Subgroup and sensitivity analysis

Where the data was available, several potential effect modifiers were assessed through subgroup analyses. These included:

- Insecticides used for both active ingredients and manufacturer
- Malaria vector species
- Setting (Urbanicity, classed as rural/ urban/ peri-urban)

Subgroups were assessed on their credibility of being a genuine effect modifier using the Instrument for assessing the Credibility of Effect Modification (ICEMAN).¹⁹ This is a tool that reviewers can use based on answering a series of questions that address specific criteria that can be used to evaluate whether an effect modification is likely.¹⁹ ICEMAN credibility assessment statements are expressed as very low (very likely no effect modification), low (likely no effect modification), moderate (likely effect modification), and high (very likely effect modification).

Unit of analysis issues

As all authors had appropriately accounted for clustering in their analysis, the inflation of standard errors was not required as originally planned as per the protocol.^{17,18}

GRADE

The GRADE approach¹⁰ for grading the certainty of evidence was followed. GRADE Evidence Profiles were created using "GRADEpro GDT" for each comparison considered. The evidence profiles have presented the following information for each outcome: absolute risks for the treatment and control, estimates of relative risk, and a rating of the certainty of the evidence based. As all evidence has been derived from RCTs, the certainty of evidence has started as high and has been downgraded appropriately. All instances of

downgrading have been documented in the footnotes in the summary of findings tables (Tables 1, 2, 3, and 4). The following outcomes have been presented in the summary of findings tables (where applicable):

- Malaria case incidence rate (overall)
- Malaria case incidence rate (1-year post intervention)
- Malaria case incidence rate (2-years post intervention)
- Parasite prevalence (6-months follow-up)
- Parasite prevalence (12-months follow-up)
- Parasite prevalence (18-months follow-up)
- Parasite prevalence (24-months follow-up)

Role of the funding source

The funder of the study had a role in the development of the protocol, the wording and development of the review questions, the interpretation of the final results and the development of this manuscript.

Results

Results of the search

There were 8998 citation records identified in the initial database search (i.e., PubMed, Embase, CINAHL, Cochrane Library) and 496 citation records were identified from the trial registries (ClinicalTrials.gov, WHO ICTRP, ISRCTN), for a total of 9494 citation records. Of these, a total of 3694 records were removed (3662 records were identified and removed via the Deduplicator¹⁴ and a further 32 records were identified and removed via Covidence). This left 5800 unique citation records to be screened. Two citation records were identified through direct correspondence with the authors (described below) and through manual searching through the ClinicalTrials.gov trial registry. The former of these records was an ongoing trial (NCT04566510) which has been noted for future reviews on this topic but has not contributed to any of the analysis of this report.

The records were screened by title and abstract and 5752 citations were excluded for not meeting the inclusion criteria. This left 48 records in which the reports were sought and were screened at the full-text level. There were 36 reports that were excluded for not meeting the inclusion criteria. Of these 36, 21 reports were excluded for having an ineligible study design, eight reports were excluded for having ineligible outcomes and seven reports were excluded for having ineligible interventions.

The 12 remaining reports were then merged at the study level, leaving three studies (12 reports) to be included in the review. The report that was identified through direct correspondence with the authors was an ongoing study that had been accepted for publication but was still in production (as of writing, this study is still in production with the Lancet). This study has been merged with the reports of the protocol that were identified during the search and screening procedures. Therefore, the final totals were three studies included in this review which have been reported in 12 reports identified through the search and one report identified via direct correspondence with the study authors. The breakdown of reports to studies is presented in Table 5. The PRISMA flow diagram of this screening process is presented in Figure 1.

Study Citation	Number of Reports
Accrombessi, Cook ¹⁵	3 2 identified through screening 1 identified through direct author correspondence with authors
Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴	3
Tiono, Ouédraogo ²⁰	7

Table 5 - Breakdown of reports to studies included in the systematic review

Characteristics of the included studies

Study designs and time periods

This review has included three studies,^{4,15,20} one of which is a trial that has been accepted for publication following peer-review but is still unavailable (at time of writing) the authors of this study were contacted directly for their finalised data. All the included studies were cluster-randomised control trials, with the study from Tiono, Ouédraogo²⁰ employing a stepped-wedge design for intervention implementation. The years during which the trials took place were between 2014-2015,²⁰ 2018-2020,⁴ and 2020 – ongoing (as of October 2022).¹⁵

Population, setting and vector characteristics

The sample size ranged from approximately 4,000 households¹⁵ to 39,307 households.⁴ The number of participants for each study ranged from 1,980²⁰ to 61,183.⁴ The number of participants was not provided by one study.¹⁵ All studies included both adults and children in their design, however children were prioritised in the measurement of the outcomes and population demographics (data from adults included in select outcomes, detailed below). Accrombessi, Cook¹⁵ reported data for adults and children (collected from cross-sectional studies) and only children (active-case detection, details below) between the ages of 6 months to 9 years old who did not have severe illnesses and resided in the study villages at the time of the intervention. Moshia, Kulkarni⁴ included households with at least one child of appropriate age (between six months to ten years old) who permanently lived in households recruited through a census. Adults were also considered in the data from cross-sectional surveys (details below). Tiono, Ouédraogo²⁰ (2018) included children selected randomly from a census, who were between the ages of 6 months to 5 years old. The percentage of female to male children was balanced for all included studies at 48%,¹⁵ 51.7%⁴ and 49%.²⁰

The countries involved in this review included Benin,¹⁵ Burkina Faso²⁰ and Tanzania⁴ with the trials in Burkina Faso²⁰ and Tanzania⁴ both being conducted in a setting of mixed urbanicity (mix of rural and peri-urban). The study conducted in Benin was conducted in a rural setting.¹⁵ Transmission intensity of malaria followed the rainy season in each location, which ranged from April-July and October-November (Benin),¹⁵ May-October (Burkina-Faso)²⁰ and October-July (Tanzania).⁴ The species of parasite for each trial was *Plasmodium falciparum*, and every setting was considered to have a high level of transmission (*P. falciparum* prevalence of $\geq 35\%$) according to the schema in the WHO: *a framework for malaria elimination*.²¹ The main vectors of interest for the trials of Accrombessi, Cook¹⁵ and Tiono, Ouédraogo²⁰ included both *Anopheles coluzzi* and *An. gambiae sensu stricto*. While the main vector considered by Moshia, Kulkarni⁴ was *An. funestus*.

Interventions and Comparisons

All studies implemented the intervention at the household level (e.g. distributed nets according to number of people residing in each household), and every study reported to have achieved a high level of coverage.²² Accrombessi, Cook¹⁵ assessed coverage as household access, and reported that one net was provided per every two people. Moshia, Kulkarni⁴ and Tiono, Ouédraogo²⁰ assessed coverage as population access and reported a baseline intervention coverage of 62.2% and 95%, respectively.

Accrombessi, Cook¹⁵ explored two interventions against a common comparator. The first intervention was the chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITN “Interceptor G2®”. This ITN was made of polyester netting (100 deniers) coated with a wash-resistant formulation of 200 mg/m² chlorfenapyr (a pyrole) and 100 mg/m² alpha-cypermethrin (a pyrethroid). The second intervention was the pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITN “Royal Guard®”. This ITN was made of polyethylene (120 deniers) incorporating 225 mg/m² pyriproxyfen (an insect growth regulator) and 261 mg/m² alpha-cypermethrin. Both interventions were compared against each other in addition to a control pyrethroid-only ITN treated with alpha-cypermethrin (coated onto filaments) at a target dose of 200 mg/m² of polyester fabric (100 deniers).

Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ also compared two interventions. The first intervention was the “Interceptor G2[®]” (same specifications as above) and the second was the “Royal Guard[®]” (same specifications as above). These interventions were compared to the “Interceptor[®]” (same specifications as above) and were also compared to “Olyset Plus[®]”, a pyrethroid-PBO ITN (10g/kg of PBO and 20g/kg of permethrin incorporated into polyethylene fibres).

Finally, Tiono, Ouédraogo ²⁰ evaluated the effectiveness of the pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITN “Olyset Duo[®]”. These were polyethylene nets treated with a combination of 2% w/w permethrin and 1% w/w pyriproxyfen incorporated into polyethylene fibres. These were compared against pyrethroid-only ITNs “Olyset[®]” (2% w/w permethrin incorporated into polyethylene fibres). Tiono, Ouédraogo ²⁰ employed a stepped-wedge design, where five clusters were randomised to the standard “Olyset[®]” ITNs at baseline and replaced with the “Olyset Duo[®]” ITNs by the end of the trial (June 2014 to December 2015).

Outcomes

The main outcome measured across all three studies was malaria case incidence. In the Accrombessi, Cook ¹⁵ trial, malaria case incidence was measured in a cohort of 30 children per cluster (aged 6 months to 10 years) that were randomly selected and actively followed up for 20 months. Similarly, Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ measured malaria case incidence by actively following one child per household (aged 6-months to 14-years), from 35 randomly selected households per cluster, for up to 1-year. A second independent cohort of children from 40 randomly selected households per cluster were actively followed for 1-year, 1-year post intervention (e.g. from 1-year post to 2-years post). Tiono, Ouédraogo ²⁰ however, measured malaria case incidence in approximately 2157 (balanced between groups) children aged six months to five years through passive case detection (presentation to health facility with malaria symptoms).

The other outcomes measured across all three studies were parasite prevalence and prevalence of anaemia. These outcomes were collected using cross-sectional surveys. Accrombessi, Cook ¹⁵ conducted a survey at 6-months and 18-months post implementation of the intervention. This survey included 70 people (of any age) randomly selected in each cluster. Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ conducted cross-sectional surveys of up to two children per household if they were aged between 6 months and 14 years. These surveys were conducted at 12-months, 18-months and 24-months post implementation of the intervention. Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ also collected data regarding all-cause mortality and malaria mortality during these surveys. Finally, Tiono, Ouédraogo ²⁰ conducted four cross-sectional surveys of all children in the study area. These surveys were performed in June 2014, December 2014, May 2015 and July 2015 (time post intervention ranged from 5-weeks to 9-months). Due to the stepped-wedged nature of this trial, the data from May 2015 represents the survey in which 50% of the clusters randomised had received the intervention and 50% were still using the control ITN. Tiono, Ouédraogo ²⁰ also collected all-cause mortality data during these surveys.

Malaria infection incidence and incidence of severe disease were outcomes stipulated in the protocol. However, these outcomes could not be synthesised as they were not reported by any of the included studies. Data regarding adverse events was also reported in two studies^{4,20} and contextual information regarding net quality was only reported in one.⁴ Summary characteristics of the included studies has been provided in Table 6. The full details of these studies have been included in the characteristics of included studies tables (Appendix 3)

Study (location)	Year(s) of study	Dual active ingredient insecticide treated nets		Outcomes reported
		DAI ITN characteristics	Number of clusters, population details and coverage	
Accrombessi 2021 (Protocol author and submission date) (Benin, Cote, Zagnanado, and Ouinhi Districts)	2020 - ongoing	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Interceptor G2 (200 mg/m2 chlorfenapyr and 100 mg/m2 alpha-cypermethrin) 2. Royal Guard (225 mg/m2 pyriproxyfen and 261 mg/m2 alpha-cypermethrin) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters = 60 (approximately 200 households per cluster) • Population = Approximately 1200 per cluster (actual numbers not provided) • Overall coverage = one LLIN per every two people (complete details not provided) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria case incidence rate • Parasite Prevalence • Prevalence of naemia
Mosha 2022 (Tanzania, Misungwi district of Mwanza)	2018 – 2020	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Interceptor G2 (200 mg/m2 chlorfenapyr and 100 mg/m2 alpha-cypermethrin) 2. Royal Guard (225 mg/m2 pyriproxyfen and 261 mg/m2 alpha-cypermethrin) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters = 84 (119 households) • Population = 236,496 • Overall coverage = Coverage at baseline measured as 62.2% (Population access) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parasite prevalence (defined in the study as malaria prevalence) • Malaria case incidence • All-cause mortality • Malaria mortality • Prevalence of anaemia
Tiono 2018 (Burkina Faso, Cascades Region)	2014-2017	1. Olyset Duo (2% w/w permethrin and 1% w/w pyriproxyfen)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clusters = 40 (consisting of 1-4 neighboring villages, aka compound). • Population = Population numbers not provided at time of randomization. 6062 households participated • Overall coverage = Coverage at baseline measured as 95% (Population access) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria case incidence rate • Parasite prevalence • All-cause mortality • Prevalence of anaemia

Table 6 - Summary characteristics of included studies

Assessment of the risk of bias

Bias arising from the randomisation process

Randomisation and allocation concealment were achieved through employing an independent statistician in Moshā, Kulkarni⁴ and were judged as having low risk of bias for this domain. Accrombessi, Cook¹⁵ stated in their protocol that “Restricted randomisation will be used...” but did not provide the review team with additional information regarding this procedure, or baseline demographics outside of children sex ratios for meta-determination of the randomisation sequence followed. Likewise, Tiono, Ouédraogo²⁰ achieved randomisation using “Stata version 10”, however, no further details were provided regarding this process for whether allocation concealment took place. As such, both studies were judged as having ‘some concerns’ for this domain.

Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants

All studies were regarded as having low risk of bias for this domain. All studies identified clusters before the randomisation process and the baseline demographic data provided by Moshā, Kulkarni⁴ and Tiono, Ouédraogo²⁰ suggest that there were no imbalances between groups which may suggest differential recruitment between groups (this data was not provided for Accrombessi, Cook¹⁵).

Bias arising from deviations from intended interventions

All studies attempted to blind participants and staff to the intervention being received. Moshā, Kulkarni⁴ utilised ITNs that were similar in appearance apart from a colour-coded loop. Tiono, Ouédraogo²⁰ stated that all ITNs were of similar shape, size and colour. While the methods of blinding for the Accrombessi, Cook¹⁵ study have not been provided by the authors, the protocol for this trial states “Study participants will be blinded to the type of nets they have received. All field staff will be blinded to the allocation and analyses will be conducted on blinded data”. As such, the risk of bias for all studies for this domain was low.

Bias arising from missing outcome data

In the Accrombessi, Cook¹⁵ trial, malaria case incidence was measured in a cohort of 30 children per cluster that were randomly selected and followed up for 20 months. Meanwhile parasite prevalence and prevalence of anaemia were measured following cross-sectional surveys of approximately 70 people (per cluster).

Moshā, Kulkarni⁴ measured malaria case incidence by actively following one child, from 35 randomly selected households per cluster, for up to 1-year. A second independent cohort of children from 40 randomly selected households per cluster were actively followed for 1-year, 1-year post intervention (e.g. from 1-year post to 2-years post). The authors also collected parasite prevalence, prevalence of anaemia data and mortality data (all-cause and due to malaria) from cross-sectional surveys of up to two children per household if they were aged between 6 months and 14 years.

Finally, Tiono, Ouédraogo²⁰ measured malaria case incidence of children aged six months to five years through passive case detection (presentation to health facility with malaria symptoms). A cross-sectional survey of all children in the study area was conducted (when the stepped-wedge design achieved 50:50 split between intervention arms), this survey collected data of parasite prevalence, prevalence of anaemia and mortality.

Across all studies and for all outcomes, data was not made available for every participant that belonged to a randomised cluster. However, the process of randomisation (that was evidenced in each study) and randomly selecting participants to provide outcome data, suggests that these results were not biased. Additionally, data was made available from every cluster, for all three studies. As such, all three studies have been judged to have a low risk of bias for this domain, and for every outcome reported.

Bias arising from measurement of the outcome

Measurement of all outcomes examined across every study were deemed to be appropriate (see details regarding outcomes above), and all studies employed an appropriate blinding method (see above) that

suggests that blinding of the outcome assessor was likely. Therefore, all studies have been judged to have a low risk of bias for this domain, and for every outcome reported.

Bias arising from selection of the reported results

The raw data from Accrombessi, Cook¹⁵ have been provided directly from the authors and includes data from 1-year post, 2-year post and overall data for all three outcomes reported above. All this data has been used in the review analyses and has followed a pre-specified analysis plan established in the protocol. Both Moshia, Kulkarni⁴ and Tiono, Ouédraogo²⁰ reported multiple analyses of the data for each outcome (time points analysis). However, all the results were reported in the manuscripts transparently and included in this review as appropriate. These analyses were also conducted following the pre-specified analysis plan established in the trial protocols and the risk of bias for all three studies for this domain for each outcome is low.

Overall bias

Overall, the risk of bias was low for all studies across all outcomes. The only concerns arose were limited details provided by Accrombessi, Cook¹⁵ and Tiono, Ouédraogo²⁰ regarding allocation concealment. However, these were considered minor. Judgments for each included study have been summarised in figure 2 with support for every judgment provided in Appendix 3.

Data synthesis and meta-analysis

Comparison 1 - Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

Two studies^{4,15} contributed data for this comparison and the below outcomes. There was a 28% reduction in malaria case incidence (overall) in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (IRR = 0.72, 95%CI: 0.67 – 0.78, $p < 0.001$, Figure 3). There was considerable heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 98\%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 43.57$, $p < 0.001$). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment identified these subgroups as both having low credibility. This assessment suggested that effect modification is unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used. Every analysis conducted (including all subgroups) have been provided in detail in Appendix 4. The ICEMAN credibility assessments have been presented in Appendix 5.

Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post intervention)

There was a 56% reduction in malaria case incidence at 1-year post intervention in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (IRR = 0.44, 95%CI: 0.37 – 0.52, $p < 0.001$, Figure 4). There was no important heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 0\%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 0.39$, $p = 0.53$). Subgroup for vector species and setting using ICEMAN credibility assessment identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility suggesting an unlikely effect modification is for the overall estimate.

Malaria Case Incidence (2-years post intervention)

There was a 43% reduction in malaria case incidence at 2-years post intervention in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (IRR = 0.57, 95%CI: 0.51 – 0.63, $p < 0.001$, Figure 5). There was no important heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 0\%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 0.69$, $p = 0.53$). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is very unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

Parasite prevalence (6-months follow-up)

Accrombessi, Cook¹⁵ reported a 50% reduction in parasite prevalence at 6-months follow-up, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.50, 95%CI: 0.43 – 0.59, $p < 0.001$, Figure 6).

Parasite prevalence (12-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 22% reduction in parasite prevalence at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.78, 95%CI: 0.72 – 0.85, $p < 0.001$, Figure 7).

Parasite prevalence (18-months follow-up)

There was a 25% reduction in parasite prevalence at 18-months follow-up, in clusters chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.75, 95%CI: 0.70 – 0.80, $p < 0.001$, Figure 8). There was no important heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 25%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 1.33$, $p = 0.25$). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is very unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

Parasite prevalence (24-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 44% reduction in parasite prevalence at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.56, 95%CI: 0.50 – 0.63, $p < 0.001$, Figure 9).

Parasite prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)

There was a 36% reduction in parasite prevalence at the furthest possible follow-up time point, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.64, 95%CI: 0.59 – 0.69, $p < 0.001$, Figure 10). There was considerable heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 91%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 10.63$, $p = 0.001$). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment identified these subgroups as both having low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

Prevalence of anaemia (6-months follow-up)

Accrombessi, Cook ¹⁵ reported a 17% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at 6-months follow-up, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.83, 95%CI: 0.66 – 1.04, $p = 0.16$, Figure 11).

Prevalence of anaemia (12-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 48% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 1.48, 95%CI: 0.58 – 3.79, $p = 0.41$, Figure 12).

Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)

There was a 5% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at 18-months follow-up, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.95, 95%CI: 0.80 – 1.13, $p = 0.20$, Figure 13). There was moderate heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 40%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 1.68$, $p = 0.20$). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is very unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

Prevalence of anaemia (24-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 21% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.79, 95%CI: 0.48 – 1.30, $p = 0.35$, Figure 14).

Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible follow-up)

As this data has come from cross-sectional surveys, the survey from each study taken from the longest time post-intervention (where appropriate) was used (Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ – 24 months, Accrombessi, Cook¹⁵ – 18 months). There was a 3% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at the furthest possible follow-up time point, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.97, 95%CI: 0.81 – 1.16, p=0.076, Figure 15). There was no important heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 32\%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 0.99$, $p = 0.32$). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is very unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

Comparison 2 - Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

Only one study⁴ contributed data for the outcomes under this comparison. Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 32% reduction in malaria case incidence (overall), in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (RR = 0.68, 95%CI: 0.59 – 0.79, $p < 0.001$, Figure 16).

Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post intervention)

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 2% reduction in malaria case incidence at 1-year post intervention, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (RR = 0.98, 95%CI: 0.71 – 1.36, $p = 0.90$, Figure 17).

Malaria Case Incidence (2-years post intervention)

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 35% reduction in malaria case incidence at 2-years post intervention, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (RR = 0.65, 95%CI: 0.55 – 0.77, $p < 0.001$, Figure 18).

Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 19% reduction in parasite prevalence at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (RR = 0.81, 95%CI: 0.68 – 0.98, $p = 0.03$, Figure 19).

Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 6% reduction in parasite prevalence at 18-months follow-up, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (RR = 0.94, 95%CI: 0.86 – 1.04, $p = 0.23$, Figure 20).

Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 37% reduction in parasite prevalence at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (RR = 0.63, 95%CI: 0.56 – 0.71, $p < 0.001$, Figure 21).

Prevalence of anaemia (12-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 1% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (RR = 0.99, 95%CI: 0.43 – 2.31, $p = 0.03$, Figure 22).

Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 28% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 18-months follow-up, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (RR = 1.28, 95%CI: 0.77 – 2.14, $p = 0.35$, Figure 23).

Prevalence of anaemia (24-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 4% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (RR = 1.04, 95%CI: 0.62 – 1.73, p = 0.89, Figure 24).

Comparison 3 - Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-only ITNs

Malaria case incidence (overall)

All three included studies contributed data to this outcome. There was a 14% reduction in malaria case incidence (overall) in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (IRR = 0.86, 95%CI: 0.81 – 0.92, p = 0.41, Figure 25). There was moderate heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 41%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 4.64$, $p < 0.001$). The data has been separated into subgroups based on active-ingredient composition and manufacturer. However, ICEMAN credibility assessments determined very low credibility, suggesting that there was very likely no effect modification between these subgroups and the overall effect should be used. Subgroup analysis was also conducted for vector species and setting; however, ICEMAN credibility assessments determined these subgroups to also be very-low. As such, it is very likely that no effect modification was present.

Malaria case incidence (1-year post intervention)

Only data from Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ and Accrombessi, Cook ¹⁵ have provided data for outcomes regarding time from implementation of the intervention. There was a 19% reduction in malaria case incidence at 1-year post intervention in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (IRR = 0.81, 95%CI: 0.70 – 0.93, p = 0.003, Figure 26). There was no important heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 0%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 0.74$, $p = 0.74$). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is very unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

Malaria case incidence (2-years post intervention)

There was a 13% reduction in malaria case incidence at 2-years post intervention in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (IRR = 0.87, 95%CI: 0.80 – 0.95, p=0.003, Figure 27). There was moderate heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 48%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 0.17$, $p = 0.003$). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is very unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

Parasite prevalence at 6-months follow-up

Accrombessi, Cook ¹⁵ reported a 4% reduction in parasite prevalence at 6-months follow-up, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.96, 95%CI: 0.85 – 1.08, p=0.51, Figure 28).

Parasite prevalence (12-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 30% reduction in parasite prevalence at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.70, 95%CI: 0.60 – 0.80, p < 0.001, Figure 29).

Parasite prevalence (18-months follow-up)

There was a 2% reduction in parasite prevalence at 18-months follow-up, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.98, 95%CI: 0.92 – 1.04, p = 0.49, Figure 30). There was no important heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 0%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 0.20$, $p = 0.65$). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment

identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is very unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

Parasite prevalence (24-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported an 18% reduction in parasite prevalence at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.82, 95%CI: 0.75 – 0.90, $p < 0.001$, Figure 31).

Parasite prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)

All three included studies contributed data to this outcome. The survey from each study taken from the longest time post-intervention (where appropriate) was used (Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ – 24 months, Accrombessi, Cook ¹⁵ – 18 months). However, due to the stepped-wedged nature of Tiono, Ouédraogo ²⁰, the data from survey conducted in May 2015 has been used. This data represents the longest point in the trial from the implementation of the intervention in which 50% of the clusters randomised had received the intervention and 50% were still using the control ITN. There was a 9% reduction in parasite prevalence at the furthest possible follow-up time point, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.91, 95%CI: 0.82 – 1.02, $p = 0.10$, Figure 32). The data has been separated into subgroups based on active-ingredient composition and manufacturer. However, ICEMAN credibility assessments determined very low credibility, suggesting that there was very likely no effect modification between these subgroups and the overall effect should be used. Subgroup analysis was also conducted for vector species and setting; however, ICEMAN credibility assessments determined these subgroups to be low and very-low respectively. As such, it is likely to very likely that no effect modification was present.

Prevalence of anaemia at 6-months follow-up

Accrombessi, Cook ¹⁵ reported a 14% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 6-months follow-up, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 1.14, 95%CI: 0.93 – 1.39, $p = 0.20$, Figure 33).

Prevalence of anaemia (12-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 22% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 1.22, 95%CI: 0.45 – 3.33, $p = 0.70$, Figure 34).

Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)

There was a 6% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at 18-months follow-up, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.94, 95%CI: 0.79 – 1.13, $p = 0.53$, Figure 35). There was no important heterogeneity between these data ($I^2 = 0\%$, $\text{Chi}^2 = 0.00$, $p = 0.96$). Subgroup analyses were conducted for vector species and setting. The ICEMAN credibility assessment identified these subgroups as both having very low credibility. This suggested that effect modification is very unlikely and for the overall estimate to be used.

Prevalence of anaemia (24-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ reported a 2% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 1.02, 95%CI: 0.64 – 1.62, $p = 0.92$, Figure 36).

Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible follow-up)

There was a 15% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at the furthest possible follow-up time point, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-only ITNs (RR = 0.85, 95%CI: 0.72 – 1.00, $p = 0.06$, Figure 37). The data has been separated into subgroups based on active-ingredient composition and manufacturer. However, ICEMAN credibility assessments determined low

credibility, suggesting that there was likely no effect modification between these subgroups and the overall effect should be used. Subgroup analysis was also conducted for vector species and setting; however, ICEMAN credibility assessments determined these subgroups to be very-low. As such, it is very likely that no effect modification was present.

Comparison 4 - Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs versus pyrethroid-PBO ITNs

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

Only one study⁴ directly compared any DAI ITN against an ITN that combined a pyrethroid and PBO in the one net. Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 25% increase in malaria case incidence (overall) in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (IRR = 1.25, 95%CI: 1.10 – 1.41, p = 0.0005, Figure 38).

Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post intervention)

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 104% increase in malaria case incidence at 1-year post intervention, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (IRR = 2.04, 95%CI: 1.55 – 2.68, p < 0.001, Figure 39).

Malaria Case Incidence (2-years post intervention)

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 10% increase in malaria case incidence at 2-years post intervention, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (IRR = 1.10, 95%CI: 0.95 – 1.27, p = 0.19, Figure 40).

Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 13% increase in parasite prevalence at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (RR = 1.13, 95%CI: 0.95 – 1.33, p = 0.16, Figure 41).

Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 17% increase in parasite prevalence at 18-months follow-up, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (RR = 1.17, 95%CI: 1.07 – 1.27, p = 0.0005, Figure 42).

Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported an 8% reduction in parasite prevalence at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (RR = 0.92, 95%CI: 0.84 – 1.02, p = 0.11, Figure 43).

Prevalence of anaemia (12-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 20% reduction in prevalence of anaemia at 12-months follow-up, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (RR = 0.80, 95%CI: 0.32 – 2.00, p = 0.63, Figure 44).

Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 60% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 18-months follow-up, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (RR = 1.60, 95%CI: 0.97 – 2.65, p = 0.06, Figure 45).

Prevalence of anaemia (24-months follow-up)

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a 35% increase in prevalence of anaemia at 24-months follow-up, in clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (RR = 1.35, 95%CI: 0.83 – 2.18, p = 0.22, Figure 46).

Mortality

Both Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ and Tiono, Ouédraogo²⁰ reported data regarding mortality outcomes. Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported a total of five deaths among cohort children during the study. While these deaths have been reported per group and year, the reasons (of death) have not been separated by group or year. As reported by the authors three deaths were from drowning, one was due to severe malaria, and one due to pneumonia, all of which were judged to be unrelated to the study interventions. Tiono, Ouédraogo²⁰ reported that there were 19 serious adverse events across all study participants (discussed below), and six of these resulted in deaths (n = 1 [Standard ITN], n = 5 [DAI ITN]). However, the months in which these deaths were recorded was not provided which prevented this data being presented as a forest-plot, as an appropriate denominator could not be determined, due to the stepped-wedge design of the trial.

Adverse Events

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported that at 3 months post-intervention, adverse events were reported in 90 (44.1%) of those assigned the pyrethroid-only ITN, 80 (38.8%) of those assigned pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs, 17 (8.5%) assigned the chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITN, and 17 (8.5%) of those assigned the pyrethroid-PBO ITN. They also narratively reported that skin irritation was the most reported adverse event, however no adverse event was considered to be serious.

Tiono, Ouédraogo²⁰ reported 21 non-serious adverse events in the pyrethroid-only ITN group and one in the pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITN group. The adverse event in this group was a case of bronchitis. The adverse events in the pyrethroid-only ITN group included bronchitis, conjunctivitis, eye pruritus, pelvic pain, pruritus, rhinitis, cough and watering eyes all of which were resolved by study staff. Tiono, Ouédraogo²⁰ also reported 10 serious adverse events in the pyrethroid-only ITN group and 9 in the pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITN group. These included severe malaria with other comorbidities, uncomplicated malaria with vomiting, gastroenteritis with severe dehydration and pneumonia. However, these were not disaggregated between groups.

Contextual Factors

Only Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ reported data related to contextual factors of the ITNs used during the trial. The authors reported the proportion of ITNs that were torn (defined as hole area ≥ 790 cm²). There were 86 (28%) torn in the pyrethroid-only ITN group, 109 (39%) were torn in the pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITN group, 96 (34%) were torn in the chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITN group, and 81 (43%) were torn in the pyrethroid-PBO group. No study reported any data regarding values or preferences regarding the interventions.

Cost Effectiveness

Cost effectiveness was only reported by Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ who modelled cost-effectiveness over the 2-year trial period. Malaria incidence estimates for each trial year were combined with probabilities of progression to severe disease and death that were collected from secondary sources. The authors used age-stratified malaria estimates for all countries from the “Global Burden of Disease Study 2019” incidence in people older than 10 years was estimated as a function of incidence in children aged 6 months to 10 years, and deaths in people older than 10 years were estimated as a fixed ratio to modelled deaths in children aged 6 months to 10 years. The authors then used Monte Carlo simulation to conduct probabilistic analyses, which reflected combined uncertainty in stochastic parameters. Analyses were re-run, varying one key parameter at a time, to examine the robustness of results to plausible variations in individual parameters. A threshold analysis identified the price of each net at which cost-effectiveness conclusions would change.

Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ stated that chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs were estimated to avert the most DALYs (disability adjusted life years) (mean 152 DALYs averted [SD 72] per 10,000 total population). This was followed by pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (37 DALYs averted [72] per 10,000 population). Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs incurred 9 more DALYs [71] per 10,000 population than compared to pyrethroid-only ITNs.

Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ also reported that pyrethroid-only ITNs were the least costly to procure at \$2.07 per net (\$US), this was followed by pyrethroid-PBO ITNs at \$2.98 per net. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs were the next most expensive at \$3.02 per net, while pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs were the most expensive \$3.68. However, when considering the costs of malaria diagnosis and treatment, and compared to pyrethroid-only ITNs over 2 years the chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs were the least costly (incremental cost \$2894 [SD 1129] per 10 000 population). This was followed by pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (\$4816 [SD 1360]) and pyriproxyfen-pyrethroids ITNs were the most expensive (\$9621 [SD 1327]).

Mosha, Kulkarni ⁴ conclude by stating that chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs were the more cost-effective strategy over a 2-year period. Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs would cost an additional \$19 (95%CI from \$105 to \$1) to public providers or \$28 (95%CI from \$11 to \$120) to donors per DALY averted compared to pyrethroid-only ITNs. The pyrethroid-PBO ITNs were less effective and more costly and were estimated to cost an additional \$130 (95%CI from \$12 to -\$59) to public providers and \$136 to donors (95%CI from \$22 to -\$58) per DALY averted.

Discussion

This is the first systematic review to assess the effectiveness of DAI ITNs against pyrethroid-only or pyrethroid-PBO ITNs. Three, cluster-randomised controlled trials were included in this review. Two studies employed a typical design and were conducted in Benin¹⁵ and Tanzania.⁴ One study utilised a stepped-wedge design and was conducted in Burkina Faso.²⁰ All studies were conducted in settings with high transmission of *P. falciparum*. The interventions investigated included chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs (Interceptor G2) and pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs (Royal Guard and/or Olyset Duo). These interventions have been compared against pyrethroid-only ITNs (Interceptor and/or Olyset) or pyrethroid-PBO ITNs (Olyset Plus). All studies utilised similar modes of intervention implementation and achieved a high coverage of the ITNs at baseline.

When collapsing the data across time points, the evidence suggests that clusters that receive a chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITN (figure 3) will likely result in a reduction of malaria case incidence compared to clusters that receive a pyrethroid-only ITN. This finding was associated with moderate certainty of the evidence (Table 1). Similarly, the evidence also suggests that clusters that receive a pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITN (figure 25) will result in a reduction of malaria case incidence compared to clusters that receive a pyrethroid-only ITN. This finding was associated with high certainty of the evidence (Table 3). Compared to the control group, the reduction in malaria case incidence appears to be greater for the clusters receiving the chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITN than the reduction observed for clusters receiving the pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITN. However, this difference as with all results discussed in this section, needs to be contextualised by a guideline panel.

At 1-year post intervention, the evidence suggests that clusters that receive a chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITN (figure 4) or pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITN (figure 26) will result in a reduction of malaria case incidence compared to clusters that receive pyrethroid-only ITNs. Both findings were associated with high certainty of the evidence (Table 1 and 3). These results were mirrored at 2-years post-intervention. The evidence suggests that, compared to clusters receiving pyrethroid-only ITNs, clusters that receive either chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs (figure 5) or pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs (figure 27) will also result in a reduction of malaria case incidence. Again, both findings were associated with high certainty of the evidence. For both time points it appears that the reduction in malaria case incidence is greater for the clusters receiving the DAI ITN containing chlorfenapyr and pyrethroid, than the reduction observed for clusters that received the DAI ITN containing pyriproxyfen and pyrethroid (both compared to clusters receiving pyrethroid-only ITNs).

Parasite prevalence at 6-months follow-up was only reported by Accrombessi, Cook ¹⁵ for both formulations of DAI ITNs. The authors have reported that both clusters receiving both formulations resulted in a reduction in parasite prevalence. However, chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs appear to offer a greater reduction (figure 6,

table 1) with higher certainty of the evidence, compared to pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs (figure 28, table 3) with moderate certainty of the evidence. Parasite prevalence at 12-months and 24-months follow-up was only reported by Mosha, Kulkarni⁴ for both formulations of DAI ITNs. For the data at both the 12-month time point and 24-month time point, the authors have reported that clusters receiving either chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs (figure 7, figure 9) or pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs (figure 29, figure 31) resulted in a reduction of parasite prevalence, compared to clusters receiving the pyrethroid-only ITN. All findings for these four outcomes were associated with high certainty in the evidence (table 1, table 3).

For parasite prevalence at 18-months, the evidence suggests that clusters that receive either formulation of DAI ITN will result in a reduction of parasite prevalence (figure 8, figure 30). However, chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs appear to offer a greater reduction in parasite prevalence, associated with higher certainty of the evidence (table 1), compared to the reduction offered by pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs (table 3), which was only associated with moderate evidence.

Only one study⁴ compared both formulations of DAI ITN against pyrethroid-PBO ITNs. Compared to pyrethroid-PBO ITNs, the authors have reported that clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs were associated with reduced malaria case incidence when collapsed across time points (figure 16), for 1-year post intervention (figure 17), and for 2-years post intervention (figure 18). These findings were associated with high, low, and high certainty of the evidence, respectively (table 2). Likewise, for the outcome of parasite prevalence a reduction was observed for the clusters that received chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs at 12-months (figure 19), 18-months (figure 20) and 24-months (figure 21) post follow-up. These findings were associated with moderate, moderate, and high certainty in the evidence, respectively (table 2).

For clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs, the authors have reported that compared to clusters that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs, there was an increase in malaria case incidence when collapsed across time points (figure 38), at 1-year post intervention (figure 39), and for 2-years post intervention (figure 40). These findings were associated with high, high, and moderate certainty of the evidence (table 4). This was also consistent for the outcome of parasite prevalence, where increases were observed for parasite prevalence in the clusters that received pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs at 12-months (figure 41), 18-months (figure 42), and 24-months (figure 43) post follow-up compared to those that received pyrethroid-PBO ITNs. These findings were associated with moderate, high, and moderate certainty of the evidence, respectively (table 4).

Only three studies were identified that met the inclusion criteria of this review, however all these studies are recent (within the last 5 years) have compared similar interventions, have implemented the interventions uniformly achieving high coverage, and have reported similar results. The major differences between these studies included the manufacturer of the ITNs compared, the main vectors of interest and their setting. However, upon conducting subgroup analyses (Appendix 4) and ICEMAN credibility assessments (Appendix 5) none of these factors were deemed to be effect modifiers.

All studies were cluster randomised controlled trials and therefore, the overall certainty in the body of evidence started as high. The impact of DAI ITNs has been evaluated in lower-level evidence, however this has not contributed to the evidence synthesised as part of this review.

Evidence for outcomes was only downgraded for inconsistency or imprecision as appropriate and documented in the footnotes of tables 1, 2, 3 and 4. The evidence for all outcomes under all four comparisons investigated was either high or moderate, except the outcomes of prevalence of anaemia (table 2, 3 and 4) and malaria case incidence (1-year post intervention) (table 4).

Publication bias was unable to be assessed during this review as only three studies were included. However, the comprehensive search strategy and reaching out to authors directly ameliorated some concerns of publication bias in this review.

Conclusion

We have high certainty evidence that chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs and pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid ITNs are more effective than pyrethroid-only ITNs in reducing malaria case incidence. This benefit also extends to parasite prevalence for which we have moderate-high certainty evidence. However, only chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid ITNs demonstrated a reduction in these outcomes when compared to pyrethroid-PBO ITNs.

Despite most of this evidence being high-moderate certainty, only three studies were included in this review. These studies were conducted in high transmission settings, and additional studies conducted in other transmission settings would further strengthen the evidence base in favour of DAI ITNs. Future trials should also explore these interventions for longer than 2-years post implementation of the intervention to provide more robust data as to their long-term effectiveness.

Contributors

Declaration of interests

Data sharing

Acknowledgments

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Deviations from protocol

1. No need to adjust standard errors for failing to account for clustering as all studies had done so appropriately
2. The following subgroups were specified in the protocol but were not conducted for the stated reasons
 - a. Level of transmission; (High: incidence of about 450 cases/1000 persons/year or Plasmodium falciparum (Pf) / Plasmodium vivax (Pv) prevalence of $\geq 35\%$; Moderate: incidence of 250-450 per 1000 persons per year and Pf/Pv prevalence of 10-35%; Low: incidence of 100-250 per 1000 persons per year and Pf/Pv prevalence of 1-10%; Very low: incidence of <100 per 1000 persons per year and Pf/Pv prevalence $<1\%$.) (the level of transmission will be categorized according to the schema found in the *Framework for malaria elimination*)²⁴ ; seasonality of transmission (Not conducted as all studies were from high transmission settings)
 - b. Species of parasite (Not conducted as all studies explored P. falciparum)
 - c. Coverage of intervention applied and level of net coverage per person or household (Not conducted as all studies had a high intervention coverage)
 - d. Durability of net and insecticides used (No study had provided sufficient data regarding net durability. As the assessment of durability was not the focus of this review this subgroup has been omitted).
 - e. Characteristics of insecticides used, e.g., target sites, modes of action, and duration required to produce such effect(s). (The subgrouping parameters of this pre-specified group were identical to

- the “insecticide class” subgroup that has been presented in the review. As such, these two subgroups have been combined and reported together in the review.
- f. Population demographics e.g., sex/age/SES/ethnicity etc. All included studies provided population demographics for the study cohorts. These demographics were similar enough to not warrant subgrouping).
 - g. Human behaviour (e.g. sleeping behaviour) (Two studies had provided this information, however one study had not. After contacting the authors for this information, it was not received and the two remaining studies were not different enough to warrant subgrouping).
 - h. Coverage of other background interventions. (All included studies confirmed that no other interventions were being carried out in the trial region during the study period. As such, no subgrouping necessary).
3. Sensitivity analyses was originally planned conducted to analyse the following (below). However, as all the included studies were at low risk of bias, and had appropriately controlled for clustering it was unnecessary.
- a. The impact of bias by excluding studies that are at a high risk of bias.
 - b. Where we have inflated standard errors for trials where cluster designs have not been considered, we will analyse trials as if the individual was the unit of randomisation.
4. The following outcomes were not included in the GRADE evidence profiles due to a lack of available data from the included studies:
- a. Malaria infection incidence
 - b. Incidence of severe disease
 - c. All-cause mortality
 - d. Malaria mortality

References

Appendix 1 – Search Strategies

Databases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PubMed (NCBI) • Embase (Ovid), • CINAHL with Full Text (EBSCO) • Cochrane Library (Wiley)
Trial Registries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ClinicalTrials.gov, • WHO ICTRP • ISRCTN Trial Registry
Seed Articles	32699237 [uid] OR 35339225 [uid]
Date Run	6/7/2022
PubMed (NCBI)	3246
Embase (Ovid)	4705
CINAHL with Full Text (EBSCO)	417
Cochrane Library (Wiley)	630
ClinicalTrials.gov	220
WHO ICTRP	14
ISRCTN Trial Registry	262
TOTAL RESULTS	9494
Search Created By	Carrie Price, MLS, Health Professions Librarian Albert S. Cook Library Towson University Towson, MD, USA

PubMed (NCBI)

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AND

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AND

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Embase (Ovid)

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2	(black water fever or black water fevers or blackwater fever or blackwater fevers or malaria* or marsh fever or marsh fevers or p falciparum or p falciparum or paludism or plasmodia or plasmodial or plasmodiosis or plasmodium or plasmodiums or remittent fever or remittent fevers or swamp fever or swamp fevers).mp.	142794

3	1 or 2	142794
4	bed net/ or insecticide treated net/	6085
5	(bednet OR bednets OR insecticide treated net OR insecticide treated nets OR insecticide treated bednet OR insecticide treated bednets OR insecticide treated bed net OR insecticide treated bed nets OR itn s OR itn OR itns OR llin* OR long lasting insecticidal net OR long lasting insecticidal nets OR long lasting insecticide net OR long lasting insecticide nets OR mesh OR meshes OR net OR nets OR netting).mp.	245605
6	4 or 5	245605
7	allethrin/ or diflubenzuron/ or fenoxycarb/ or juvenile hormone/ or kinoprene/or permethrin/ or piperonyl butoxide/ or pyriproxyfen/ or pyrethrin/ or pyrethroid/	19450
8	('2' or two).ti,ab. or (2gard or abate or actellic or acticin or agent* or allethrin* or alphacypermethrin or altosid or ambush or aqua k-othrine or aqua reslin super or aquatain amf or armol or atroban or bacillus or bendiocarb or bifenthrin or bioallethrin or biomopedicul or bistar 10wp or chlorfenapyr* or cielo ulv or cispermethrin or clothianidin or cypermethrin* or cyphenothrin or dai s or dai or dais or deltamethrin or device 25wp or diflubenzuron or dimilin or dinotefuran or dioflubenzuron or doubl* or dronol or dual or dually or du-dim 2 dt or duranet or ectiban or ectomethrin or elimite or etofenprox or expar or fastm or fendona or fenoxycarb or ficam or fludora or flupyradifurone or fmc 33297 or fmc33297 or fyfanon or g2 or gamabenceno or gamaderm or gepescab or gokilaht-s 5ec or icon or iconlife or ig2 or imidacloprid or infectomite or infectopedicul or insect growth regulator* or interceptor or interceptor g2 or interceptorg2 or ipevet or ipevetex or juvenile hormone* or k othrine or kinoprene or klinits or klypson 500 wg or kothrine or lambda cyhalothrin or lambdacyhalothrin or limitor 5 gr or loxazol or lyclear or magnet or malathion or methoprene or miranet or mosquiron 100ec or mozkill or nedax plus or net protect or netprotect or new nok or nix or nonpyrethroid* or novaluron or novo herklin or nrdc 143 or nrdc 147 or olyset or olysetnet or olysetplus or oms 1821 or pali 250 wg or panda or pandanet or pbo or pdms or pendulum or perigen or permanet or permanone or permectrin or permethrin* or permicren or permite or piopel or piperonyl butoxide* or pirimiphos methyl or pirimiphosmethyl or polydimethylsiloxane or pounce or pp	15940831

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9	7 or 8	15940831
10	3 and 6 and 9	4705

CINAHL Plus with Full Text

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AND

(MH "mosquito nets" OR "bednet" OR "bednets" OR "insecticide treated net" OR "insecticide treated nets" OR "insecticide treated bednet" OR "insecticide treated bednets" OR "insecticide treated bed net" OR "insecticide treated bed nets" OR "itn s" OR "itn" OR "itns" OR "lin*" OR "long lasting insecticidal net" OR "long lasting insecticidal nets" OR "long lasting insecticide net" OR "long lasting insecticide nets" OR "mesh" OR "meshes" OR "net" OR "nets" OR "netting")

AND

("pyriproxifen" OR "2" OR "2gard" OR "abate" OR "actellic" OR "acticin" OR "agent*" OR "allethrin*" OR "alphacypermethrin" OR "altosid" OR "ambush" OR "aqua k-othrine " OR "aqua reslin super" OR "aquatain amf" OR "armol " OR "atroban" OR "bacillus" OR "bendiocarb" OR "bifenthrin" OR "bioallethrin" OR "biomopedicul " OR "bistar 10wp" OR "chlorfenapyr*" OR "cielo ulv" OR "cispermethrin" OR "clothianidin" OR "cypermethrin*" OR "cyphenothrin" OR "dai s" OR "dai" OR "dais" OR "deltamethrin" OR "device 25wp" OR "diflubenzuron" OR "dimilin" OR "dinotefuran" OR "dioflubenzuron" OR "doubl*" OR "dronol" OR "dual" OR "dually" OR "du-dim 2 dt" OR "duranet" OR "ectiban" OR "ectomethrin " OR "elimite " OR "etofenprox" OR "expar" OR "fastm" OR "fendona" OR "fenoxycarb" OR "ficam " OR "fludora" OR "flupyradifurone" OR "fmc 33297 " OR "fmc33297 " OR "fyfanon" OR "g2" OR "gamabenceno" OR "gamaderm" OR "gepescab " OR "gokilaht-s 5ec " OR "icon" OR "iconlife" OR "ig2" OR "imidacloprid" OR "infectomite " OR "infectopedicul" OR "insect growth regulator*" OR "interceptor " OR "interceptor g2" OR "interceptorg2 " OR "ipevet" OR "ipevetex" OR "juvenile hormone*" OR "k othrine" OR "kinoprene" OR "klinits" OR "klypson 500 wg" OR "kothrine" OR "lambda cyhalothrin" OR "lambdacyhalothrin" OR "limitor 5 gr" OR "loxazol" OR "lyclear " OR "magnet" OR "malathion" OR "methoprene" OR "miranet" OR "mosquiron 100ec" OR "mozkill" OR "nedax plus" OR "net protect" OR "netprotect" OR "new nok" OR "nix" OR "nonpyrethroid*" OR "novaluron" OR "novo herklin" OR "nrdc 143" OR "nrdc 147 " OR "olyset" OR "olysetnet" OR "olysetplus" OR "oms 1821" OR "pali 250 wg" OR "panda" OR "pandanet" OR "pbo" OR "pdms" OR "pendulum" OR "perigen" OR "permanet" OR "permanone " OR "permectrin" OR "permethrin*" OR "permicren" OR "permite" OR "piopel" OR "piperonyl

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Cochrane Library (Wiley)

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AND

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ClinicalTrials.gov

Malaria AND net	95
Malaria AND bednet	57
Malaria AND LLIN	31
Malaria AND ITN	37
TOTAL	220

Search terms are automatically truncated. "net" returns "nets".

WHO ICTRP

Malaria (condition) AND net (intervention)	0
Malaria (condition) AND nets (intervention)	6
Malaria (condition) AND bednet (intervention)	1
Malaria (condition) AND bednets (intervention)	0
Malaria (condition) AND LLIN (intervention)	4
Malaria (condition) AND LLINs (intervention)	2
Malaria (condition) AND ITN (intervention)	1

Malaria (condition) AND ITNs (intervention)	0
TOTAL	14

ISRCTN

Malaria

262

Appendix 2 – Studies excluded at full text

Title	Authors	Exclusion Reason
Department of Error		Wrong study design
Does IPTi decrease malaria morbidity but not mortality? Christine Stabell Benn ¹	Aaby, P.	Wrong study design
Bio-efficacy of new long-lasting insecticide-treated bed nets against <i>Anopheles funestus</i> and <i>Anopheles gambiae</i> from central and northern Mozambique	Abilio, A. P.; Marrune, P.; De Deus, N.; Mbofana, F.; Muianga, P.; Kampango, A.	Wrong outcomes
Effect of insecticide-treated bednets for malaria control in Southeast Anatolia-Turkey	Alten, B.; Caglar, S. S.; Simsek, F. M.; Kaynas, S.	Wrong intervention
The effectiveness of permethrin-impregnated bed nets for malaria control in Kg. Ganoh, an Orang Asli area of Rompin District, Pahang	Amal, N. M.; Yussof, S.	Wrong study design
Long-term use of insecticide treated bed nets reduces malaria transmission and death rates in children	Anonymous,	Wrong intervention
Mosquito nets protect children from malaria	Anonymous,	Wrong study design
A cluster randomized controlled cross-over bed net acceptability and preference trial in Solomon Islands: Community participation in shaping policy for malaria elimination	Atkinson, J. A.; Bobogare, A.; Vallely, A.; Boaz, L.; Kelly, G.; Basifiri, W.; Forsyth, S.; Baker, P.; Appleyard, B.; Toaliu, H.; Williams, G.	Wrong intervention
Pyrethroid resistance in sub-Saharan Africa	Bajunirwe, Francis	Wrong study design
Evaluation of Interceptor long-lasting insecticidal nets in eight communities in Liberia	Banek, K.; Kilian, A.; Allan, R.	Wrong intervention
Seeing (RED)	Benn, C.	Wrong study design
Malaria elimination: Worthy, challenging, and just possible	Das, P.; Horton, R.	Wrong study design
Insecticide treated nets - Technological & operational challenges	Dash, A. P.; Yadav, R. S.	Wrong study design
Randomised trials in child health in developing countries 2011	Duke, T.	Wrong study design
Bed nets prove their mettle against malaria	Enserink, M.	Wrong study design
Use of insecticide-treated nets by pregnant and childbearing-age women: Action research in Southern Nigeria	Esienumoh, Ekpoanwan; Mboho, Margaret; Ndiok, Akon	Wrong study design
Pyriproxyfen-treated bed nets reduce reproductive fitness and longevity of pyrethroid-resistant <i>Anopheles gambiae</i> under laboratory and field conditions	Grisales, N.; Lees, R. S.; Maas, J.; Morgan, J. C.; Wangrawa, D. W.; Guelbeogo, W. M.; N'Fale, S.; Lindsay, S. W.; McCall, P. J.; Ranson, H.	Wrong outcomes
Evidence supporting deployment of next generation insecticide treated nets in Burkina Faso: bioassays with either chlorfenapyr or	Hien, A. S.; Soma, D. D.; Maiga, S.; Coulibaly, D.; Diabate, A.; Belemvire, A.; Diouf, M. B.; Jacob, D.; Kone, A.	Wrong outcomes

piperonyl butoxide increase mortality of pyrethroid-resistant <i>Anopheles gambiae</i>	Dotson, E.; Awolola, T. S.; Oxborough, R. M.; Dabire, R. K.	
Control of malaria vectors and management of insecticide resistance through universal coverage with next-generation insecticide-treated nets	Killeen, G. F.	Wrong study design
Malaria nets shape up for resistance	Lines, J.	Wrong study design
Insecticide products: Treatment of mosquito nets at home	Lines, J. D.; Zaim, M.	Wrong study design
Comparative functional survival and equivalent annual cost of 3 long-lasting insecticidal net (LLIN) products in Tanzania: A randomised trial with 3-year follow up	Lorenz, L. M.; Bradley, J.; Yukich, J.; Massue, D. J.; Mboma, Z. M.; Pigeon, O.; Moore, J.; Kilian, A.; Lines, J.; Kisinza, W.; Overgaard, H. J.; Moore, S. J.	Wrong intervention
Life shortening effect of Olyset Duo, a longlasting insecticidal net incorporating a mixture of pyrethroid and pyriproxyfen, against pyrethroidresistant mosquito	Lucas, J. R.; Invest, J.; Ohashi, K.; Teshima, H.; Shono, Y.	Wrong intervention
Comparing the durability of the long-lasting insecticidal nets DawaPlus 2.0 and DuraNet© in northwest Democratic Republic of Congo	Mansiangi, P.; Umesumbu, S.; Eteawa, I.; Zandibeni, J.; Bafwa, N.; Blaufuss, S.; Olapeju, B.; Ntoya, F.; Sadou, A.; Irish, S.; Mukomena, E.; Kalindula, L.; Watsenga, F.; Akogbeto, M.; Babalola, S.; Koenker, H.; Kilian, A.	Wrong study design
Durability of three types of dual active ingredient long-lasting insecticidal net compared to a pyrethroid-only LLIN in Tanzania: methodology for a prospective cohort study nested in a cluster randomized controlled trial	Martin, J. L.; Messenger, L. A.; Mosha, F. W.; Lukole, E.; Mosha, J. F.; Kulkarni, M.; Churcher, T. S.; Sherrard-Smith, E.; Manjurano, A.; Protopopoff, N.; Rowland, M.	Wrong outcomes
Effectiveness of two types of long lasting insecticidal nets after two years of use for malaria vector control in an area of high pyrethroid resistance, muleba -tanzania	Martine, J. L.; Protopopof, N.; Magesa, S.; Mosha, F. W.	Wrong study design
Evaluation of next generation of insecticide treated nets: the Tanzanian experiences	Mosha, J. F.; Lukole, E.; Mosha, F. W.; Manjurano, A.; Martin, J.; Kulkarni, M.; Mwalimu, C. D.; Rowland, M.; Protopopoff, N.	Wrong study design
Estimating the Malaria Prevention Impact of New Nets: Observational Analyses to Evaluate the Evidence Generated During Piloted New Net Distributions in Rwanda	PATH; Rwanda Biomedical Centre; University of Rwanda; Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine	Wrong study design
Estimating the Malaria Prevention Impact of New Nets: Observational Analyses to Evaluate the Evidence Generated During Piloted New Net Distributions in Mozambique	PATH; Tropical Health LLP; Ministry of Health, Mozambique; Instituto Nacional de Saúde; Tulane University; Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine	Wrong study design
A new promising long lasting insecticide net in the control of insecticide resistant vectors: Olyset Duo: A pyriproxyfen and permethrin mixture net	Protopopoff, N.; Oxborough, R.; Irish, S.; Malone, D.; Mosha, F. W.; Rowland, M.	Wrong study design
Accelerating the evidence for new classes of long-lasting insecticide-treated nets	Protopopoff, N.; Rowland, M.	Wrong study design

Durability, household usage and washing pattern of DuraNet(©) and Interceptor(®) long-lasting insecticidal nets in long-term field trials in India	Sharma, S. K.; Yadav, R. S.; Srivastava, H. C.; Bhatt, R. M.; Pant, C. S.; Haque, M. A.; Sreehari, U.; Raghavendra, K.	Wrong intervention
The impact of Olyset net and DawaPlus 2.0 on the risk of plasmodium infection in Gembe East, Western Kenya	Tamari, N.; Sonye, G. O.; Awuor, B.; Kongere, J. O.; Hashimoto, M.; Kataoka, M.; Munga, S.; Minakawa, N.	Wrong outcomes
Erratum: Assessing the impact of the addition of pyriproxyfen on the durability of permethrin-treated bed nets in Burkina Faso: A compound-randomized controlled trial (Malaria Journal (2019) 8 (383) DOI: 10.1186/s12936-019-3018-1)	Toe, K. H.; Mechan, F.; Tangena, J. A. A.; Morris, M.; Solino, J.; Tchicaya, E. F. S.; Traore, A.; Ismail, H.; Maas, J.; Lissenden, N.; Pinder, M.; Lindsay, S. W.; Tiono, A. B.; Ranson, H.; Sagnon, N.	Wrong outcomes
Assessing the impact of the addition of pyriproxyfen on the durability of permethrin-treated bed nets in Burkina Faso: A compound-randomized controlled trial	Toe, K. H.; Mechan, F.; Tangena, J. A. A.; Morris, M.; Solino, J.; Tchicaya, E. F. S.; Traore, A.; Ismail, H.; Maas, J.; Lissenden, N.; Pinder, M.; Lindsay, S. W.; Tiono, A. B.; Ranson, H.; Sagnon, N.	Wrong outcomes
Effectiveness of a long-lasting insecticide treatment kit (ICON® Maxx) for polyester nets over three years of household use: a WHO phase III trial in Tanzania	Tungu, P. K.; Sudi, W.; Kisinza, W.; Rowland, M.	Wrong outcomes

Appendix 3 – Characteristics of included studies

Accrombessi 2021

<p>Study: Assessing the efficacy of two dual-active ingredients long-lasting insecticidal nets for the control of malaria transmitted by pyrethroid-resistant vectors in Benin: study protocol for a three-arm, single-blinded, parallel, cluster-randomized controlled trial</p> <p>AND</p> <p>Preliminary data collected from direct correspondence with the authors</p> <p><i>*Reviewer note, all of this methodological detail has been collected from the protocol, and is presented in the future tense as appropriate. Details of methods actually conducted were not provided by the authors*</i></p>	
DESIGN	
Lead Author	Manfred Accrombessi (protocol author)
Publication year	Protocol published in 2021, publication of results is pending
Trial name	Part of a larger project called “The new net project”
Other reports of this study (i.e., author, year, title, doi)	Protocol – Accrombessi (2021) Final results to be published at later date
Time period study was conducted	Intervention distribution occurred in March 2020. Outcomes data is still being collected, however outcomes reported by the authors are up to 20-months post-intervention.
Design	Three-arm superiority, cluster-randomised controlled trial
Eligibility criteria of participants	<p>The cohort will include children aged 6 months to 9 years old resident in the study villages, without any severe illnesses and whose parents/carers have given written informed consent for their child to be included in the study. The participant also needed to be a resident of the study area for the past three months to be eligible to contribute data via the cross-sectional surveys.</p> <p>Age-stratified individuals are randomly selected from each cluster using the census list generated during the registration activity. A maximum of two household members will be selected at random, using a random number table.</p> <p>The inclusion criteria are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For adults: willing to participate and provide consent • For children: Having an adult caregiver willing to provide written consent for the household and clinical survey and assent for children over 10. • Residence in the village over the last 3 months <p>Exclusion criteria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dwelling not found or vacant during the survey • No adult caregiver capable to give informed consent • Habitants severely ill
Recruitment methods and rate	<p>Using satellite map we identified and geo-located 60 villages within the district that are accessible and within a travelling time from the office in Cove town of less than 2 hours’ drive and ideally at a distance of minimum 2 kilometers from each other. Each cluster will be comprised of 1 hamlet/ village for a total number of houses of 200 household (1200 residents) per cluster.</p> <p>The selection of the 60 clusters for the main study will be based on the following criteria determined from the baseline cross-sectional survey:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Hamlet leader and population acceptance 2. Within 2 hours drive from Cove Office

	<p>3. Clusters with estimated malaria infection prevalence over 30% (from baseline cross sectional survey)</p> <p>4. Clusters minimum 2 km apart</p> <p>To estimate malaria case incidence, a cohort of 25 children per cluster aged 6 months to 9 years will be randomly selected from a census list of children living in the study clusters and followed over 24 months. For malaria infection prevalence assessment, two cross-sectional surveys will be conducted at 6 and 18 months post-net distribution; 70 individuals per cluster will be randomly selected for each cross-sectional survey, stratified by age (< 5 years, 5–9 years, 10–14 years, ≥15 years and older) from each of the 60 clusters.</p>
Unit of allocation	Village was the unit of randomisation (60 clusters)
Method of Randomization/ matching or other	The protocol states that “Restricted randomisation will be used to allocate the clusters to arms in order to ensure that they are balanced on known factors that may affect the main outcomes. The following factors will be used: baseline (pre-intervention) malaria infection prevalence in children aged 0.5 to 10 years, cluster-level LLIN usage (prior to distribution), socio-economic status, village size, species composition (proportion <i>An.gambiae</i> / <i>An.coluzzii</i>) and distance to nearest health facility”
Number of clusters per arm	20 clusters per arm (60 clusters total)
Adjustment for clustering	The statistical analysis plan provided by the authors states “...using a Cox proportional hazards model allowing for multiple events per child and using robust estimates of variance to account for the clustered design” and “...The unit of analysis will be the individual participant with clustering account for using random effects”
Cluster details (including buffer sizes between clusters, other indication of dilution effects)	<p>Each cluster will be comprised of 1 village or a group of villages for an average of 200 households (1200 residents) per cluster. Clusters will have a minimum of 100 children and 100 households.</p> <p>A “fried egg” design will be used for cluster boundaries. Clusters will be designed with core and buffer areas to reduce the likelihood of spillover of intervention effects. Nets will be distributed to all households in a cluster (i.e. core and buffer areas) but data collection to measure intervention effects will be restricted to households situated in the core areas to avoid spillover from neighbouring clusters receiving different nets. The cluster demarcation will be performed using the spatial analyst toolbox in ArcGIS (ESRI, Redlands, USA) based on the following criteria; a minimum of 50 children aged 6 months to 10 years in the core area and a buffer of minimum 1000 m between core households and any households in an adjacent cluster.</p>
Number of participants per arm (including number of exclusions and reasons)	<p>Each cluster will be comprised of 1 village or a group of villages for an average of 200 households (1200 residents) per cluster. Clusters will have a minimum of 100 children and 100 households.</p> <p>Clusters would have a minimum of 100 children and 100 households to get a minimum of 50 children less than 10 years to be enrolled in the cohort.</p> <p>A cohort of 30 children per cluster aged 6 months to 10 years old will be randomly selected from a census list of children living in the study clusters at the beginning of the first year and followed every two weeks/1 month over a 21 months period.</p>

Outcomes assessed	Malaria Case Incidence Rate Parasite Prevalence Prevalence of Anaemia
SETTING	
Country	Benin
Site/s (town/settlements/region)	Cove, Zagnanado, and Ouinhi Districts, located in the Zou department, central Benin, 154 km north of Cotonou. This area consists of 123 villages with approximately 54,000 households and population size of 220,000 inhabitants. The main economic activities of the population are farming, fishing, hunting, and trading.
Peak transmission season	April to November with two peaks during the rainy seasons from April to July and then from October to November
Baseline malaria endemicity/ level of transmission	A prevalence of malaria infection between 20 to 40%. Malaria is highly endemic, and Malaria infection prevalence in the Zou department was 20% in children under 5 years old according to the demographic health survey (DHS) conducted in 2011 to 2012 and increased to 36.5% in the 2017–2018 DHS.
Study site (e.g., rural/ urban/ peri-urban/ level of urbanicity)	Rural
Vector species and vector profile details (i.e., behaviours, resistance profile/ susceptibility tests, parity, sporozoite rates and all other reported information)	Main vector species were Anopheles coluzzii and Anopheles gambiae sensu stricto. High pyrethroid resistance in the main malaria vectors. Entomological surveys performed in the Cove region in 2015 revealed high levels of pyrethroid resistance intensity (> 200 fold) mainly due to high frequencies of kdr of > 90% and elevated cytochrome P450 enzymes.
Malaria species	P. falciparum
PARTICIPANTS (those who received the intervention and on whom impact was measured)	
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants who received the intervention	"In the cohort we had 48% female children (aged 6 months to 10 years)." "In the 6 month cross-sectional we had 45% female and in the 18 month cross-sectional we had 54% female. The cross sectionals were all ages" - Direct correspondence with author
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants on whom the impact was measured.	The cohort will include children aged 6 months to 9 years old resident in the study villages, without any severe illnesses and whose parents/carers have given written informed consent for their child to be included in the study. Inclusion criteria during cross-sectional surveys will be the willingness to participate and provide consent (or for parents/carers to provide consent for children); resident in the village during the previous 3 months, selected individuals without severe illness.
Frequency of travel in the last month	Not reported
INTERVENTION 1	
Dual AI net brand, insecticide type, dose, material of net (including active ingredient, timing and frequency of application, durability of the net and insecticide)	Interceptor G2 Mixture LLIN made of polyester netting (100 deniers) coated with a wash-resistant formulation of 200 mg/m ² chlorfenapyr and 100 mg/m ² alpha-cypermethrin. The nets are blue, rectangular, and identical sizes (1.8m long, 1.6m wide, and 1.8m high)
Net treatment strategy	Not reported

(e.g., how were the nets treated with the insecticide(s))	
Deployment strategy of nets (e.g., who received the nets? Where the houses in which they were installed permanent? What was the frequency of distribution?)	<p>A short questionnaire will be used to collect demographic details on household residents to estimate the number of nets required to be distributed in each house and to randomly select children for the cohort. Each building will be mapped using a Global Positioning System to assist with delineating clusters.</p> <p>Nets will be distributed with the support of the National Malaria Control Programme (NMCP). All households in the study area will receive one net for every two people. The census listing will be used to facilitate net distribution at a central location in each hamlet.</p> <p>One LLIN was given to every two people as recommended by NMCP. The study LLIN requirement has been calculated following standard guideline to cover 100% of the study area population (population divided by 1.6 to account for households with uneven numbers of members). The household listing, generated during the house mapping and registration, will be used to distribute the LLIN at a central location in each hamlet. Householders will be asked to return their old net and use the new LLIN provided.</p>
How was the intervention measured? (e.g. how was net usage monitored/observed by the authors? How was coverage of nets measured?)	<p>The coverage achieved in each cluster will be evaluated through a post-intervention coverage survey one month after distribution. Net coverage and usage will also be assessed during cohort visits and cross-sectional surveys. Three indicators will be used: proportion of households with at least one ITN for every 2 people”, “proportion of household members with enough ITNs to sleep under (population access)” and “proportion of residents reporting using an ITN last night</p>
Coverage of household / person (% of households with at least 1 ITN % of households with at least 1 ITN for every 2 people % of population with access to an ITN Nets per HH or per person)	<p>One LLIN was given to every two people as recommended by NMCP (1 to 2 people =1 LLIN, 3/4 people=2 LLINs, 5/6= 3 LLINs etc...). The study LLIN requirement has been calculated following standard guideline to cover 100% of the study area population (population divided by 1.6 to account for households with uneven numbers of members). The household listing, generated during the house mapping and registration, will be used to distribute the LLIN at a central location in each hamlet. Householders will be asked to return their old net and use the new LLIN provided.</p>
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	Not reported (however protocol suggests aiming of 85% access with 75% usage).
Length of intervention and time points of outcome measurement	Outcomes measured at 6, 18 and 24 months. Intervention was maintained throughout
Changes in human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, non-intervention-based spraying of houses)	No other interventions were conducted in the area (including IRS) - Direct correspondence with author
Background interventions (all reported in primary study – e.g., spraying prior to treatment period (and during) including coverage of background interventions. Other malaria or vector-specific control interventions [indoor surface treatment, nets/ other insecticides/ barrier], cointerventions, treatment of individuals that may impact outcome)	To reach a minimum of 85% access following the distribution and a minimum of 75% usage, information, education, and communication (IEC) activities will be conducted before, during, and after LLIN distribution to increase usage in the study area, including instructions on when and how to wash the nets. A door to door hang-up campaign will take place after the distribution and depending on net usage rates, subsequent hang-up campaigns will be organized to increase net usage. Throughout the study, community health workers will be utilized to

	encourage continuous net use in the study population. Hamlet and religious leaders will be also involved in the sensitization campaigns for net usage.
INTERVENTION 2	
Dual AI net brand, insecticide type, dose, material of net (including active ingredient, timing and frequency of application, durability of the net and insecticide)	Royal Guard Mixture LLIN made of polyethylene (120 deniers) incorporating 225 mg/m ² pyriproxyfen and 261 mg/m ² alpha-cypermethrin. The nets are blue, rectangular, and identical sizes (1.8m long, 1.6m wide, and 1.8m high).
Net treatment strategy (e.g., how were the nets treated with the insecticide(s))	Not reported
Deployment strategy of nets (e.g., who received the nets? Where the houses in which they were installed permanent? What was the frequency of distribution?)	Same as above (Intervention 1)
How was the intervention measured? (e.g. how was net usage monitored/observed by the authors? How was coverage of nets measured?)	Same as above (Intervention 1)
Coverage of household / person (% of households with at least 1 ITN % of households with at least 1 ITN for every 2 people % of population with access to an ITN Nets per HH or per person)	Same as above (Intervention 1)
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	Not reported (however protocol suggests aiming of 85% access with 75% usage).
Length of intervention and time points of outcome measurement	Outcomes measured at 6, 18 and 24 months. Intervention was maintained throughout
Changes in human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, non-intervention-based spraying of houses)	Not reported
Background interventions (all reported in primary study – e.g., spraying prior to treatment period (and during) including coverage of background interventions. Other malaria or vector-specific control interventions [indoor surface treatment, nets/ other insecticides/ barrier], cointerventions, treatment of individuals that may impact outcome)	Same as above (Intervention 1)
COMPARISON	
Dual AI net brand, insecticide type, dose, material of net (including active ingredient, timing and frequency of application, durability of the net and insecticide)	Interceptor LLIN A pyrethroid-treated LLIN with alpha-cypermethrin (coated onto filaments) at a target dose of 200 mg/m ² of polyester fabric (100 deniers). The nets are blue, rectangular, and identical sizes (1.8m long, 1.6m wide, and 1.8m high).

Net treatment strategy (e.g., how were the nets treated with the insecticide(s))	Not reported
Deployment strategy of nets (e.g., who received the nets? Where the houses in which they were installed permanent? What was the frequency of distribution?)	Same as above (Intervention 1)
How was the intervention measured? (e.g. how was net usage monitored/observed by the authors? How was coverage of nets measured?)	Same as above (Intervention 1)
Coverage of household / person (% of households with at least 1 ITN % of households with at least 1 ITN for every 2 people % of population with access to an ITN Nets per HH or per person)	Same as above (Intervention 1)
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	Not reported (however protocol suggests aiming of 85% access with 75% usage).
Length of intervention and time points of outcome measurement	Outcomes measured at 6, 18 and 24 months. Intervention was maintained throughout
Changes in human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, non-intervention-based spraying of houses)	Not reported
Any other details regarding comparator not described elsewhere.	Same as above (Intervention 1)
MALARIA CASE INCIDENCE RATE	
Defined as symptoms plus parasitaemia, over a population at risk or person-time. Detected either through passive or active surveillance.	
Name	As above
Definition/ assessment metric	The primary outcome is malaria case incidence in children aged 6 months to 10 years over 24 months. A malaria case is defined as an infra-rouge frontal temperature above 37.5 °C or history of a fever in the last 48 h and a positive rapid diagnostic test (RDT). Malaria case incidence was measured in an active cohort of approximately 30 children per cluster followed up for 20 months (for 2 years following the net distribution- follow up was delayed immediately following the net distribution due to the Covid pandemic).
Events	Data presented as no. clinical episodes (follow-up time child-years) <u>OVERALL</u> Pyrethroid-only LLIN Group = 898 (874.4) Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid Group = 743 (883.9) Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid Group = 494 (887.3) <u>YEAR 1</u> Pyrethroid-only LLIN Group = 268 (344.5) Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid Group = 211 (342.7) Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid Group = 124 (349.2)

	<p><u>YEAR 2</u> Pyrethroid-only LLIN Group = 630 (529.9) Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid Group = 532 (541.2) Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid Group = 370 (538.1)</p>
Total (or unit time)	Unit time presented above
Time of outcome assessment	Year 1 and 2 presented above as is combined data
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	<p>Results presented as incidence per child-year (95% CI for each group)</p> <p><u>OVERALL</u> Pyrethroid-only LLIN Group = 1.02 (0.96 – 1.09) Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid Group = 0.84 (0.78 – 0.90) Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid Group = 0.56 (0.51 – 0.61)</p> <p><u>YEAR 1</u> Pyrethroid-only LLIN Group = 0.77 (0.69 – 0.87) Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid Group = 0.61 (0.54 – 0.7) Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid Group = 0.35 (0.29 – 0.42)</p> <p><u>YEAR 2</u> Pyrethroid-only LLIN Group = 1.19 (1.09 – 1.28) Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid Group = 0.98 (0.9 – 1.07) Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid Group = 0.69 (0.62 – 0.76)</p>
Effect type	IRR
MALARIA INFECTION INCIDENCE	
Defined as parasitaemia with or without symptoms, over a population at risk or person-time. Detected through passive or active surveillance.	
Name	N/A
Definition/ assessment metric	N/A
Events	N/A
Total (or unit time)	N/A
Time of outcome assessment	N/A
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	N/A
Effect type	N/A
INCIDENCE OF SEVERE DISEASE	
Defined as hospitalization with parasitaemia, over a population at risk or person-time.	
Name	N/A
Definition/ assessment metric	N/A
Events	N/A
Total (or unit time)	N/A
Time of outcome assessment	N/A
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	N/A
Effect type	N/A
PARASITE PREVALENCE	

Parasitaemia with or without symptoms, over the population sampled. Detected through cross-sectional surveys.	
Name	As above
Definition/ assessment metric	Malaria infection prevalence in the study population at 6 and 18 months post bed net distribution. Prevalence was measured in cross-sectional surveys in a random sample of approximately 70 people per cluster, of any age. Infection was measured using RDT and people were tested regardless of symptoms. Cross-sectional surveys took place 6 and 18 months after net distribution.
Events	Results presented as n/N (%) <u>6 MONTHS POST-INTERVENTION</u> Pyrethroid-only LLIN Group = 412/1471 (28%) Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid Group = 394/1463 (26.9%) Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid Group = 231/1475 (15.7%) <u>18 MONTHS POST-INTERVENTION</u> Pyrethroid-only LLIN Group = 576/1489 (38.7%) Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid Group = 564/1468 (38.2%) Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid Group = 414/1483 (27.9%)
Total (or unit time)	As above
Time of outcome assessment	6 and 18 months post-intervention
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	Results presented in comparison to the pyrethroid-only group (reference) as OR (95% CI) and p-value <u>6 MONTHS POST-INTERVENTION</u> Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid Group = 0.92 (0.63-1.35) p = 0.6742 Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid Group = 0.47 (0.32-0.69) p = 0.0002 <u>18 MONTHS POST-INTERVENTION</u> Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid Group = 0.97 (0.69-1.37) p = 0.8724 Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid Group = 0.61 (0.43-0.85) p = 0.0041
Effect type	OR
ALL-CAUSE MORTALITY	
Number of deaths over the population at risk or person-time.	
Name	N/A
Definition/ assessment metric	N/A
Events	N/A
Total (or unit time)	N/A
Time of outcome assessment	N/A
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	N/A
Effect type	N/A
MALARIA MORTALITY	
Number of deaths attributed to malaria over the population at risk or person-time.	
Name	N/A
Definition/ assessment metric	N/A
Events	N/A

Total (or unit time)	N/A
Time of outcome assessment	N/A
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	N/A
Effect type	N/A
PREVALENCE OF ANAEMIA Defined by study thresholds of anaemia.	
Name	As above
Definition/ assessment metric	Anaemia was measured in children aged under 5 years in the cross-sectional surveys at 6 and 18 months post-net distribution. Hemoglobin (measured by Haemocue), defined as < 10 g/dL (moderate) and < 8 g/dL (severe).
Events	Results presented as n/N (%) <u>6 MONTHS POST-INTERVENTION</u> Pyrethroid-only LLIN Group = 99/241 (41.1%) Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid Group = 117/250 (46.8%) Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid Group = 82/241 (34%) <u>18 MONTHS POST-INTERVENTION</u> Pyrethroid-only LLIN Group = 118/252 (46.8%) Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid Group = 108/245 (44.1%) Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid Group = 118/246 (47.9%)
Total (or unit time)	As above
Time of outcome assessment	6 and 18 months post-intervention
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	Results presented in comparison to the pyrethroid-only group (reference) as OR (95% CI) and p-value <u>6 MONTHS POST-INTERVENTION</u> Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid Group = 1.24 (0.71-2.18) p = 0.4452 Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid Group = 0.71 (0.4-1.27) p = 0.2447 <u>18 MONTHS POST-INTERVENTION</u> Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid Group = 0.84 (0.39-1.79) p = 0.6545 Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid Group = 1.08 (0.51-2.228) p = 0.8429
Effect type	OR
COSTS	
Event/raw costs	Not reported
Results	Not reported
Time of cost assessment	Not reported
Resources needed/ used	Not reported
ADDITIONAL DATA	
Unintended benefits	Not reported
Harms	Collected according to protocol but not reported
Other contextual information present/measured/reported) (feasibility, acceptability, preferences/values, impact on equity)	Not reported

Entomological outcomes measured (list)	EIR, as a measure for malaria transmission rate in the primary vector species. Mosquito density and survivorship, mosquito resting behaviour, species composition, ovary development, and fecundity. Frequency and intensity of phenotypic and genotypic resistance to pyrethroid, chlorfenapyr, and pyriproxyfen insecticides. Prevalence of elevated cytochrome P450s and other metabolic enzymes associated with pyrethroid resistance.
Other	Not reported
Source of funding	This research is supported by a grant to the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine from UNITAID and Global Fund via the Innovative Vector Control Consortium (IVCC). This cluster-randomized clinical trial is part of a larger project "The New Net project". The funders do not play a role in study design, collection, management, analysis and interpretation of data. They do not influence the writing of the report and the decision to submit.
Possible conflicts of interest	The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	The protocol states that "Restricted randomisation will be used to allocate the clusters to arms in order to ensure that they are balanced on known factors that may affect the main outcomes. The following factors will be used: baseline (pre-intervention) malaria infection prevalence in children aged 0.5 to 10 years, cluster-level LLIN usage (prior to distribution), socio-economic status, village size, species composition (proportion <i>An.gambiae</i> / <i>An.coluzzii</i>) and distance to nearest health facility"
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until clusters were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	NI	
	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N	No baseline demographics were provided in the requested information from the authors. However, restricted randomisation based on baseline variables should account for this.

	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	<p>The protocol states that “Restricted randomisation will be used to allocate the clusters to arms in order to ensure that they are balanced on known factors that may affect the main outcomes. The following factors will be used: baseline (pre-intervention) malaria infection prevalence in children aged 0.5 to 10 years, cluster-level LLIN usage (prior to distribution), socio-economic status, village size, species composition (proportion <i>An.gambiae</i>/<i>An.coluzzii</i>) and distance to nearest health facility”</p> <p>Unclear if the sequence was concealed.</p> <p>No baseline demographics were provided in the requested information from the authors. However, restricted randomisation based on baseline variables should account for this.</p>
Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?	Y	
	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?		
	1b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?	N	No baseline demographics were provided in the requested information from the authors. However, restricted randomisation based on baseline variables should account for this.
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Low
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	Y	All participants had to provide informed consent, or informed consent was provided by parents/caregivers of young children
	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware	N	Authors describe this as a single blinded study, but then state "Study

	of their assigned intervention during the trial?		participants will be blinded to the type of nets they have received. All field staff will be blinded to the allocation and analyses will be conducted on blinded data".
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N	This suggests complete blinding
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	NA	
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	ITT and per protocol analyses were used.
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized ?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	All participants had to provide informed consent, or informed consent was provided by parents/caregivers of young children Authors describe this as a single blinded study, stating "Study participants will be blinded to the type of nets they have received. All field staff will be blinded to the allocation and analyses will be conducted on blinded data".

			ITT and per protocol analyses were used.
Outcome: Malaria Case Incidence			
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	All clusters were included in the analyses.
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	Malaria case incidence was measured in an active cohort of approximately 30 children per cluster followed up for 20 months. These 30 children were chosen randomly.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	Y	Random selection suggests that the result will not be biased
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	<p>All clusters were included in the analyses.</p> <p>Malaria case incidence was measured in an active cohort of approximately 30 children per cluster followed up for 20 months. These 30 children were chosen randomly.</p> <p>Random selection suggests that the result will not be biased</p>

Bias measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Malaria was confirmed if a temperature was recorded and a positive RDT was returned.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	Authors describe this as a single blinded study, but then state "Study participants will be blinded to the type of nets they have received. All field staff will be blinded to the allocation and analyses will be conducted on blinded data". This suggests complete blinding
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Malaria was confirmed if a temperature was recorded and a positive RDT was returned. Authors describe this as a single blinded study, but then state "Study participants will be blinded to the type of nets they have received. All field staff will be blinded to the allocation and analyses will be conducted on blinded data". This suggests complete blinding
	5.1 Were the data that produced this result	Y	The authors have provided a pre-specified analysis plan, and protocol.

	analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?		
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	Not all data available yet.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	Not all data available yet.
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	The authors have provided a pre-specified analysis plan, and protocol. Not all data available yet. Not all data available yet.
Outcome: Parasite Prevalence			
	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	All clusters were included in the analyses.
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	Prevalence was measured in cross-sectional surveys in a random sample of approximately 70 people per cluster, of any age.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	Y	Random selection suggests that the result will not be biased
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	All clusters were included in the analyses. Prevalence was measured in cross-sectional surveys in a random sample of approximately 70 people per cluster, of any age. Random selection suggests that the result will not be biased
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Infection was measured using RDT and people were tested regardless of symptoms.

	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	<p>Authors describe this as a single blinded study, but then state "Study participants will be blinded to the type of nets they have received. All field staff will be blinded to the allocation and analyses will be conducted on blinded data".</p> <p>This suggests complete blinding</p>
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	<p>Infection was measured using RDT and people were tested regardless of symptoms.</p> <p>Authors describe this as a single blinded study, but then state "Study participants will be blinded to the type of nets they have received. All field staff will be blinded to the allocation and analyses will be conducted on blinded data".</p> <p>This suggests complete blinding</p>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was	Y	The authors have provided a pre-specified analysis plan, and protocol.

	finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?		
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	Not all data available yet.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	Not all data available yet.
	Risk of bias judgement	The authors have provided a pre-specified analysis plan, and protocol.	
		Not all data available yet.	
		Not all data available yet.	
Outcome: Prevalence of Anaemia			
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	All clusters were included in the analyses.
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	Prevalence was measured in cross-sectional surveys in a random sample of approximately 70 people per cluster, of any age.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	Y	Random selection suggests that the result will not be biased
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	All clusters were included in the analyses. Prevalence was measured in cross-sectional surveys in a random sample of approximately 70 people per cluster, of any age.

			Random selection suggests that the result will not be biased
Bias measurement in of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Hemoglobin concentration (measured by Haemocue), defined as < 10 g/dL (moderate) and < 8 g/ dL (severe).
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	Authors describe this as a single blinded study, but then state "Study participants will be blinded to the type of nets they have received. All field staff will be blinded to the allocation and analyses will be conducted on blinded data". This suggests complete blinding
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	

			<p>type of nets they have received. All field staff will be blinded to the allocation and analyses will be conducted on blinded data".</p> <p>This suggests complete blinding</p>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	The authors have provided a pre-specified analysis plan, and protocol.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	Not all data available yet.
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	Not all data available yet.
	Risk of bias judgement	<p>The authors have provided a pre-specified analysis plan, and protocol.</p> <p>Not all data available yet.</p> <p>Not all data available yet.</p>	

Study: Effectiveness and cost-effectiveness against malaria of three types of dual-active-ingredient long-lasting insecticidal nets (LLINs) compared with pyrethroid-only LLINs in Tanzania: a four-arm, cluster-randomised trial	
DESIGN	
Lead Author	Jacklin F Mosha
Publication year	2022
Trial name	Not reported
Other reports of this study (i.e., author, year, title, doi)	Mosha 2021 (Protocol)
Time period study was conducted	Selection of villages and households was done during the census between May 11 and July 2, 2018. Enrolment of children for the cohort was done in March, 2019. Between Jan 26 and 28, 2019, LLINs were distributed among households in the study area.
Design	Four parallel-arm, superiority, cluster-randomised, controlled trial
Eligibility criteria of participants	<p>No specific eligibility criteria of participants were mentioned. All individuals in the study area were considered eligible if they provided informed consent (or an adult provided informed consent in the case of children) to receiving and using a LLIN.</p> <p>Inclusion criteria for prevalence and incidence data collection were households with at least one child of appropriate age who permanently resided in the selected household and an adult caregiver who could provide written consent.</p>
Recruitment methods and rate	<p>Five potential study sites in Tanzania's Victoria lake zone were evaluated based on four criteria: report of a minimum of 30% malaria infection prevalence in total population, <i>A. gambiae sensu stricto</i> (s.s.) or <i>A. funestus</i> s.s. as the main vectors, insecticide pyrethroid resistance in standard WHO bioassays (<50% mortality), and no indoor residual spraying (IRS) planned for the next 3 years.</p> <p>Selection of villages and households was done during the census between May 11 and July 2, 2018. Enrolment of children for the cohort was done in March, 2019. The study area included 39 307 households across 72 villages. These households formed 84 clusters, which were evenly distributed between the four groups (21 [25%] clusters- per group). Between Jan 26 and 28, 2019, a total of 147 230 LLINs were distributed among households in the study area. 28 599 core-area households were eligible for cross-sectional surveys of malaria prevalence.</p>
Unit of allocation	<p>Cluster (which consisted of at least 119 household) n = 84</p> <p>A cluster was defined in the protocol as a village or group of hamlets with a minimum of 150 households containing children aged 6 months to 14 years living in the core area; this number was later reduced to 119 households during mapping and census.</p>
Method of Randomization/ matching or other	An independent statistician conducted constrained randomisation to allocate the 84 clusters to the four study groups at a ratio of 1:1:1:1, ensuring that absolute differences in cluster means between study groups were within the specified ranges for specific cluster characteristics.

	<p>Randomisations was verified by checking the frequency of allocations to the same study group of all pairs of clusters.</p> <p>The inhabitants of each cluster and the field staff who were responsible for enrolment and collected data were masked to the type of LLIN allocated. LLINs of each type were similar in appearance apart from a colour-coded loop and a unique identifying code.</p>												
Number of clusters per arm	Clusters were allocated to one of four study groups: the pyrethroid-only (reference) group; the pyriproxyfen group; the chlorfenapyr group; and the piperonyl butoxide group. There were 86 clusters in total and 21 clusters in each arm.												
Adjustment for clustering	<p>The study has adjusted for baseline cluster-level variables used in the randomisation procedure.</p> <p>The within-period intracluster correlation coefficient (ICC) was 0.059, with a between-period ICC of 0.022 and cluster autocorrelation coefficient (CAC) of 0.375.</p>												
Cluster details (including buffer sizes between clusters, other indication of dilution effects)	<p>A mapping census was performed to determine clusters. A cluster was defined in the protocol as a village or group of hamlets with a minimum of 150 households containing children aged 6 months to 14 years living in the core area. Clusters were designed with core and buffer areas, with all houses in core areas located at least 600 m from any houses in adjacent clusters to reduce contamination of intervention.</p> <p>The study area included 39307 households across 72 villages. These households formed 84 clusters, which were evenly distributed between the four groups (21 [25%] clusters per group).</p>												
Number of participants per arm (including number of exclusions and reasons)	<table> <tr> <td>Pyrethroid-only</td> <td>group</td> <td>(61183)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Pyriproxyfen</td> <td>group</td> <td>(57567)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Chlorfenapyr</td> <td>group</td> <td>(60115)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>PBO</td> <td>group</td> <td>(57631)</td> </tr> </table> <p>Numbers lost to follow up varied but remained balanced between groups, and is reported below with the outcome data. Common reasons for loss to follow up include: children not attending clinical appointment, malaria test result missing and death. Lost to follow up was not presented available for the prevalence data.</p>	Pyrethroid-only	group	(61183)	Pyriproxyfen	group	(57567)	Chlorfenapyr	group	(60115)	PBO	group	(57631)
Pyrethroid-only	group	(61183)											
Pyriproxyfen	group	(57567)											
Chlorfenapyr	group	(60115)											
PBO	group	(57631)											
Outcomes assessed	<p>Parasite prevalence (defined in the study as malaria prevalence)</p> <p>Malaria case incidence</p> <p>All-cause mortality</p> <p>Malaria mortality</p> <p>Prevalence of anaemia</p>												
SETTING													
Country	Northwest Tanzania												
Site/s (town/settlements/region)	Misungwi district of Mwanza												
Peak transmission season	<p>The dry season is July to August.</p> <p>High transmission season is October to July.</p> <p>Low transmission season is August to September.</p>												
Baseline malaria endemicity/ level of transmission	Misungwi has moderate to high malaria transmission. In a study conducted in 2010, prevalence was 52% across all age groups. During the preliminary assessment in May 2018, presence of all main												

	<p>Tanzanian malaria vectors, <i>A. gambiae</i> s.s., <i>A. arabiensis</i> and <i>A. funestus</i> s.s., were found in the area.</p> <p><u>Baseline mean household EIR</u> Pyrethroid-only group = 0.35 (0.72), N=331 Pyriproxyfen group = 0.11 (0.34), N=328 Chlorfenapyr group = 0.04 (0.20), N=332 Piperonyl butoxide group = 0.07 (0.26), N=326</p>																																																																																																																								
Study site (e.g., rural/ urban/ peri-urban/ level of urbanicity)	Rural to Urban (mixed)																																																																																																																								
Vector species and vector profile details (i.e., behaviours, resistance profile/ susceptibility tests, parity, sporozoite rates and all other reported information)	94.5% of the species identified were <i>A. funestus</i> . The protocol mentions that <i>A. gambiae</i> s.s., <i>A. arabiensis</i> have also been detected in the area. Pyrethroid resistance was high in <i>A. funestus</i> , with mortality below 85% after exposure to 10 times diagnostic concentrations of a-cypermethrin or permethrin. Exposure to pyriproxyfen sterilised only 127 (24%) of 536 of <i>A. funestus</i> and 23 (21%) of 112 <i>A. gambiae sensu lato</i> . No resistance was observed against chlorfenapyr insecticide																																																																																																																								
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Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants who received the intervention	<p>The numbers of the participants that received the intervention were not provided. However the characteristics of these participants has been provided at a cluster level.</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td colspan="3">PYRETHROID-ONLY STUDY</td> <td colspan="2">GROUP CLUSTERS</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Overall</td> <td>study area:</td> <td>61</td> <td>183</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Core</td> <td>cluster areas:</td> <td>43</td> <td>877</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5">Mean number of people per household in the study area: 7.3 (3.3)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5">HH AND CHILDREN (6 months - 14 years)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Households:</td> <td colspan="2">680</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Children:</td> <td colspan="2">1295</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5">Median age of selected children, years: 6 (3-10), N=1295</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Low socioeconomic status:</td> <td colspan="2">210/680 (30.9%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5">LLIN use in household residents of all age groups: 2957/4962 (59.6%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5">LLIN use in selected children: 831/1295 (64.2%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5">Malaria infection prevalence in selected children: 519/1130 (45.9%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5">Anaemia prevalence in children: 28/453 (6.2%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5">CHILDREN ENROLLED IN COHORT (6 months - 10 years)(March 2019 and February 2020)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Median</td> <td>age, years:</td> <td>5 (3-7),</td> <td colspan="2">N=1523</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Female:</td> <td colspan="2">787/1523 (51.7%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Male:</td> <td colspan="2">736/1523 (48.3%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">LLIN use are enrolment:</td> <td colspan="2">1450/1523 (95.2%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">PYRIPROXYFEN STUDY</td> <td colspan="2">GROUP CLUSTERS</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Overall</td> <td>study area:</td> <td>57</td> <td colspan="2">567</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Core</td> <td>cluster areas:</td> <td>43</td> <td colspan="2">266</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5">Mean number of people per household in the study area: 6.8 (3.0)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5">HH AND CHILDREN (6 months - 14 years)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Households:</td> <td colspan="2">667</td> </tr> </table>	PYRETHROID-ONLY STUDY			GROUP CLUSTERS		Overall	study area:	61	183		Core	cluster areas:	43	877		Mean number of people per household in the study area: 7.3 (3.3)					HH AND CHILDREN (6 months - 14 years)					Households:			680		Children:			1295		Median age of selected children, years: 6 (3-10), N=1295					Low socioeconomic status:			210/680 (30.9%)		LLIN use in household residents of all age groups: 2957/4962 (59.6%)					LLIN use in selected children: 831/1295 (64.2%)					Malaria infection prevalence in selected children: 519/1130 (45.9%)					Anaemia prevalence in children: 28/453 (6.2%)					CHILDREN ENROLLED IN COHORT (6 months - 10 years)(March 2019 and February 2020)					Median	age, years:	5 (3-7),	N=1523		Female:			787/1523 (51.7%)		Male:			736/1523 (48.3%)		LLIN use are enrolment:			1450/1523 (95.2%)		PYRIPROXYFEN STUDY			GROUP CLUSTERS		Overall	study area:	57	567		Core	cluster areas:	43	266		Mean number of people per household in the study area: 6.8 (3.0)					HH AND CHILDREN (6 months - 14 years)					Households:			667	
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Children: 1290
 Median age of selected children, years: 6 (3-10), N=1290
 Low socioeconomic status: 230/667 (34.5%)
 LLIN use in household residents of all age groups: 2813/4520 (62.2%)
 LLIN use in selected children: 839/1290 (65.0%)
 Malaria infection prevalence in selected children: 516/1118 (46.2%)
 Anaemia prevalence in children: 28/500 (5.6%)
 CHILDREN ENROLLED IN COHORT (6 months - 10 years)(March 2019 and February 2020)
 Median age, years: 5 (3-8), N=1523
 Female: 789/1523 (51.8%)
 Male: 734/1523 (48.2%)
 LLIN use are enrolment: 1473/1523 (96.7%)

CHLORFENAPYR STUDY **GROUP CLUSTERS**
 Overall study area: 60 115
 Core cluster areas: 41 748
 Mean number of people per household in the study area: 7.2 (3.1)
 HH AND CHILDREN (6 months - 14 years)
 Households: 671
 Children: 1249
 Median age of selected children, years: 6 (3-9), N=1249
 Low socioeconomic status: 209/671 (31.1%)
 LLIN use in household residents of all age groups: 2849/4803 (59.3%)
 LLIN use in selected children: 781/1249 (62.5%)
 Malaria infection prevalence in selected children: 469/1099 (42.7%)
 Anaemia prevalence in children: 28/507 (5.5%)
 CHILDREN ENROLLED IN COHORT (6 months - 10 years)(March 2019 and February 2020)
 Median age, years: 5 (2-7), N=1495
 Female: 718/1495 (48.0%)
 Male: 777/1495 (52.0%)
 LLIN use are enrolment: 1432/1495 (95.8%)

PBO STUDY **GROUP CLUSTERS**
 Overall study area: 57 631
 Core cluster areas: 45 020
 Mean number of people per household in the study area: 6.9 (2.8)
 HH AND CHILDREN (6 months - 14 years)
 Households: 638
 Children: 1185
 Median age of selected children, years: 6 (3-10), N=1185
 Low socioeconomic status: 237/638 (37.1%)
 LLIN use in household residents of all age groups: 2695/4369 (61.7%)
 LLIN use in selected children: 751/1185 (63.4%)
 Malaria infection prevalence in selected children: 444/1056 (42.0%)
 Anaemia prevalence in children: 20/472 (4.2%)
 CHILDREN ENROLLED IN COHORT (6 months - 10 years)(March 2019 and February 2020)

	<p>Median age, years: 5 (3-8), N=1527 Female: 825/1527 (54.0%) Male: 702/1527 (46.0%) LLIN use are enrolment: 1467/1527 (96.1%)</p>
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants on whom the impact was measured.	<p>Criteria for prevalence and incidence data collection were households with at least one child of appropriate age who permanently resided in the selected household and an adult caregiver who could provide written consent. For Prevalence data, children were eligible if aged between 6 months and 14 years. For incidence data, children were eligible if aged between 6 months and 10 years. Houses allocated to cluster buffer areas received the same LLINs as those distributed in the core area, but outcome monitoring was done only in households in the core areas.</p> <p>FOR MALARIA CASE INCIDENCE *note, not all children were eligible for outcome assessment)</p> <p>Pyrethroid-only group: Year 1 (743); Year 2 (842) Pyriproxyfen group: Year 1 (748); Year 2 (844) Chlorfenapyr group: Year 1 (742); Year 2 (845) Piperonyl butoxide group: Year 1 (749); Year 2 (840)</p> <p>Children 6 months to 10 years (cohort children 2019-2020) Sex, Female Pyrethroid-only group: 787/1523 (51.7%) Pyriproxyfen group: 789/1523 (51.8%) Chlorfenapyr group: 718/1495 (48.0%) Piperonyl butoxide group: 825/1527 (54.0%)</p> <p>FOR SURVEYS FOR PREVALENCE OUTCOMES *note not all children were eligible for outcome assessment)</p> <p>Pyrethroid-only group: 12 months (1123); 18 months (1127); 24 months (1199) Pyriproxyfen group: 12 months (1069); 18 months (1153); 24 months (1258) Chlorfenapyr group: 12 months (1126); 18 months (1246); 24 months (1272) Piperonyl butoxide group: 12 months (1071); 18 months (1160); 24 months (1259)</p> <p>Children 6 months to 14 years (2018) Median age of selected children, years Pyrethroid-only group: 6 (3–10), N=1295 Pyriproxyfen group: 6 (3–10), N=1290 Chlorfenapyr group: 6 (3–9), N=1249 Piperonyl butoxide group: 6 (3–10), N=1185</p> <p>Low socioeconomic status Pyrethroid-only group: 210/680 (30.9%) Pyriproxyfen group: 230/667 (34.5%) Chlorfenapyr group: 209/671 (31.1%)</p>

	Piperonyl butoxide group: 237/638 (37.1%)
Frequency of travel in the last month	They said "A questionnaire was administered to enquire about LLIN use the night before the visit, adverse events, travel history, and visit to health facilities within the past 2 weeks", but gave no data.
INTERVENTION 1	
Dual AI net brand, insecticide type, dose, material of net (including active ingredient, timing and frequency of application, durability of the net and insecticide)	Pyriproxyfen combined with alpha-cypermethrin, Royal Guard
Net treatment strategy (e.g., how were the nets treated with the insecticide(s))	LLINs were treated with a combination of pyriproxyfen (5.5 g/kg) and a-cypermethrin (5.5 g/kg; Royal Guard, Disease Control Technologies, Greer, SC, USA).
Deployment strategy of nets (e.g., who received the nets? Where the houses in which they were installed permanent? What was the frequency of distribution?)	All households enumerated in the core and buffer areas of clusters were allocated at least one LLIN for every two people
How was the intervention measured? (e.g. how was net usage monitored/observed by the authors? How was coverage of nets measured?)	A survey was done in eight randomly selected houses in each cluster 3 months after distribution to assess LLIN coverage. At 24 months a second survey was conducted that also tested the nets for active ingredient retention.
Coverage of household / person (% of households with at least 1 ITN % of households with at least 1 ITN for every 2 people % of population with access to an ITN Nets per HH or per person)	Coverage decreased from 62.2% (2813/4520) at baseline to 38.3% (2087/5455) after 2 years.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	Not reported specifically. Authors mention that all households were targeted and provide the total number of LLINs distributed (147230) but this was not broken down into groups.
Length of intervention and time points of outcome measurement	LLINs were distributed once, between Jan 26th and Jan 28th 2019. Outcomes were recorded over three years (described below).
Changes in human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, non-intervention-based spraying of houses)	Behaviour change communication activities were done during and after the net distribution to increase LLIN use
Background interventions (all reported in primary study – e.g., spraying prior to treatment period (and during) including coverage of background interventions. Other malaria or vector-specific control interventions [indoor surface treatment, nets/ other insecticides/ barrier], cointerventions, treatment of individuals that may impact outcome)	Previous vector control interventions in the region included indoor residual spraying and a universal LLIN coverage campaign in 2015, as well as distribution of LLINs to primary school students in 2018 and to pregnant women during antenatal care visits
INTERVENTION 2	
Dual AI net brand, insecticide type, dose, material of net (including active ingredient, timing and frequency of application, durability of the net and insecticide)	Chlorfenapyr combined with alpha-cypermethrin, Interceptor G2
Net treatment strategy	LLINs were treated with a wash-resistant formulation of 200 mg/

(e.g., how were the nets treated with the insecticide(s))	m2 chlorfenapyr and 100 mg/m2 alpha-cypermethrin
Deployment strategy of nets (e.g., who received the nets? Where the houses in which they were installed permanent? What was the frequency of distribution?)	All households enumerated in the core and buffer areas of clusters were allocated at least one LLIN for every two people.
How was the intervention measured? (e.g. how was net usage monitored/observed by the authors? How was coverage of nets measured?)	A survey was done in eight randomly selected houses in each cluster 3 months after distribution to assess LLIN coverage. At 24 months a second survey was conducted that also tested the nets for active ingredient retention.
Coverage of household / person (% of households with at least 1 ITN % of households with at least 1 ITN for every 2 people % of population with access to an ITN Nets per HH or per person)	At least one LLIN was distributed for every two people. 3 months after LLIN distribution, 3155 (72.1%) of 4378 of study participants surveyed reported using the assigned study LLINs the previous night; this proportion was similar between study groups. Coverage decreased from 59.3% (2849/4803) at baseline to 46.4% (2585/5576) after 2 years
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	Not reported specifically. Authors mention that all households were targeted and provide the total number of LLINs distributed (147230) but this was not broken down into groups.
Length of intervention and time points of outcome measurement	LLINs were distributed once, between Jan 26th and Jan 28th 2019. Outcomes were recorded over three years (described below) and assessed at 12, 18 and 24 months.
Changes in human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, non-intervention-based spraying of houses)	Behaviour change communication activities were done during and after the net distribution to increase LLIN use
Background interventions (all reported in primary study – e.g., spraying prior to treatment period (and during) including coverage of background interventions. Other malaria or vector-specific control interventions [indoor surface treatment, nets/ other insecticides/ barrier], cointerventions, treatment of individuals that may impact outcome)	Previous vector control interventions in the region included indoor residual spraying and a universal LLIN coverage campaign in 2015, as well as distribution of LLINs to primary school students in 2018 and to pregnant women during antenatal care visits
COMPARISON	
Dual AI net brand, insecticide type, dose, material of net (including active ingredient, timing and frequency of application, durability of the net and insecticide)	There were two comparison groups used in this study. The first was a pyrethroid-only (reference) group, which received LLINs containing the pyrethroid a-cypermethrin (5 g/kg; Interceptor, BASF SE, Ludwigshafen Germany – INTERCEPTOR LN). The second was a piperonyl butoxide group, with LLINs combining piperonyl butoxide (10 g/kg) and the pyrethroid permethrin (20 g/kg; Olyset Plus, Sumitomo Chemical, Tokyo, Japan).
Net treatment strategy (e.g., how were the nets treated with the insecticide(s))	As above.
Deployment strategy of nets (e.g., who received the nets? Where the houses in which they were installed permanent? What was the frequency of distribution?)	All households enumerated in the core and buffer areas of clusters were allocated at least one LLIN for every two people.

How was the intervention measured? (e.g. how was net usage monitored/observed by the authors? How was coverage of nets measured?)	A survey was done in eight randomly selected houses in each cluster 3 months after distribution to assess LLIN coverage. At 24 months a second survey was conducted that also tested the nets for active ingredient retention.																																																
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Any other details regarding comparator not described elsewhere.	Previous vector control interventions in the region included indoor residual spraying and a universal LLIN coverage campaign in 2015, as well as distribution of LLINs to primary school students in 2018 and to pregnant women during antenatal care visits																																																
MALARIA CASE INCIDENCE RATE Defined as symptoms plus parasitaemia, over a population at risk or person-time. Detected either through passive or active surveillance.																																																	
Name	Malaria case incidence																																																
Definition/ assessment metric	To assess malaria case incidence, 35 households per cluster were enrolled after LLIN distribution in year 1. From each household, one child aged 6 months to 10 years was selected at random and actively followed up for 1 year. A second independent cohort of 40 children per cluster (number increased because of the low incidence in the first year) was recruited 1 year after distribution. Malaria was assessed with a RDT.																																																
Events	Presented as number of clinical episodes over child-years <table border="0"> <tr> <td colspan="5">PYRETHROID-ONLY</td> <td>GROUP</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Year</td> <td>1:</td> <td>194/605.1</td> <td>(0.32</td> <td>per</td> <td>year)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Year</td> <td>2:</td> <td>449/793.4</td> <td>(0.57</td> <td>per</td> <td>year)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Overall:</td> <td></td> <td>643/1398.5</td> <td>(0.46</td> <td>per</td> <td>year)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="5">PYRIPROXYFEN</td> <td>GROUP</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Year</td> <td>1:</td> <td>161/604.5</td> <td>(0.27</td> <td>per</td> <td>year)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Year</td> <td>2:</td> <td>418/787.4</td> <td>(0.53</td> <td>per</td> <td>year)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Overall:</td> <td></td> <td>579/1391.9</td> <td>(0.42</td> <td>per</td> <td>year)</td> </tr> </table>	PYRETHROID-ONLY					GROUP	Year	1:	194/605.1	(0.32	per	year)	Year	2:	449/793.4	(0.57	per	year)	Overall:		643/1398.5	(0.46	per	year)	PYRIPROXYFEN					GROUP	Year	1:	161/604.5	(0.27	per	year)	Year	2:	418/787.4	(0.53	per	year)	Overall:		579/1391.9	(0.42	per	year)
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Year	1:	161/604.5	(0.27	per	year)																																												
Year	2:	418/787.4	(0.53	per	year)																																												
Overall:		579/1391.9	(0.42	per	year)																																												

	CHLORENAPYR	GROUP
Year	1: 79/603.8 (0.13 per year)	
Year	2: 248/790.6 (0.31 per year)	
Overall:	317/1394.4 (0.23 per year)	
	PBO	GROUP
Year	1: 79/591.8 (0.13 per year)	
Year	2: 381/788.9 (0.48 per year)	
Overall:	460/1380.7 (0.33 per year)	
Total (or unit time)	Reported above	
Time of outcome assessment	Reported above	
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	Malaria clinical case incidence over 24 months of follow-up (1380.7 to 1398.5 child-years per group) was 0.46 per child-year in the pyrethroid-only reference group, 0.42 per child-year in the pyriproxyfen group (IRR 0.99 [95% CI 0.66-1.50], p=0.9801), 0.23 per child-year in the chlorfenapyr group (0.56 [0.37-0.86], p=0.0072), and 0.33 per child-year in the piperonyl butoxide group (0.92 [0.61-1.38], p=0.6809)	
Effect type	IRR	
MALARIA INFECTION INCIDENCE		
Defined as parasitaemia with or without symptoms, over a population at risk of person-time. Detected through passive or active surveillance.		
Name	N/A	
Definition/ assessment metric	N/A	
Events	N/A	
Total (or unit time)	N/A	
Time of outcome assessment	N/A	
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	N/A	
Effect type	N/A	
INCIDENCE OF SEVERE DISEASE		
Defined as hospitalization with parasitaemia, over a population at risk or person-time.		
Name	N/A	
Definition/ assessment metric	N/A	
Events	N/A	
Total (or unit time)	N/A	
Time of outcome assessment	N/A	
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	N/A	
Effect type	N/A	
PARASITE PREVALENCE		
Parasitaemia with or without symptoms, over the population sampled. Detected through cross-sectional surveys.		
Name	Parasite prevalence (defined in the study as malaria prevalence)	
Definition/ assessment metric	Prevalence of malaria infection diagnosed with a positive rapid diagnostic test in children aged 6 months to 14 years. This was measured at 12, 18 and 24 months post intervention through a cross-	

	sectional survey. In each household, up to two children aged 6 months to 14 years were randomly selected for detection of malaria parasitaemia.		
Events	PYRETHROID-ONLY		GROUP
	12	months:	350/1123
	18	months:	642/1227
	24	months:	549/119
	PYRIPROXYFEN		GROUP
	12	months:	232/1069
	18	months:	583/1069
	24	months:	472/1258
	CHLORENAPYR		GROUP
	12	months:	176/1126
	18	months:	509/1246
	24	months:	326/1272
	PBO		GROUP
	12	months:	206/1071
	18	months:	502/1160
		24 months: 512/1259	
Total (or unit time)	Reported above		
Time of outcome assessment	Reported above		
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	12		months
	statistically significant reduction was observed only in the chlorfenapyr group and not in the pyriproxyfen or piperonyl butoxide groups		
	18		months
	no group showed a significant reduction relative to the pyrethroid-only group at 18 months		
	24		months
No statistically significant reduction in the prevalence of malaria infection was observed in the pyriproxyfen group (472 [37.5%] of 1258 children; aOR 0.79 [95% CI 0.54-1.17], p=0.2354) or the piperonyl butoxide group (512 [40.7%] of 1259; 0.99 [0.67-1.45], p=0.9607) relative to the pyrethroid-only reference group (549 [45.8%] of 1199); however, prevalence was significantly lower in the chlorfenapyr group (326 [25.6%] of 1272; 0.45 [0.30-0.67], p=0.0001) than in the pyrethroid-only group.			
Effect type	OR or RR		
ALL-CAUSE MORTALITY			
Number of deaths over the population at risk or person-time.			
Name	All cause mortality		
Definition/ assessment metric	Number of deaths over the population at risk or person-time		
Events	PYRETHROID-ONLY		GROUP
	Year	1:	0/743
	Year	2:	2/842
	PYRIPROXYFEN		GROUP

	Year	1:	0/748
	Year	2:	2/844
	CHLORENAPYR		GROUP
	Year	1:	1/742
	Year	2:	0/845
	PBO		GROUP
	Year	1:	0/749
	Year 2:		0/840
Total (or unit time)	Reported above		
Time of outcome assessment	Reported above		
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	Five deaths among cohort children were reported. While these deaths have been reported per group and year, the reasons have not been separated by group or year. As reported by the authors three deaths were from drowning, one was due to severe malaria, and one due to pneumonia, all of which were judged to be unrelated to the study interventions.		
Effect type	RR or OR		
MALARIA MORTALITY			
Number of deaths attributed to malaria over the population at risk or person-time.			
Name	Malaria mortality		
Definition/ assessment metric	Number of deaths attributed to malaria over the population at risk or person-time.		
Events	Reported below		
Total (or unit time)	Reported below		
Time of outcome assessment	Reported below		
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	There was only 1 death attributed to malaria throughout the entire study. However, this death has not been categorized to treatment group, or year.		
Effect type	Not synthesizable		
PREVALENCE OF ANAEMIA			
Defined by study thresholds of anaemia.			
Name	Prevalence of anaemia		
Definition/ assessment metric	Moderate or severe anaemia was defined as haemoglobin concentration <8 g/dL. This was measured in children 6 months to 4 years measured at 12, 18, and 24 months during the cross-sectional surveys. In each household, up to two children aged 6 months to 14 years were randomly selected for anaemia assessment.		
Events	PYRETHROID-ONLY		GROUP
	12	months:	7/1123
	18	months:	45/1227
	24	months:	29/119
	PYRIPROXYFEN		GROUP
	12	months:	8/1069
	18	months:	37/1069
	24	months:	38/1258
	CHLORENAPYR		GROUP

	12	months:	11/1126
	18	months:	33/1246
	24	months:	28/1272
	PBO		GROUP
	12	months:	10/1071
	18	months:	23/1160
	24 months: 26/1259		
Total (or unit time)	Reported above		
Time of outcome assessment	Reported above		
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	No significant difference in moderate and severe anaemia was observed in any of the intervention groups at any time point		
Effect type	RR or OR		
COSTS			
Event/raw costs	<u>Costs- constant USD</u> Standard 2-yearly Cases: 4,785 DALYs: 412 Societal - 50,329 Household - 22,486 Public provider - 28,040 Donor - 24,281 PBO 2-yearly Cases: 4,378 DALYs: 375 Societal - 53,007 Household - 20,569 Public provider - 32,856 Donor - 29,333 Pyriproxyfen 2-yearly Cases: 4,886 DALYs: 422 Societal - 60,410 Household - 22,808 Public provider - 37,661 Donor - 33,810 Chlorfenapyr 2-yearly Cases: 3,026 DALYs: 260 Societal - 45,016 Household - 14,087 Public provider - 30,934 Donor - 28,585		
Results	Chlorfenapyr LLINs were estimated to avert the most DALYs (mean 152 DALYs averted [SD 72] per 10 000 total population), followed by piperonyl butoxide LLINs (37 DALYs averted [72] per 10 000		

	<p>population), while pyriproxyfen LLINs incurred 9 more DALYs [71] per 10 000 population than did pyrethroid-only LLINs.</p> <p>From public provider and donor perspectives, chlorfenapyr LLINs would be the most cost-effective of the three dual-active-ingredient LLINs, costing an additional \$19 (95% uncertainty interval 1-105) to public providers or \$28 (11-120) to donors per DALY averted relative to pyrethroid-only LLINs-well below plausible costeffectiveness thresholds (\$292-393 per DALY averted)</p>
Time of cost assessment	Cost effectiveness was modelled over the 2-year trial. Malaria incidence estimates for each trial year were combined with probabilities of progression to severe disease and death on the basis of secondary sources
Resources needed/ used	Nets and active ingredients
ADDITIONAL DATA	
Unintended benefits	Not reported
Harms	<p>Side-effect related to use of standard pyrethroid-only LLINs were reported in 90 (44.1%) of 204 participants at 3 months post-distribution, 167 (10.1%) of 1647 at 12 months, two (0.1%) of 1579 at 18 months, and 11 (0.7%) of 1683 at 24 months.</p> <p>Pyriproxyfen LLINs side-effects were reported in 80 (38.8%) of 206 participants at 3 months, 143 (9.3%) of 1543 at 12 months, none of 1425 at 18 months, and seven (0.4%) of 1692 at 24 months.</p> <p>Piperonyl butoxide group (17 [8.5%] of 199) at 3 months</p> <p>Chlorfenapyr group (17 [8.5%] of 199) at 3 months</p> <p>Skin irritation or paraesthesia was the most commonly reported side-effect in all groups, reported in 497 (83.1%) of 598 participants who reported side-effects. No serious or severe side effects were reported.</p>
Other contextual information present/measured/reported (feasibility, acceptability, preferences/values, impact on equity)	The proportion of study LLINs that were torn (defined as hole area $\geq 790 \text{ cm}^2$) ²³ was 86 (28%) of 303 in the pyrethroid-only group, 109 (39%) of 282 in the pyriproxyfen group, 96 (34%) of 284 in the chlorfenapyr group, and 81 (43%) of 188 in the piperonyl butoxide group. Chemical analysis on 30 nets per group showed that the active ingredient concentration in each type of LLIN met the specification criteria when new. At 24 months, partner active ingredient retention was 28% for pyriproxyfen, 18% for chlorfenapyr, and 30% for piperonyl butoxide.
Entomological outcomes measured (list)	Entomological inoculation rate Vector density Sporozoite rate Insecticide resistance
Other	Not reported.
Source of funding	The trial was funded by UK Research and Innovation Joint Global Health Trials programme (reference number MR/R006040/1).
Possible conflicts of interest	The authors declared no conflicts of interest. The funders of the study had no role in study design, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, or writing of the report.

Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	An independent statistician conducted constrained randomisation to allocate the 84 clusters to the four study groups at a ratio of 1:1:1:1, ensuring that absolute differences in cluster means between study groups were within the specified ranges for specific cluster characteristics.
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until clusters were enrolled and assigned to interventions?	Y	Randomisations was verified by checking the frequency of allocations to the same study group of all pairs of clusters. The inhabitants of each cluster and the field staff who were responsible for enrolment and collected data were masked to the type of LLIN allocated. LLINs of each type were similar in appearance apart from a colour-coded loop and a unique identifying code.
	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N	No differences detected
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	An independent statistician conducted constrained randomisation to allocate the 84 clusters to the four study groups at a ratio of 1:1:1:1, ensuring that absolute differences in cluster means between study groups were within the specified ranges for specific cluster characteristics. Randomisations was verified by checking the frequency of allocations to the same study group of all pairs of clusters. The inhabitants of each cluster and the field staff who were responsible for enrolment and collected data were masked to the type of LLIN allocated. LLINs of each type were similar in appearance apart from a colour-coded

			loop and a unique identifying code. No differences detected
Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?	Y	Participants belonged to households which were then segmented into clusters based on a mapping census
	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?	NA	
	1b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?		N
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Participants belonged to households which were then segmented into clusters based on a mapping census
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	Y	Informed consent was given by all participants
	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	The inhabitants of each cluster and the field staff who were responsible for enrolment and collected data were masked to the type of LLIN allocated. LLINs of each type were similar in appearance apart from a colour-coded loop and a unique identifying code.
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N	
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	NA	
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	ITT was used throughout the study
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a	NA	

	substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized ?		
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	<p>Informed consent was given by all participants</p> <p>The inhabitants of each cluster and the field staff who were responsible for enrolment and collected data were masked to the type of LLIN allocated. LLINs of each type were similar in appearance apart from a colour-coded loop and a unique identifying code.</p> <p>ITT was used throughout the study</p>

Outcome: Malaria Case Incidence

Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	To assess malaria case incidence, 35 households per cluster were enrolled after LLIN distribution in year 1. From each household, one child aged 6 months to 10 years was selected at random and actively followed up for 1 year. A second independent cohort of 40 children per cluster (number increased because of the low incidence in the first year) was recruited 1 year after distribution.
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	N	No evidence that the results was not biased
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	N	Children were randomly selected, so it is unlikely that missingness in the outcome may depend on its true value.
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	To assess malaria case incidence, 35 households per cluster were enrolled after LLIN distribution in year 1. From each household, one child aged 6 months to 10 years was selected at random and actively followed up for 1

			<p>year. A second independent cohort of 40 children per cluster (number increased because of the low incidence in the first year) was recruited 1 year after distribution.</p> <p>No evidence that the results was not biased</p> <p>Children were randomly selected, so it is unlikely that missingness in the outcome may depend on its true value</p>
Bias measurement in of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Prevalence of malaria infection diagnosed with a positive rapid diagnostic test
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The inhabitants of each cluster and the field staff who were responsible for enrolment and collected data were masked to the type of LLIN allocated. LLINs of each type were similar in appearance apart from a colour-coded loop and a unique identifying code.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Prevalence of malaria infection diagnosed with a positive rapid diagnostic test
		The inhabitants of each cluster and the field staff who were responsible for enrolment and collected data were masked to the type of LLIN allocated. LLINs of each type were	

			similar in appearance apart from a colour-coded loop and a unique identifying code.
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	Protocol provided and the results present align. Some outcomes have not been fully reported, but that is because the trial is ongoing for outcomes longer than 2 years post intervention.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	Yes, but does not impact bias, as all time points were reported in full
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Protocol provided and the results present align. Some outcomes have not been fully reported, but that is because the trial is ongoing for outcomes longer than 2 years post intervention.
Outcome: Parasite Prevalence			
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	Prevalence of malaria infection diagnosed with a positive rapid diagnostic test in children aged 6 months to 14 years. In each household, up to two children aged 6 months to 14 years were randomly selected for detection of malaria parasitaemia.
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	N	No evidence that the results was not biased
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	N	Children were randomly selected, so it us unlikely that missingness in the outcome may depend on its true value
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Prevalence of malaria infection diagnosed with a positive rapid diagnostic test in children aged 6

			<p>months to 14 years. In each household, up to two children aged 6 months to 14 years were randomly selected for detection of malaria parasitaemia.</p> <p>No evidence that the results was not biased</p> <p>Children were randomly selected, so it is unlikely that missingness in the outcome may depend on its true value</p>
<p>Bias measurement in of the outcome</p>	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Prevalence of malaria infection diagnosed with a positive rapid diagnostic test
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The inhabitants of each cluster and the field staff who were responsible for enrolment and collected data were masked to the type of LLIN allocated. LLINs of each type were similar in appearance apart from a colour-coded loop and a unique identifying code.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	<p>Prevalence of malaria infection diagnosed with a positive rapid diagnostic test</p> <p>The inhabitants of each cluster and the field staff who were responsible for enrolment and collected data were masked to the type of LLIN allocated. LLINs of each type were</p>

			similar in appearance apart from a colour-coded loop and a unique identifying code.
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	Protocol provided and the results present align. Some outcomes have not been fully reported, but that is because the trial is ongoing for outcomes longer than 2 years post intervention.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	Yes, but does not impact bias, as all time points were reported in full
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Protocol provided and the results present align. Some outcomes have not been fully reported, but that is because the trial is ongoing for outcomes longer than 2 years post intervention. But does not impact bias, as all time points were reported in full
Outcome: Prevalence of Anaemia			
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	Moderate or severe anaemia was defined as haemoglobin concentration <8 g/dL. This was measured in children 6 months to 4 years measured at 12, 18, and 24 months during the cross-sectional surveys. In each household, up to two children aged 6 months to 14 years were randomly selected for anaemia assessment.
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	N	No evidence that the results was not biased
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	N	Children were randomly selected, so it is unlikely that missingness in the

	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	outcome may depend on its true value
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	<p>Moderate or severe anaemia was defined as haemoglobin concentration <8 g/dL. This was measured in children 6 months to 4 years measured at 12, 18, and 24 months during the cross-sectional surveys. In each household, up to two children aged 6 months to 14 years were randomly selected for anaemia assessment.</p> <p>No evidence that the results was not biased</p> <p>Children were randomly selected, so it is unlikely that missingness in the outcome may depend on its true value</p>
Bias measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Moderate or severe anaemia was defined as haemoglobin concentration <8 g/dL. This was measured in children 6 months to 4 years measured at 12, 18, and 24 months during the cross-sectional surveys. In each household, up to two children aged 6 months to 14 years were randomly selected for anaemia assessment.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	The inhabitants of each cluster and the field staff who were responsible for enrolment and collected data were masked to the type of LLIN allocated. LLINs of each type were similar in appearance apart from a colour-coded loop and a unique identifying code.
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome	NA	

	have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	<p>Moderate or severe anaemia was defined as haemoglobin concentration <8 g/dL. This was measured in children 6 months to 4 years measured at 12, 18, and 24 months during the cross-sectional surveys. In each household, up to two children aged 6 months to 14 years were randomly selected for anaemia assessment.</p> <p>The inhabitants of each cluster and the field staff who were responsible for enrolment and collected data were masked to the type of LLIN allocated. LLINs of each type were similar in appearance apart from a colour-coded loop and a unique identifying code.</p>
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	<p>Protocol provided and the results present align.</p> <p>Some outcomes have not been fully reported, but that is because the trial is ongoing for outcomes longer than 2 years post intervention.</p>
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	Yes, but does not impact bias, as all time points were reported in full
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	<p>Protocol provided and the results present align.</p> <p>Some outcomes have not been fully reported, but that is because the trial is ongoing for outcomes longer than 2 years post intervention.</p>

		But does not impact bias, as all time points were reported in full
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Tiono 2018

Study:	
DESIGN	
Lead Author	Alfred B Tiono
Publication year	2018
Trial name	AvecNet Trial
Other reports of this study (i.e., author, year, title, doi)	Sagnon 2015 (Trial Protocol 1) Tiono 2015 (Trail Protocol 2) Tiono 2016 (Conference Presentation) Tiono 2018b (Supplementary Material to Manuscript)
Time period study was conducted	Protocol 1: 2014 to 2017. Protocol 2: May 2014 to May 2015.
Design	Two-group, step wedge, cluster-randomised, controlled, superiority trial
Eligibility criteria of participants	Protocol 2: Children resident in Burkina Faso, aged 6 months to 5 years old. Eligibility criteria: Resident children, aged 6 months to 5 years old will be enumerated and an average of 50 per cluster (range 30-100, depending on village size) will be selected randomly, stratified by age and invited to participate in the clinical surveys and passive case detection (PCD). No distinctions will be made regarding gender, ethnic group, medical condition or physical health. -Gender:Both -Target number of participants: 2000 -Participant exclusion criteria: Those who have not provided their consent for inclusion in the study
Recruitment methods and rate	Protocol 1: The study villages will be enumerated following normal demographic surveillance procedures and compounds mapped before being randomised to net type. Protocol 2: Recruitment start date: 01/05/2014 Recruitment end date: 01/05/2015
Unit of allocation	Cluster (consisting of one to four neighbouring villages, aka compound)
Method of Randomization/ matching or other	Random selection was done with Stata version 10. five randomly selected clusters of villages were provided with PPF-treated LLINs and the remaining 35 village clusters with standard LLINs
Number of clusters per arm	This was stepped wedged trial. In the first month, only 5 clusters were randomly selected to receive the PPF-LLINs. Then five clusters were randomly selected each month from July, 2014, to September, 2014, for replacement of standard LLINs with PPF-treated LLINs, so that, by the end of 2014, each study group had an equal number of clusters. By September of 2015, every cluster had received the PPF-LLIN. Step-wedge design was utilized because it represented the type of deployment used by net distribution programmes.
Adjustment for clustering	Poisson regression models were used, with log-transformed time at risk as an offset, and with inclusion of village cluster as a random effect and calendar month and health facility as fixed effects. Protocol 2: Adjusting for a coefficient of up to 0.5 for the differences

	<p>in cluster size. Within each model, effect size (that is, difference between PPF-LLIN and LLIN clusters) will, as appropriate, be adjusted for clustering within the groups of villages, the shortest distance between each PPF-LLIN cluster of villages and its nearest control, village-cluster size, and village-cluster.</p>
<p>Cluster details (including buffer sizes between clusters, other indication of dilution effects)</p>	<p>Number of clusters: 40 Number of villages: 91 Number of households: 6062</p> <p>Protocol 2: i) LLINs are a community-level intervention; and ii) the village cluster is a suitable unit for randomization since they represent a discrete spatial cluster.</p> <p>It is important that within the study area there are no villages that are not enrolled in the study in order for the PPF-LLIN to have maximum impact on larval populations and minimize the spill-over of mosquitoes from villages without these nets.</p> <p>The main endpoint analysis will adjust for distance between village clusters with different types of nets. This adjustment is critical since the impact of PPF-LLIN is likely to increase as they cover larger areas and so reduce the spill over of mosquitoes from villages with LLINs.</p>
<p>Number of participants per arm (including number of exclusions and reasons)</p>	<p>At baseline 1980 children were enrolled into 40 clusters. However, by the fourth survey at the end of study, the cohort comprised 2148 children. A mean of 46–56 additional children per cluster were included in surveys two to four.</p> <p>Protocol 2: A minimum of 40 children per cluster (range 40 to 75), depending on cluster size, will be randomly selected, stratified by age and invited to participate in the clinical and travel/residence surveys and passive case detection (PCD).</p>
<p>Outcomes assessed</p>	<p>Malaria case incidence rate Parasite prevalence All-cause mortality Prevalence of anaemia</p>
<p>SETTING</p>	
<p>Country</p>	<p>Burkina Faso</p>
<p>Site/s (town/settlements/region)</p>	<p>Protocol 1: The study will be carried out in two villages in the Cascades Region of Burkina Faso. Dalamba (village A) Sanako (village B)</p> <p>Protocol 2: The study site is situated south of the road from Banfora and Sideradougou (10° 56' 00" N, 004° 46' 00" W) and is approximately 1,250 km², bisected by a river in a north- south axis.</p>
<p>Peak transmission season</p>	<p>Rainy season from May to October with little rain in other months. This defines the seasonal malaria transmission with most malaria episodes experienced during or immediately following the rainy season.</p>
<p>Baseline malaria endemicity/ level of transmission</p>	<p>South-east of Banfora town in Burkina Faso, a country where malaria is relatively stable but highly endemic. Malaria prevalence dropped by half and the incidence of clinical disease fell by 40% from 2000-15. Burkina Faso, with more than 10</p>

	million uncomplicated cases of malaria annually, is one of 20 sub-Saharan countries where malaria cases increased between 2015 and 2016. 61% of children aged six months to five years infected in 2014.
Study site (e.g., rural/ urban/ peri-urban/ level of urbanicity)	Urbanicity was not specifically reported. However, the authors stated that most people were living in small rural villages in houses made with mud or cement walls and thatched or metal roofs.
Vector species and vector profile details (i.e., behaviours, resistance profile/ susceptibility tests, parity, sporozoite rates and all other reported information)	<p><i>A gambiae</i> sensu stricto and <i>Anopheles coluzzii</i> were the two most common vectors between groups.</p> <p>The authors discuss in the introduction that these vectors are highly resistant but have not conducted any resistance testing themselves in this paper.</p> <p>They have presented the following information regarding parity and sporozoite proportions, by each group:</p> <p>PROPORTION OF PAROUS MOSQUITOES Standard LLIN = 60% (625/1038) PPF LLIN = 62% (1364/2198)</p> <p>PROPORTION OF MOSQUITOES WITH SPOROZOITES Standard LLIN = 4% (206/4858) PPF LLIN = 3% (273/8935)</p>
Malaria species	<i>P falciparum</i>
PARTICIPANTS (those who received the intervention and on whom impact was measured)	
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants who received the intervention	<p>1980 total children were enrolled in the study. Data are n (%), median (IQR) or n/N (%)</p> <p>Girls = 962 (49%) Boys = 1018 (51%) Age (months) = 35 (22-48) Sleeps under a mosquito net = 1828 (92%) Received antimalarials in past 14 days = 143 (7%) Sick with a fever during past 48h = 250 (13%) Axillary temp degC = 36.6 (36.3-36.0) Positive RDT = 226/321 (70%) Presence of <i>P. falciparum</i> parasites by microscopy = 981/1918 (51%) >5000 <i>P falciparum</i> parasites per uL = 271/1918 (14%) <i>P falciparum</i> parasite density (per UL) = 1698 (6.1) <small>(Geometric mean and SD)</small> Presence of <i>P falciparum</i> gametocytes = 380/1918 (20%) Haemoglobin (g/L) = 102.0 (94.0-1110.0) Moderate anaemia = 131/1800 (7%) Severe anaemia = 2/1800 (0%)</p>
Characteristics, numbers, and demographics of participants on whom the impact was measured.	<p>Only available for replacement children enrolled into study at third survey (totals below).</p> <p>Female, N (%) 342/675 (51%) Age (months), median (IQR): 29 (20,42) Sleeps under a mosquito net, N (%): 669/675 (99%) Took anti-malarials in last 14 days, N (%): 5/675 (1%) Sick with a fever during previous 48 hours N (%): 29/675 (4%) Positive rapid diagnostic test, N (%): 24/37 (65%)</p>

	Supplementary Material: At the first survey, 1,980 children were enrolled in the cohort, with 675 children added at the third survey to replace those lost or exited. By the fourth survey at the end of study, there were 2,148 children in the cohort. An average of 46-56 additional children per cluster were included in surveys two to four.
Frequency of travel in the last month	Protocol 2: History of travel away from the village for periods of over a week will be captured by the monthly surveys and time at risk will be censored for such periods. In addition, malaria cases in children who resided outside their study village for more than half the elapsed study period at the time of illness will be censored. However this was not reported.
INTERVENTION (Repeat if multiple arms)	
Dual AI net brand, insecticide type, dose, material of net (including active ingredient, timing and frequency of application, durability of the net and insecticide)	PPF-LLIN The nets contain 2% w/w permethrin and 1% w/w pyriproxyfen incorporated into polyethylene fibres giving adequate release of permethrin and pyriproxyfen for an estimated 3 years (Sumitomo Chemical) The PPF-LLINs were distributed according to the step-wedged design detailed above. The nets were white and sized at 1.8m wide by 1.9m long by 15m high
Net treatment strategy (e.g., how were the nets treated with the insecticide(s))	Chemical content of 30 randomly selected LLINs and 30 PPF-treated LLINs was checked with high-performance liquid chromatography at the Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine (Liverpool, UK), which confirmed the target doses.
Deployment strategy of nets (e.g., who received the nets? Where the houses in which they were installed permanent? What was the frequency of distribution?)	Nets were distributed to achieve one LLIN per bed or sleeping place at the beginning of the transmission season in 2014. Each month for the next 4 months after LLIN donation, residents in 5 randomly selected village clusters will be asked to exchange their LLINs for PPF-LLIN. (According to stepped-wedge design)
How was the intervention measured? (e.g. how was net usage monitored/observed by the authors? How was coverage of nets measured?)	Coverage was assessed as number of children who were sleeping under a net, at each survey (4 different time points, survey 1 – June 2014, survey 2 – December 2014, survey 3 – May 2015, survey 4 – July 2015).
Coverage of household / person (% of households with at least 1 ITN % of households with at least 1 ITN for every 2 people % of population with access to an ITN Nets per HH or per person)	29 084 LLINs (24 357 standard and 4727 PPF treated) were distributed to cover the 30 608 sleeping places identified during the pre-study population census, yielding an overall coverage of 95%. This decreased to 92% in survey 1, but then increased to greater than 99% in surveys 2, 3 and 4.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	Coverage exceeded 80% in all clusters except for one in which residents' multiple absences from home for traditional gold-mining activities made it impossible to deliver nets despite numerous attempts
Length of intervention and time points of outcome measurement	Outcomes were measured at 4 different time points (for the cross-sectional surveys, described above). Length of the intervention lasted from June 2014 to December 2015. However as this was a stepped-wedge design, not all clusters experienced the intervention for the same time. (detailed above).
Changes in human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, non-intervention-based spraying of houses)	Collected according to protocol 2, however not reported

Background interventions (all reported in primary study – e.g., spraying prior to treatment period (and during) including coverage of background interventions. Other malaria or vector-specific control interventions [indoor surface treatment, nets/ other insecticides/ barrier], cointerventions, treatment of individuals that may impact outcome)	Burkina Faso Government’s Roll Back Malaria information, education, and communication procedures were followed to encourage correct net use and maintenance for both type of nets.
COMPARISON	
Dual AI net brand, insecticide type, dose, material of net (including active ingredient, timing and frequency of application, durability of the net and insecticide)	Standard LLIN 2% w/w permethrin incorporated into polyethylene fibres giving adequate release of permethrin for about 5 years. The PPF-LLINs were distributed according to the step-wedged design detailed above. The nets were white and sized at 1.8m wide by 1.9m long by 15m high
Net treatment strategy (e.g., how were the nets treated with the insecticide(s))	Chemical content of 30 randomly selected LLINs and 30 PPF-treated LLINs was checked with high-performance liquid chromatography at the Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine (Liverpool, UK), which confirmed the target doses.
Deployment strategy of nets (e.g., who received the nets? Where the houses in which they were installed permanent? What was the frequency of distribution?)	Nets were distributed to achieve one LLIN per bed or sleeping place at the beginning of the transmission season in 2014
How was the intervention measured? (e.g. how was net usage monitored/observed by the authors? How was coverage of nets measured?)	Coverage was assessed as number of children who were sleeping under a net, at each survey (4 different time points, survey 1 – June 2014, survey 2 – December 2014, survey 3 – May 2015, survey 4 – July 2015).
Coverage of household / person (% of households with at least 1 ITN % of households with at least 1 ITN for every 2 people % of population with access to an ITN Nets per HH or per person)	29 084 LLINs (24 357 standard and 4727 PPF treated) were distributed to cover the 30 608 sleeping places identified during the pre-study population census, yielding an overall coverage of 95%. This decreased to 92% in survey 1, but then increased to greater than 99% in surveys 2, 3 and 4.
Coverage across cluster/site/jurisdiction	Coverage exceeded 80% in all clusters except for one in which residents’ multiple absences from home for traditional gold-mining activities made it impossible to deliver nets despite numerous attempts
Length of intervention and time points of outcome measurement	Outcomes were measured at 4 different time points (for the cross-sectional surveys, described above). Length of the intervention lasted from June 2014 to December 2015. However as this was a stepped-wedge design, not all clusters experienced the intervention for the same time. (detailed above).
Changes in human behaviour (e.g., sleeping behaviour, non-intervention-based spraying of houses)	Not reported
Any other details regarding comparator not described elsewhere.	Burkina Faso Government’s Roll Back Malaria information, education, and communication procedures were followed to encourage correct net use and maintenance for both type of nets.
MALARIA CASE INCIDENCE RATE Defined as symptoms plus parasitaemia, over a population at risk or person-time. Detected either through passive or active surveillance.	
Name	As above

Definition/ assessment metric	Incidence of clinical episodes of malaria among cohort children presenting at health facilities. Confirmed through presence of a fever and RDT.
Events	Malaria Episodes Standard LLIN = 1691 PPF-LLIN = 2047
Total (or unit time)	Years of Exposure Standard LLIN = 844 PPF-LLIN = 1351
Time of outcome assessment	Ongoing reporting throughout duration of trial
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	The overall incidence of clinical malaria was 1.5 per child-year at risk in the PPF-treated LLIN group versus 2.0 per child-year at risk in the LLIN group. The adjusted IRR (adjusted for cluster, month and health facility) was 0.88 (0.77-0.99)
Effect type	IRR
MALARIA INFECTION INCIDENCE	
Defined as parasitaemia with or without symptoms, over a population at risk or person-time. Detected through passive or active surveillance.	
Name	N/A
Definition/ assessment metric	N/A
Events	N/A
Total (or unit time)	N/A
Time of outcome assessment	N/A
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	N/A
Effect type	N/A
INCIDENCE OF SEVERE DISEASE	
Defined as hospitalization with parasitaemia, over a population at risk or person-time.	
Name	N/A
Definition/ assessment metric	N/A
Events	N/A
Total (or unit time)	N/A
Time of outcome assessment	N/A
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	N/A
Effect type	N/A
PARASITE PREVALENCE	
Parasitaemia with or without symptoms, over the population sampled. Detected through cross-sectional surveys.	
Name	As above
Definition/ assessment metric	Presence of malaria parasites detected through cross-sectional surveys. Finger prick samples were collected for thick blood films. Children with fever within the last 24 hours were tested for malaria using a RDT.
Events	Survey 1

	Standard LLIN – 851/1627 (52%) PPF-LLIN - ...
	Survey 2 Standard LLIN – 1096/1761 (62%) PPF-LLIN – 1124/1843 (61%)
	Survey 3 Standard LLIN – 604 /1388 (44%) PPF-LLIN – 757/1854 (41%)
	Survey 4 Standard LLIN - ... PPF-LLIN – 2159/3758 (57%)
Total (or unit time)	Reported above
Time of outcome assessment	Survey 1 – June 2014 Survey 2 – December 2014 Survey 3 – May 2015 Survey 4 – July 2015
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	At the second survey, the proportion of children with P falciparum infection was not significantly different between the groups (odds ratio [OR] 0.93, 95% CI 0.74 to 1.15). The authors have not provided a report for the results for survey 3.
Effect type	OR/RR
ALL-CAUSE MORTALITY Number of deaths over the population at risk or person-time.	
Name	As above
Definition/ assessment metric	As above
Events	Standard LLINs = 1 PPF-LLINs = 5
Total (or unit time)	The authors have simply reported that of all 19 serious adverse events encountered six resulted in death.
Time of outcome assessment	Not reported
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	This can only be reported narratively. The authors have not reported the months in which these AEs were encountered, and so we do not have an appropriate denominator to use for analysis
Effect type	Not synthesisable
MALARIA MORTALITY Number of deaths attributed to malaria over the population at risk or person-time.	
Name	N/A
Definition/ assessment metric	N/A
Events	N/A
Total (or unit time)	N/A
Time of outcome assessment	N/A
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	N/A
Effect type	N/A

PREVALENCE OF ANAEMIA	
Defined by study thresholds of anaemia.	
Name	As above
Definition/ assessment metric	Moderate anaemia was defined as haemoglobin concentration of <80g/L Severe anaemia was defined as haemoglobin concentrations of <50g/L. Finger prick samples were collected for haemoglobin measurement at each cross-sectional survey. This was performed using a portable spectrophotometer.
Events	<p>Survey 1 Standard LLIN Moderate – 104/1511 (7%) Severe – 2/1511 (<1%)</p> <p>PPF-LLIN Moderate - ... Severe - ...</p> <p>Survey 2 Standard LLIN Moderate – 113/1768 (6%) Severe – 7/1768 (<1%)</p> <p>PPF-LLIN Moderate - 54/1782 (3%) Severe - 0 (0%)</p> <p>Survey 3 Standard LLIN Moderate – 62/1420 (4%) Severe – 1/1420 (<1%)</p> <p>PPF-LLIN Moderate – 51/1834 (3%) Severe – 0 (0%)</p> <p>Survey 4 Standard LLIN Moderate -... Severe - ...</p> <p>PPF-LLIN Moderate – 62/3726 (2%) Severe – 0 (0%)</p>
Total (or unit time)	As above
Time of outcome assessment	Survey 1 – June 2014 Survey 2 – December 2014 Survey 3 – May 2015 Survey 4 – July 2015
Results (i.e., main results – epidemiological, unadjusted and adjusted, secondary	The prevalence of moderate anaemia was lower in the PPF-treated LLIN

outcomes, sensitivity analyses, subgroups, and clusters)	group than in the standard LLIN group (OR 0.48, 95% CI 0.24–0.96; p=0.04;
Effect type	OR/RR
COSTS	
Event/raw costs	Not reported
Results	Not reported
Time of cost assessment	Not reported
Resources needed/ used	Not reported
ADDITIONAL DATA	
Unintended benefits	Not reported
Harms	<p>There were 21 non-serious adverse events in the standard LLIN group and one in the PPF-treated LLIN group.</p> <p>The PPF-LIN group was a case of bronchitis. The AEs in the standard LLIN-group included bronchitis, conjunctivitis, eye pruritus, pelvic pain, prurities, rhinitis, cough and watering eyes. All of which were resolved by study staff.</p> <p>Severe AEs were also considered. There were 10 SAEs in the standard group and 9 in the PPF-LLIN group. These included severe malaria with other comorbidities, uncomplicated malaria with vomiting, gastroenteritis with severe dehydration and pneumonia. The others have provided the number of each that died (reported above) and were hospitalized (not reported above, as authors have not disambiguated between hospitalization due to malaria and other SAEs).</p>
Other contextual information present/measured/reported) (feasibility, acceptability, preferences/values, impact on equity)	Not reported
Entomological outcomes measured (list)	<p>Protocol 1: Knockdown and mortality rates, egg larvae production. geno and phenotype testing for resistance.</p> <p>Protocol 2: Microscopy confirmed gametocyte carriers (GC), Entomological inoculation rate (EIR), exposure to mosquitos.</p>
Other	The step-wedge design was adopted since it represents the type of deployment used by net distribution programmes.
Source of funding	<p>EU Seventh Framework Programme.</p> <p>Protocol 1 and 2: The study is supported by the European Union Seventh Framework Programme FP7/2007-2013 under grant agreement number 265660, AvecNet. We are grateful to the Sumitomo Chemical Company Limited who will donate the nets for this trial.</p>
Possible conflicts of interest	<p>The funder of the study and net manufacturers had no role in study design, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, or writing of the report.</p> <p>The authors have declared that they have no competing interests.</p>

Domain	Signalling question	Response	Comments
Bias arising from the randomization process	1a.1 Was the allocation sequence random?	Y	Random selection was done with Stata version 10. five randomly selected clusters of
	1a.2 Was the allocation sequence concealed until	NI	

	clusters were enrolled and assigned to interventions?		villages were provided with PPF-treated LLINs and the remaining 35 village clusters with standard LLINs. No information provided regarding allocation concealment
	1a.3 Did baseline differences between intervention groups suggest a problem with the randomization process?	N	This was a stepped-wedged trial
	Risk of bias judgement	Some concerns	Random selection was done with Stata version 10. five randomly selected clusters of villages were provided with PPF-treated LLINs and the remaining 35 village clusters with standard LLINs. No information provided regarding allocation concealment This was a stepped-wedged trial
Bias arising from the timing of identification or recruitment of participants	1b.1 Were all the individual participants identified and recruited (if appropriate) before randomization of clusters?	Y	Participants belonged to households within villages which were then organised into clusters
	1b.2 If N/PN/NI to 1b.1: Is it likely that selection of individual participants was affected by knowledge of the intervention assigned to the cluster?		
	1b.3 Were there baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification or recruitment of individual participants between intervention groups?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Low
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	2.1a Were participants aware that they were in a trial?	Y	All participants had to provide informed consent to receive the intervention or control

	2.1b If Y/PY/NI to 2.1a: Were participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial?	N	both types of nets were of similar shape, size, and colour, and blood films were read by microscopists masked to the identity and intervention status of the participants
	2.2 Were carers and people delivering the interventions aware of participants' assigned intervention during the trial?	N	
	2.3 If Y/PY/NI to 2.1b or 2.2: Were there deviations from the intended intervention that arose because of the trial context?	NA	
	2.4 If Y/PY to 2.3: Were these deviations likely to have affected the outcome?	NA	
	2.5 If Y/PY/NI to 2.4: Were these deviations from intended intervention balanced between groups?	NA	
	2.6 Was an appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention?	Y	Yes ITT was followed
	2.7 If N/PN/NI to 2.6: Was there potential for a substantial impact (on the result) of the failure to analyse participants in the group to which they were randomized ?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	All participants had to provide informed consent to receive the intervention or control both types of nets were of similar shape, size, and colour, and blood films were read by microscopists masked to the identity and intervention status of the participants.
Outcome: Malaria Case Incidence			
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	Only children aged 6 months to 5 years provided outcome data if they presented to a

		health facility with malaria symptoms	
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	Y	This is an appropriate method for assessing this outcome (passive case detection)
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	<p>Only children aged 6 months to 5 years provided outcome data if they presented to a health facility with malaria symptoms</p> <p>This is an appropriate method for assessing this outcome (passive case detection)</p>
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Incidence of clinical episodes of malaria among cohort children presenting at health facilities. Confirmed through presence of a fever and RDT.
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	blood films were read by microscopists masked to the identity and intervention status of the participants
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome	NA	

	was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?		
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	A protocol (2) was provided and followed and there has been full and complete reporting of all outcomes specified.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Outcome: Parasite Prevalence			
Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	N	Children were randomly selected for enrolment in the cross-sectional survey
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	Y	Random selection suggests that the result will not be biased
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	Children were randomly selected for enrolment in the cross-sectional survey Random selection suggests that the result will not be biased
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	Finger prick samples were collected for thick blood films. Children with fever within the last 24 hours were tested for malaria using an RDT.

	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	N	Blood films were read by microscopists masked to the identity and intervention status of the participants
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?	Y	A protocol (2) was provided and followed and there has been full and complete reporting of all outcomes specified.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	Survey data was reported at 4 different time points, however the results of each time point have been reported in full
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	A protocol (2) was provided and followed and there has been full and complete reporting of all outcomes specified. Survey data was reported at 4 different time points, however the results of each time point have been reported in full
Outcome: Prevalence of Anaemia			

Bias due to missing outcome data	3.1a Were data for this outcome available for all clusters that recruited participants?	Y	
	3.1b Were data for this outcome available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters?	Y	
	3.2 If N/PN/NI to 3.1a or 3.1b: Is there evidence that the result was not biased by missing data?	NA	
	3.3 If N/PN to 3.2 Could missingness in the outcome depend on its true value?	NA	
	3.4 If Y/PY/NI to 3.3: Is it likely that missingness in the outcome depended on its true value?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in measurement of the outcome	4.1 Was the method of measuring the outcome inappropriate?	N	
	4.2 Could measurement or ascertainment of the outcome have differed between intervention groups?	N	
	4.3a If N/PN/NI to 4.1 and 4.2: Were outcome assessors aware that a trial was taking place?	Y	
	4.3b If Y/PY/NI to 4.3a: Were outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by study participants?	Y	
	4.4 If Y/PY/NI to 4.3b: Could assessment of the outcome have been influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	N	
	4.5 If Y/PY/NI to 4.4: Is it likely that assessment of the outcome was influenced by knowledge of intervention received?	NA	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	
Bias in selection of the reported result	5.1 Were the data that produced this result analysed in accordance with a pre-specified analysis plan that was finalized	Y	A protocol (2) was provided and followed and there has been full and complete reporting

	before unblinded outcome data were available for analysis?		of all outcomes specified.
	5.2 ... multiple eligible outcome measurements (e.g. scales, definitions, time points) within the outcome domain?	N	
	5.3 ... multiple eligible analyses of the data?	N	
	Risk of bias judgement	Low	A protocol (2) was provided and followed and there has been full and complete reporting of all outcomes specified.

Appendix 4 – All conducted analyses

Supplementary Material to New Nets Analyses and SoF's.

All decisions that were made by the methods team to facilitate meta-analysis have been recorded here. All data have been rounded to the nearest two decimal places.

Accrombessi 2021 –

Intervention 1 – Interceptor G2 (chlorfenapyr (4.8 g/kg) and alpha-cypermethrin (2.4 g/kg))

Intervention 2 -Royal Guard (combination of pyriproxyfen (5.5g/kg) and a-cypermethrin (5.5g/kg))

Comparator - Interceptor LLIN (pyrethroid a-cypermethrin 5g/kg)

Mosha 2022 –

Intervention 1 -Royal Guard (combination of pyriproxyfen (5.5g/kg) and a-cypermethrin (5.5g/kg))

Intervention 2 -Interceptor G2 (chlorfenapyr (4.8 g/kg) and alpha-cypermethrin (2.4 g/kg))

Comparator 1 - Interceptor LLIN (pyrethroid a-cypermethrin 5g/kg)

Comparator 2 - Olyset Plus (combining piperonyl butoxide (10 g/kg) and the pyrethroid permethrin (20 g/kg))

Tiono 2018 –

Intervention - Sumitomo Chemical PPF-LLIN (2% w/w permethrin and 1% w/w pyriproxyfen)

Comparator - Sumitomo Chemical Standard LLIN (2% w/w permethrin)

Analysis 1 – Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid nets versus Pyrethroid-only nets

1.1 Malaria Case Incidence

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomization process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants
- (C) Deviations from intended interventions
- (D) Missing outcome data: Malaria case incidence
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Malaria case incidence
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Malaria case incidence

Figure 1.1

Accrombessi

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

Exposure:

Outcome:	Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-only	Total
Cases	494	897	1392
Person-time	887.3	874.3	1761.7

Rate ratio = 0.54, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.48 to 0.61. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Mosha

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

Exposure:

Outcome:	Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-only	Total
Cases	317	643	960
Person-time	1394.4	1398.5	2792.9

Rate ratio = 0.49, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.43 to 0.57. This was entered as a log sale in RevMan

Baseline risk expressed per 1000 person years

Int	Time	Normalising factor	Control	Time	Normalising factor
811	2281.7	2.28	1540	2272.8	2.27
Int norm	Time norm		Con norm	Time norm	
355.44	1000		677.58	1000	

RD Values

Point Estimate	Lower Estimate	Upper Estimate
189.72	223.60	149.07

These values were calculated by multiplying the normalised control data with the point estimate and confidence intervals derived from the associated forest-plot

1.2 – Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post)

Figure 1.2

Accrombessi

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

Exposure:

Outcome:	Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-only	Total
Cases	124	267	392
Person-time	349.2	344.4	693.6

Rate ratio = 0.458036, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.36713 to 0.568856. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Mosha 2022-

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

Exposure:

Outcome:	Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-only	Total
Cases	79	194	273
Person-time	603.8	605.1	1208.9

Rate ratio = 0.408093, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.310086 to 0.53275. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Baseline risk expressed per 1000 person years

Int	Time	Normalising factor	Control	Time	Normalising factor
203	953	0.95	461	949.5	0.95
Int norm	Time norm		Con norm	Time norm	

213.01	1000	485.52	1000
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RD Values

Point Estimate	Lower Estimate	Upper Estimate
271.89	305.88	233.05

These values were calculated by multiplying the normalised control data with the point estimate and confidence intervals derived from the associated forest-plot

1.3 Malaria Case Incidence (2-year post)

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomization process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants
- (C) Deviations from intended interventions
- (D) Missing outcome data: Malaria case incidence
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Malaria case incidence
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Malaria case incidence

Figure

1.3

Accrombessi

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

Exposure:

Outcome:	Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-only	Total
Cases	370	630	1000
Person-time	538.1	529.9	1068

Rate ratio = 0.578352, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.507293 to 0.658621. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Mosha 2022-

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

Exposure:

Outcome:	Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-only	Total
Cases	248	449	697
Person-time	790.6	793.4	1584

Rate ratio 0.554295, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.472745 to 0.648711. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Baseline risk expressed per 1000 person years

Int	Time	Normalising factor	Control	Time	Normalising factor
618	1329	1.33	1079	1323	1.32
Int norm	Time norm		Con norm	Time norm	

465.12	1000	815.39	1000
--------	------	--------	------

RD Values

Point Estimate	Lower Estimate	Upper Estimate
350.62	399.54	301.69

These values were calculated by multiplying the normalised control data with the point estimate and confidence intervals derived from the associated forest-plot

1.4 Parasite Prevalence (6-months follow-up)

Figure 1.4

Accrombessi 2021

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 6 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

1.5 Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)

Figure 1.5

Mosha 2022

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 12 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

1.6 Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)

Figure 1.6

Accrombessi 2021

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 18 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

Mosha 2022

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 24 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

1.7 Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)

Figure 1.7

Mosha 2022

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 24 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

1.8 Parasite Prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)

Figure 1.8

Accrombessi 2021

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. Have reported the data for 6 months post intervention and 18 months post intervention. The raw data for 18 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

Mosha 2022

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. Have reported the data for 12 months, 18 months and 24 months post intervention. The raw data for 24 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

1.9 Prevalence of Anaemia (6-months follow-up)

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomization process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants
- (C) Deviations from intended interventions
- (D) Missing outcome data: Prevalence of anaemia
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Prevalence of anaemia
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Prevalence of anaemia

Figure

1.9

Accrombessi 2021

Have reported the number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over total number surveyed. The raw data for 6 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

1.10 Prevalence of Anaemia (12-months follow-up)

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomization process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants
- (C) Deviations from intended interventions
- (D) Missing outcome data: Prevalence of anaemia
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Prevalence of anaemia
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Prevalence of anaemia

Figure

1.10

Mosha 2022

Have reported the number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over total number surveyed. The raw data for 12 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

1.11 Prevalence of Anaemia (18-months follow-up)

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomization process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants
- (C) Deviations from intended interventions
- (D) Missing outcome data: Prevalence of anaemia
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Prevalence of anaemia
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Prevalence of anaemia

Figure

1.11

Accrombessi 2021

Have reported the number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over total number surveyed. The raw data for 18 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

Mosha 2022

Have reported the number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over total number surveyed. The raw data for 18 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

1.12 Prevalence of Anaemia (24-months follow-up)

Figure

1.12

Mosha 2022

Have reported the number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over total number surveyed. The raw data for 24 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

1.13 Prevalence of Anaemia (furthest possible follow-up)

Figure 1.13

Accrombessi 2021

Have reported the number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over total number surveyed. Have reported the data for 6 months post intervention and 18 months post intervention. The raw data for 18 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

Mosha 2022

Have reported the number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over total number surveyed. Have reported the data for 12 months, 18 months and 24 months post intervention. The raw data for 24 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

Analysis 2 – Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid nets dual AI nets versus PBO dual AI nets

2.1 Malaria Case Incidence

Figure

2.1

Mosha 2022-

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

Exposure:

Outcome:	Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-PBO	Total
Cases	317	460	777
Person-time	1394.4	1380.7	2775.1

Rate ratio = 0.68236, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.589519 to 0.789033. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Baseline risk expressed per 1000 person years

Int	Time	Normalising factor	Control	Time	Normalising factor
317	1394	1.39	460	1381	1.38
Int norm	Time norm		Con norm	Time norm	
227.34	1000		333.16	1000	

RD Values

Point Estimate	Lower Estimate	Upper Estimate
106.61	136.60	69.96

These values were calculated by multiplying the normalised control data with the point estimate and confidence intervals derived from the associated forest-plot

2.2 Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post)

Figure

2.2

Mosha 2022-

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

	Exposure:		
Outcome:	Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-PBO	Total
Cases	79	79	158
Person-time	603.8	591.8	1195.6

Rate ratio 0.980126, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.70836 to 1.356155. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Baseline risk expressed per 1000 person years

Int	Time	Normalising factor	Control	Time	Normalising factor
79	603.8	0.60	79	591.8	0.59
Int norm	Time norm		Con norm	Time norm	
130.84	1000		133.49	1000	

RD Values

Point Estimate	Lower Estimate	Upper Estimate
2.67	38.71	-48.06

2.3 Malaria Case Incidence (2-years post)

Figure

2.3

Mosha 2022-

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

Exposure:				
Outcome:	Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-PBO	Total	
Cases	248	381	629	
Person-time	790.6	788.9	1579.5	

Rate ratio 0.649519, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.551281 to 0.764158. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Baseline risk expressed per 1000 person years

Int	Time	Normalising factor	Control	Time	Normalising factor
249	790.6	0.79	381	788.9	0.79
Int norm	Time norm		Con norm	Time norm	
314.95	1000		482.95	1000	

RD Values

Point Estimate	Lower Estimate	Upper Estimate
154.54	198.01	101.42

2.4 Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)

Figure

2.4

Mosha 2022

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 12 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

2.5 Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)

Figure

2.5

Mosha 2022

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 18 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

2.6 Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)

Figure 2.6

Mosha 2022

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 24 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

2.7 Prevalence of Anaemia (12-months follow-up)

Figure

2.7

Mosha 2022

Have reported number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 12 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

2.8 Prevalence of Anaemia (18-months follow-up)

Figure

2.8

Mosha 2022

Have reported number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 18 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

2.9 Prevalence of Anaemia (24-months follow-up)

Figure

2.9

Mosha 2022

Have reported number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 24 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

Analysis 3 – Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid nets versus Pyrethroid-only nets

3.1 Malaria Case Incidence

Figure 3.1

Accrombessi

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

Exposure:

Outcome:	Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-only	Total
Cases	744	897	1641
Person-time	883.8	874.3	1758.3

Rate ratio = 0.820516, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.74352 to 0.905279. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Mosha 2022-

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

Exposure:

Outcome:	Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-only	Total
Cases	579	643	1222
Person-time	1391.9	1398.5	2790.4

Rate ratio = 0.904736, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.807238 to 1.013835. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Tiono 2018

Have presented the number of cases by total person years. However as stepped-wedge design have also reported an adjusted estimate that considers month of intervention assignment. The adjusted IRR (adjusted for cluster, month, and health facility) was 0.88 (0.77-0.99). This adjusted estimate was entered into RevMan.

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

Baseline risk expressed per 1000 person years

Int	Time	Normalising factor	Control	Time	Normalising factor
3370	3626.7	3.63	3231	3116.8	3.12
Int norm	Time norm		Con norm	Time norm	
929.22	1000		1036.64	1000	

RD Values

Point Estimate	Lower Estimate	Upper Estimate
145.13	196.96	82.93

These values were calculated by multiplying the normalised control data with the point estimate and confidence intervals derived from the associated forest-plot

3.2 Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post)

(note: data from Tiono not compatible due to step-wedge design)

Figure 3.2

Accrombessi

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

Exposure:

Outcome:	Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-only	Total
Cases	211	267	479
Person-time	342.7	344.4	687.2

Rate ratio = 0.794182, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.659831 to 0.954905. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Mosha 2022-

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

Exposure:

Outcome:	Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-only	Total
Cases	161	194	355
Person-time	604.5	605.1	1209.6

Rate ratio = 0.830721, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.669844 to 1.029091. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Baseline risk expressed per 1000 person years

Int	Time	Normalising factor	Control	Time	Normalising factor
372	947.2	0.95	461	949.5	0.95
Int norm	Time norm		Con norm	Time norm	

392.74 1000 485.52 1000

RD Values

Point Estimate	Lower Estimate	Upper Estimate
92.25	145.66	33.99

These values were calculated by multiplying the normalised control data with the point estimate and confidence intervals derived from the associated forest-plot

3.3 Malaria Case Incidence (2-years post)

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomization process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants
- (C) Deviations from intended interventions
- (D) Missing outcome data: Malaria case incidence
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Malaria case incidence
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Malaria case incidence

Figure 3.3

Accrombessi

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

Exposure:

Outcome:	Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-only	Total
Cases	533	630	1162
Person-time	541.1	529.9	1071.1

Rate ratio = 0.82852, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.659831 to 0.954905. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Moshia 2022-

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

Exposure:

Outcome:	Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-only	Total
Cases	418	449	867
Person-time	787.4	793.4	1580.8

Rate ratio = 0.938052, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.819083 to 1.07412. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Baseline risk expressed per 1000 person years

Int	Time	Normalising factor	Control	Time	Normalising factor
951	1328.5	1.33	1079	1323	1.32
Int norm	Time norm		Con norm	Time norm	
715.84	1000		815.39	1000	

RD Values

Point Estimate	Lower Estimate	Upper Estimate
106.00	163.08	40.77

These values were calculated by multiplying the normalised control data with the point estimate and confidence intervals derived from the associated forest-plot

3.4 Parasite Prevalence (6-months follow-up)

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomization process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants
- (C) Deviations from intended interventions
- (D) Missing outcome data: Parasite prevalence
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Parasite prevalence
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Parasite prevalence

Figure 3.4

Accrombessi 2021

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 6 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

3.5 Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomization process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants
- (C) Deviations from intended interventions
- (D) Missing outcome data: Parasite prevalence
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Parasite prevalence
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Parasite prevalence

Figure 3.5

Mosha 2022

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 12 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

3.6 Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomization process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants
- (C) Deviations from intended interventions
- (D) Missing outcome data: Parasite prevalence
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Parasite prevalence
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Parasite prevalence

Figure 3.6

Accrombessi 2021

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 18 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

Mosha 2022

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 18 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

3.7 Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomization process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants
- (C) Deviations from intended interventions
- (D) Missing outcome data: Parasite prevalence
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Parasite prevalence
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Parasite prevalence

Figure 3.7

Mosha 2022

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 24 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

3.8 Parasite Prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomization process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants
- (C) Deviations from intended interventions
- (D) Missing outcome data: Parasite prevalence
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Parasite prevalence
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Parasite prevalence

Figure 1.8

Accrombessi 2021

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. Have reported the data for 6 months post intervention and 18 months post intervention. The raw data for 18 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

Mosha 2022

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. Have reported the data for 12 months, 18 months and 24 months post intervention. The raw data for 24 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

Tiono 2018

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. Have reported their data from surveys conducted at 4 different time points. As this was a stepped wedge trial, surveys 2 (December 2014) and 3 (May 2015) represent the time points when intervention control ratio was 50:50. Have reported the raw data from survey 3 into RevMan as reported. This was chosen as this was the longest time point post-intervention, where the intervention ratio is 50:50.

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

3.9 Prevalence of Anaemia (6-months follow-up)

Figure

3.9

Accrombessi 2021

Have reported the number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over total number surveyed. The raw data for 6 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

3.10 Prevalence of Anaemia (12-months follow-up)

Figure 3.10

Mosha 2022

Have reported number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 12 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

3.11 Prevalence of Anaemia (18-months follow-up)

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomization process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants
- (C) Deviations from intended interventions
- (D) Missing outcome data: Prevalence of anaemia
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Prevalence of anaemia
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Prevalence of anaemia

Figure 3.11

Accrombessi 2021

Have reported the number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over total number surveyed. The raw data for 18 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

Mosha 2022

Have reported number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 18 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

3.12 Prevalence of Anaemia (24-months follow-up)

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Randomization process
- (B) Timing of identification or recruitment of participants
- (C) Deviations from intended interventions
- (D) Missing outcome data: Prevalence of anaemia
- (E) Measurement of the outcome: Prevalence of anaemia
- (F) Selection of the reported result: Prevalence of anaemia

Figure 3.12

Mosha 2022

Have reported number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 24 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

3.13 Prevalence of Anaemia (furthest possible follow-up)

Figure 3.13

Accrombessi 2021

Have reported the number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over total number surveyed. Have reported their data from at 6, and 18 months post-intervention. The raw data for 18 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

Mosha 2022

Have reported number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over the total number surveyed. Have reported the data for 12 months, 18 months and 24 months post intervention. The raw data for 24 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

Tiono 2018

Have reported number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over the total number surveyed. Have reported their data from surveys conducted at 4 different time points. As this was a stepped wedge trial, surveys 2 (December 2014) and 3 (May 2015) represent the time points when intervention control ratio was 50:50. Have reported the raw data from survey 3 into RevMan as reported. This was chosen as this was the longest time point post-intervention.

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Low Credibility. Likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup, but note remaining uncertainty.

Analysis 4 – Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid dual AI nets versus PBO dual AI nets

4.1 Malaria Case Incidence

Figure

4.1

Mosha 2022-

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

	Exposure:		
Outcome:	Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-PBO	Total
Cases	579	460	1039
Person-time	1391.9	1380.7	2772.6

Rate ratio = 1.248567, exact 95% confidence interval = 1.102793 to 1.414249. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Baseline risk expressed per 1000 person years

Int	Time	Normalising factor	Control	Time	Normalising factor
579	1392	1.39	460	1381	1.38
Int norm	Time norm		Con norm	Time norm	
415.98	1000		333.16	1000	

RD Values

Point Estimate	Lower Estimate	Upper Estimate
-83.29	-33.32	-136.60

These values were calculated by multiplying the normalised control data with the point estimate and confidence intervals derived from the associated forest-plot

4.2 Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post)

Figure

4.2

Mosha 2022-

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

	Exposure:		
Outcome:	Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-PBO	Total
Cases	161	79	240
Person-time	604.5	603.8	1208.3

Rate ratio 2.035615, exact 95% confidence interval = 1.545726 to 2.699528. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Baseline risk expressed per 1000 person years

Int	Time	Normalising factor	Control	Time	Normalising factor
161	604.5	0.60	79	603.8	0.60
Int norm	Time norm		Con norm	Time norm	
266.34	1000		130.84	1000	

RD Values

Point Estimate	Lower Estimate	Upper Estimate
-136.07	-71.96	-219.81

These values were calculated by multiplying the normalised control data with the point estimate and confidence intervals derived from the associated forest-plot

4.3 Malaria Case Incidence (2-year post)

Figure

4.3

Mosha 2022-

Have presented their data by year and also overall as cases per person year. We entered the overall raw data into Stats Direct in order to generate a crude rate ratio as follows:

Exposure:

Outcome:	Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid	Pyrethroid-PBO	Total
Cases	418	381	799
Person-time	787.4	788.9	1576.3

Rate ratio 1.099203, exact 95% confidence interval = 0.954425 to 1.266242. This was entered as a log scale in RevMan

Baseline risk expressed per 1000 person years

Int	Time	Normalising factor	Control	Time	Normalising factor
418	787.4	0.79	381	788.9	0.79
Int norm	Time norm		Con norm	Time norm	
530.86	1000		482.95	1000	

RD Values

Point Estimate	Lower Estimate	Upper Estimate
-48.30	24.15	-130.40

These values were calculated by multiplying the normalised control data with the point estimate and confidence intervals derived from the associated forest-plot

4.4 Parasite Prevalence (12-months follow-up)

Figure 4.4

Mosha 2022

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 12 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

4.5 Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)

Figure 4.5

Mosha 2022

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 18 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

4.6 Parasite Prevalence (24-months follow-up)

Figure 4.6

Mosha 2022

Have reported infection prevalence as number of those who tested positive over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 24 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

4.7 Prevalence of Anaemia (12-months follow-up)

Figure 4.7

Mosha 2022

Have reported number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 12 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

4.8 Prevalence of Anaemia (18-months follow-up)

Figure 4.8

Mosha 2022

Have reported number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 18 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

4.9 Prevalence of Anaemia (24-months follow-up)

Figure 4.9

Mosha 2022

Have reported number of anaemic children (Hb concentrations) over the total number surveyed. The raw data for 24 months post-intervention has been entered into RevMan as reported.

Subgroup analyses (With ICEMAN Assessments)

Vector Species (Funestus or Gambiae/Coluzzi)

Analysis 5 – Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid nets versus Pyrethroid-only nets

5.1 Malaria case incidence

Figure 5.1

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Low Credibility. Likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup, but note remaining uncertainty

5.2 Malaria case incidence (1-year post)

Figure 5.2

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

5.3 Malaria case incidence (2-year post)

Figure 5.2

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

5.4 Parasite prevalence (18-months follow-up)

Figure 5.4

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

5.5 Parasite prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)

Figure 5.5

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Low Credibility. Likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup, but note remaining uncertainty

5.6 Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)

Figure 5.6

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

5.7 Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible follow-up)

Figure 5.7

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

Analysis 6 – Chlorfenapyr-pyrethroid nets versus Pyrethroid-onlynets

Setting (Rural or Mixed)

6.1 Malaria case incidence (overall)

Figure 6.1

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Low Credibility. Likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup, but note remaining uncertainty

6.2 Malaria case incidence (1-year post)

Figure 6.2

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

6.3 Malaria case incidence (1-year post)

Figure 6.3

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

6.4 Parasite prevalence (18-months follow-up)

Figure 6.4

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

6.5 Parasite prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)

Figure 6.5

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Low Credibility. Likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup, but note remaining uncertainty

6.6 Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)

Figure 6.6

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

6.7 Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible follow-up)

Figure 6.7

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

Vector Species (Funestus or Gambiae/Coluzzi)

Analysis 7 – Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid nets versus Pyrethroid-only nets

7.1 Malaria case incidence (overall)

Figure 7.1

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

7.2 Malaria case incidence (1-year post intervention)

Figure 7.2

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very low Credibility. Likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup, but note remaining uncertainty

7.3 Malaria case incidence (2-year post intervention)

Figure 7.3

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very low Credibility. Likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup, but note remaining uncertainty

7.4 Parasite prevalence (18-months follow-up)

Figure 7.4

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

7.5 Parasite prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)

Figure 7.5

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Low Credibility. Likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup, but note remaining uncertainty

7.6 Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)

Figure 7.6

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

7.7 Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible follow-up)

Figure 7.7

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

Analysis 8 – Pyriproxyfen-pyrethroid nets versus Pyrethroid-only nets

Setting (Rural or Mixed)

8.1 Malaria case incidence (overall)

Figure 8.1

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

8.2 Malaria case incidence (1-year post)

Figure 8.2

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

8.3 Malaria case incidence (2-year post)

Figure 8.3

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

8.4 Parasite prevalence (18-months follow-up)

Figure 8.4

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Low Credibility. Likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup, but note remaining uncertainty

8.5 Parasite prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)

Figure 8.5

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

8.6 Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)

Figure 8.6

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

8.7 Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible follow-up)

Figure 8.7

ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Very Low Credibility. Very likely no effect modification. Use overall effect for each subgroup.

Appendix 5 – ICEMAN Credibility Assessments

Active ingredient/manufacture subgroup

Preliminary considerations

Study reference(s):

If available, protocol reference(s):

State a single outcome and, if applicable, time-point of interest (e.g., mortality at 1 year follow-up):

State a single effect measure of interest (e.g., relative or absolute risk difference):

State a single potential effect modifier of interest (e.g., age or comorbidity):

Was the potential effect modifier measured before or at randomization? yes, continue no, stop here and refer to manual for further instructions

Credibility assessment

1: Is the analysis of effect modification based on comparison within rather than between trials?

Completely between Mostly between or unclear Mostly within Completely within

Subgroup analysis or meta-analysis of individual trial information coming from overall individual participant data; and This is typical for aggregate data effects, but some trials providing analysis that combines within the analysis separates within meta-analysis. *Subgroup analysis or meta-analysis of individual trial information coming from overall individual participant data; and This is typical for aggregate data effects, but some trials providing analysis that combines within the analysis separates within meta-analysis.* *Most trials providing within-trial information; or subgroup information or effects of each individual trial.* *All trials providing within-trial information; or subgroup information or effects of each individual trial.* *within-trial subgroup and between trial information from between trial information, e.g., meta-analysis of interactions*

Comment:

2: For within-trial comparisons, is the effect modification similar from trial to trial? Not applicable: no or one within-RCT comparison

Definitely not similar Probably not similar or unclear Mostly similar Definitely similar

Effect modification reported for two or more trials and clearly for individual trials or in different directions *Effect modification not reported for two or more trials, mostly similar in direction, but differences in magnitude* *Effect modification reported for two or more trials, similar in direction, but considerable differences in magnitude* *Effect modification reported for two or more trials, similar in direction, but differences in magnitude*

Comment:

3: For between-trial comparisons, is the number of trials large? Not applicable: no between RCT comparison

Very small Rather small or unclear Rather large Large

1 or 2 or in smallest subgroup; 5 or less in continuous meta-regression *3-4 in smallest subgroup; 6-10 in continuous meta-regression* *5-9 in smallest subgroup; 15 in continuous meta-regression* *11 to 10 or more in smallest subgroup; more than 15 in continuous meta-regression*

Comment:

4: Was the direction of effect modification correctly hypothesized a priori?

Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes

Clearly post-hoc or results inconsistent with hypothesized direction or biologically very implausible *Vague hypothesis or No prior protocol available but includes correct specification of direction of effect modification, e.g., based on a biologic rationale* *Unclear within studies and not hypothesised for this meta-analysis.* *Prior protocol available and includes correct specification of direction of effect modification, e.g., based on a biologic rationale*

Comment:

5: Does a test for interaction suggest that chance is an unlikely explanation of the apparent effect modification? (consider irrespective of number of effect modifiers)

Chance a very likely explanation Chance a likely explanation or unclear Chance may not explain Chance an unlikely explanation

Interaction or meta-regression p-value >0.05 Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.05 and >0.01, or no test of interaction reported and not computable Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.01 and >0.005 Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.005

Royal Guard v Standard Parasite Prevalence
 Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.57

not computable

Royal Guard v Standard Malaria Case
 Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.02
Prevalence of Anaemia
 Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.08

Interceptor G2 v Standard Parasite Prevalence
 Test for differences between subgroups p = <0.001

Interceptor G2 v Standard Malaria Case
 Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.38

Interceptor G2 v Standard Prevalence of Anaemia
 Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.07

Comment:

6: Did the authors test only a small number of effect modifiers or consider the number in their statistical analysis?

Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes

Explicitly exploratory analysis or No mention of number or 4-10 No protocol available but large number of effect modifiers effect modifiers tested and unequivocal statement of 3 or effect modifiers tested or tested (e.g., greater than 10) and number not considered in fewer effect modifiers tested number considered in analysis multiplicity not considered in analysis analysis

Comment:

7: Did the authors use a random effects model?

Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes

Fixed (or common) effect or fixed effects model explicitly stated Probably fixed effect(s) model Probably random (or mixed) effects Random (or mixed) effects explicitly stated

Comment:

8: If the effect modifier is a continuous variable, were arbitrary cut points avoided? not applicable: not continuous

Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes

Analysis based on exploratory Analysis based on cut point(s) of Analysis based on pre-specified Analysis based on the full cut point(s), e.g., picking cut unclear origin cut point(s), e.g., suggested by continuum, e.g., assuming a point associated with highest prior RCT linear or logarithmic relationship interaction p-value

Comment:

9 Optional: Are there any additional considerations that may increase or decrease credibility? (manual section 3.9) not applicable

Yes, probably decrease Yes, probably increase

Comment:

10: How would you rate the overall credibility of the proposed effect modification?

The overall rating should be driven by the items that decrease credibility. The following provides a sensible strategy:

- All responses definitely or probably decrease credibility or unclear → very low
- Two or more responses definitely decrease credibility → maximum usually low even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
- One response definitely decreases credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
- Two responses probably decrease credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
- No response options definitely or probably decrease credibility → high very likely

Place a mark on the continuous line (or type "x" in editable version)

Comment:

Setting subgroup

Preliminary considerations

Study reference(s):

If available, protocol reference(s):

State a single outcome and, if applicable, time-point of interest (e.g., mortality at 1 year follow-up):

State a single effect measure of interest (e.g., relative or absolute risk difference):

State a single potential effect modifier of interest (e.g., age or comorbidity):

Was the potential effect modifier measured before or at randomization? yes, continue no, stop here and refer to manual for further instructions

Credibility assessment

1: Is the analysis of effect modification based on comparison within rather than between trials?

Completely between Mostly between or unclear Mostly within Completely within

Subgroup analysis or meta-analysis or meta-regression comparing overall effects of each individual trial. information coming from overall individual participant data individual participant data; and This is typical for aggregate data effects, but some trials providing analysis that combines within the analysis separates within meta-analysis. within-trial subgroup and between trial information from between trial information, e.g., meta-analysis of interactions

Comment:

2: For within-trial comparisons, is the effect modification similar from trial to trial? Not applicable: no or one within-RCT comparison

Definitely not similar Probably not similar or unclear Mostly similar Definitely similar

Effect modification reported for two or more trials and clearly for individual trials or in different directions Effect modification not reported for two or more trials, mostly similar in direction, but considerable differences in magnitude Effect modification reported for two or more trials, similar in direction, but considerable differences in magnitude Effect modification reported for two or more trials, similar in direction, but considerable differences in magnitude

Comment:

3: For between-trial comparisons, is the number of trials large? Not applicable: no between RCT comparison

Very small Rather small or unclear Rather large Large

1 or 2 or in smallest subgroup; 5 or less in continuous meta-regression 3-4 in smallest subgroup; 6-10 in continuous meta-regression 5-9 in smallest subgroup; 11 to 15 in continuous meta-regression 10 or more in smallest subgroup; more than 15 in continuous meta-regression

Comment:

4: Was the direction of effect modification correctly hypothesized a priori?

Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes

Clearly post-hoc or results inconsistent with hypothesized direction or implausible Vague hypothesis or hypothesized direction unclear hypothesis No prior protocol available but unequivocal statement of a priori hypothesis with correct direction of effect modification e.g., based on a biologic rationale Prior protocol available and includes correct specification of direction of effect modification e.g., based on a biologic rationale

Comment:

5: Does a test for interaction suggest that chance is an unlikely explanation of the apparent effect modification? (consider irrespective of number of effect modifiers)

Chance a very likely explanation Chance a likely explanation or unclear Chance may not explain Chance an unlikely explanation

Interaction or meta-regression p-value >0.05 Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.05 and >0.01, or no test of interaction reported and not computable Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.01 and >0.005 Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.005

Royal Guard v Standard

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.20

Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.74

Malaria Case Incidence (2-year post)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.17

Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible time point)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.97

Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible time point)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.42

Interceptor G2 v Standard

Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.53

Malaria Case Incidence (2-year post)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.69

Parasite prevalence (18-months)

Royal Guard v Standard

Parasite Prevalence (18-months)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.01

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.03

Interceptor G2 v Standard

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.0002

Parasite Prevalence (furthest possible time point)

Test for differences between subgroups p < 0.0001

Test for differences between subgroups $p = 0.25$

Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible time point)

Test for differences between subgroups $p = 0.21$

Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible time point)

Test for differences between subgroups $p = 0.06$

Comment:

6: Did the authors test only a small number of effect modifiers or consider the number in their statistical analysis?

Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes

Explicitly exploratory analysis or No mention of number or 4-10 No protocol available but Protocol available and 3 or fewer large number of effect modifiers effect modifiers tested and unequivocal statement of 3 or effect modifiers tested or tested (e.g., greater than 10) and number not considered in fewer effect modifiers tested number considered in analysis multiplicity not considered in analysis analysis

Comment:

7: Did the authors use a random effects model?

Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes

Fixed (or common) effect or fixed Probably fixed effect(s) model Probably random (or mixed) Random (or mixed) effects effects model explicitly stated effects explicitly stated

Comment:

8: If the effect modifier is a continuous variable, were arbitrary cut points avoided? not applicable: not continuous

Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes

Analysis based on exploratory Analysis based on cut point(s) of Analysis based on pre-specified Analysis based on the full cut point(s), e.g., picking cut unclear origin cut point(s), e.g., suggested by continuum, e.g., assuming a point associated with highest prior RCT linear or logarithmic relationship interaction p-value

Comment:

9 Optional: Are there any additional considerations that may increase or decrease credibility? (manual section 3.9) not applicable

Yes, probably decrease Yes, probably increase

Comment:

10: How would you rate the overall credibility of the proposed effect modification?

The overall rating should be driven by the items that decrease credibility. The following provides a sensible strategy:

- All responses definitely or probably decrease credibility or unclear → very low
- Two or more responses definitely decrease credibility → maximum usually low even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
- One response definitely decreases credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
- Two responses probably decrease credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
- No response options definitely or probably decrease credibility → high very likely

Place a mark on the continuous line (or type "x" in editable version)

Very low credibility	Low credibility	Moderate credibility	High credibility
Very likely no effect modification Use overall effect for each subgroup	Likely no effect modification Use overall effect for each subgroup but note remaining uncertainty	Likely effect modification Use separate effects for each subgroup but note remaining uncertainty	Very likely effect modification Use separate effects for each subgroup
<u><i>Royal Guard v Standard</i></u>	<u><i>Royal Guard v Standard</i></u>		
<u><i>Malaria Case Incidence (overall)</i></u>	<u><i>Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)</i></u>		
<u><i>Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post)</i></u>	<u><i>Interceptor G2 v Standard</i></u>		
	<u><i>Malaria Case Incidence (overall)</i></u>		
	<u><i>Malaria Case Incidence (2-year post)</i></u>		
	<u><i>Parasite Prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)</i></u>		
	<u><i>Parasite Prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)</i></u>		
	<u><i>Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)</i></u>		
	<u><i>Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible follow-up)</i></u>		
	<u><i>Interceptor G2 v Standard</i></u>		

Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post)

Malaria case Incidence (2-years post)

Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)

Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)

Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible follow-up)

Comment:

Vector subgroup

Preliminary considerations

Study reference(s):

If available, protocol reference(s):

State a single outcome and, if applicable, time-point of interest (e.g., mortality at 1 year follow-up):

State a single effect measure of interest (e.g., relative or absolute risk difference):

State a single potential effect modifier of interest (e.g., age or comorbidity):

Was the potential effect modifier measured before or at randomization? yes, continue no, stop here and refer to manual for further instructions

Credibility assessment

1: Is the analysis of effect modification based on comparison within rather than between trials?

Completely between Mostly between or unclear Mostly within Completely within

Subgroup analysis or meta-analysis or meta-regression comparing overall effects of each individual trial. information coming from overall individual participant data individual participant data; and This is typical for aggregate data effects, but some trials providing analysis that combines within the analysis separates within meta-analysis. within-trial subgroup and between trial information from between trial information, e.g., meta-analysis of interactions

Comment:

2: For within-trial comparisons, is the effect modification similar from trial to trial? Not applicable: no or one within-RCT comparison

Definitely not similar Probably not similar or unclear Mostly similar Definitely similar

Effect modification reported for two or more trials and clearly for individual trials or in different directions Effect modification not reported for two or more trials, mostly similar in direction, but considerable differences in magnitude Effect modification reported for two or more trials, similar in direction, only some differences in magnitude Effect modification reported for two or more trials, similar in direction, only some differences in magnitude

Comment:

3: For between-trial comparisons, is the number of trials large? Not applicable: no between RCT comparison

Very small Rather small or unclear Rather large Large

1 or 2 or in smallest subgroup; 5 or less in continuous meta-regression 3-4 in smallest subgroup; 6-10 in continuous meta-regression 5-9 in smallest subgroup; 11 to 15 in continuous meta-regression 10 or more in smallest subgroup; more than 15 in continuous meta-regression

Comment:

4: Was the direction of effect modification correctly hypothesized a priori?

Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes

Clearly post-hoc or results inconsistent with hypothesized direction or implausible Vague hypothesis or hypothesized direction unclear No prior protocol available but unequivocal statement of a priori hypothesis with correct direction of effect modification e.g., based on a biologic rationale Prior protocol available and includes correct specification of direction of effect modification e.g., based on a biologic rationale

Comment:

5: Does a test for interaction suggest that chance is an unlikely explanation of the apparent effect modification? (consider irrespective of number of effect modifiers)

Chance a very likely explanation Chance a likely explanation or unclear Chance may not explain Chance an unlikely explanation

Interaction or meta-regression p-value >0.05 Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.05 and >0.01, or no test of interaction reported and not computable Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.01 and >0.005 Interaction or meta-regression p-value ≤0.005

Royal Guard v Standard

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.82

Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.74

Malaria Case Incidence (2-year post)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.17

Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.66

Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.97

Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible follow-up)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.28

Interceptor G2 v Standard

Malaria Case Incidence (1- year post)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.53

Malaria Case Incidence (2- year post)

Royal Guard v Standard

Parasite Prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)

Test for differences between subgroups p = 0.004

Interceptor G2 v Standard

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

Test for differences between subgroups p < 0.0001

Parasite Prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)

Test for differences between subgroups p < 0.0001

Test for differences between subgroups $p = 0.69$

Parasite Prevalence (18-months follow-up)

Test for differences between subgroups $p = 0.25$

Prevalence of anaemia (18-months follow-up)

Test for differences between subgroups $p = 0.21$

Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible follow-up)

Test for differences between subgroups $p = 0.85$

Comment:

6: Did the authors test only a small number of effect modifiers or consider the number in their statistical analysis?

Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes

Explicitly exploratory analysis or No mention of number or 4-10 No protocol available but Protocol available and 3 or fewer large number of effect modifiers effect modifiers tested and unequivocal statement of 3 or effect modifiers tested or tested (e.g., greater than 10) and number not considered in fewer effect modifiers tested number considered in analysis multiplicity not considered in analysis analysis

Comment:

7: Did the authors use a random effects model?

Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes

Fixed (or common) effect or fixed Probably fixed effect(s) model Probably random (or mixed) Random (or mixed) effects effects model explicitly stated effects explicitly stated

Comment:

8: If the effect modifier is a continuous variable, were arbitrary cut points avoided? not applicable: not continuous

Definitely no Probably no or unclear Probably yes Definitely yes

Analysis based on exploratory Analysis based on cut point(s) of Analysis based on pre-specified Analysis based on the full cut point(s), e.g., picking cut unclear origin cut point(s), e.g., suggested by continuum, e.g., assuming a point associated with highest interaction p-value prior RCT linear or logarithmic relationship

Comment:

9 Optional: Are there any additional considerations that may increase or decrease credibility? (manual section 3.9) not applicable

Yes, probably decrease Yes, probably increase

Comment:

10: How would you rate the overall credibility of the proposed effect modification?

The overall rating should be driven by the items that decrease credibility. The following provides a sensible strategy:

- All responses definitely or probably decrease credibility or unclear → very low
- Two or more responses definitely decrease credibility → maximum usually low even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
- One response definitely decreases credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
- Two responses probably decrease credibility → maximum usually moderate even if all other responses satisfy credibility criteria
- No response options definitely or probably decrease credibility → high very likely

Place a mark on the continuous line (or type "x" in editable version)

Very low credibility **Low credibility** **Moderate credibility** **High credibility**

Very likely no effect modification Likely no effect modification Likely effect modification Very likely effect modification
Use overall effect for each subgroup but note remaining uncertainty Use overall effect for each subgroup but note remaining uncertainty Use separate effects for each subgroup but note remaining uncertainty Use separate effects for each subgroup

Royal Guard

Royal Guard

Malaria Case Incidence (overall)

Parasite Prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)

Interceptor G2

Malaria Case Incidence (1-year post) (overall)

Malaria Case Incidence (2-year post) (overall)

Parasite Prevalence (furthest possible follow-up)

Parasite Prevalence (18-month follow-up)

Prevalence of anaemia (furthest possible follow-up)

Interceptor G2

Malaria Case Incidence (1-year)

Parasite Prevalence (18-month follow-up)

[Prevalence of anaemia \(18-months follow-up\)](#)

[Prevalence of anaemia \(furthest possible follow-up\)](#)

Comment:

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